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[Implementation and benchmarking of models]

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¹ R= Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA =Data sets, microdata, etc.; DMP = Data management plan; ETHICS = Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY = Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER = Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

² PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R = EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C = EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S = EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

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Acronyms Listed in this Document	
AA	Atom Attention
AE	Accumulated Exceedance
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
AOP	Adverse Outcome Pathway
APD	Applicability Domain
API	Application Programming Interface
autoML	Automated Machine Learning
BMA	Bayesian Average Modeling
BMD	Benchmark Dose
BMR	Benchmark Response
BSA	Bovine Serum Albumin
CCK	Cell Counting Kit
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CG	Coarse-Grained
CIF	Crystallographic Information File
CL	Child Labour
CSS	Chemical Strategy for Sustainability
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DD	Dose-Dependent
DEG	Differentially Expressed Gene
DFT	Density Functional Theory

DMEM	Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium
EC50	Effective Concentration 50
EC	European Commission
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EDM	Equilibrium Distribution Modeling
EG	Ethylene Glycol
EMMC	European Materials Modelling Council
ENV	Environment
EPA	[United States] Environmental Protection Agency
EU	European Union
EZ_Cyto	EZ-Cytotoxicity
FABP	Fatty Acid Binding Protein
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FBS	Fetal Bovine Serum
FDR	False Discovery Rate
FF	Fate Factor
FS	Fair Salary
GA	Glycolic Acid
GCNN	Graph Convolutional Neural Network
GFR	Glomerular Filtration Rate
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GHGF	Greenhouse Gas Footprints
GUI	Graphical User Interface
GRM	Graphene-related materials

HCI	High Content Imaging
HH	Human Health
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTS	High Throughput Screening
IDH	Intracellular Dehydrogenase
IOP	Impact Outcome Pathway
IRFMN	Mario Negri Institute for Pharmacological Research
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KE	Key Event
KNIME	Konstanz Information Miner
kNN	k-Nearest Neighbour
LC50	Lethal Concentration 50
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
LDPE	Low-Density Polyethylene
LGO	Larger Graphene Oxide
LMC	Laboratory of Mathematical Chemistry
MCMC	Markov Chain Monte Carlo
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
MODA	Modelling Data
MPNN	Message-Passing Neural Network
MTT	3-(4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-Diphenyltetrazolium Bromide
MW	Molecular Weight

MWCNT	Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotube
NAM	New Approach Methodologies
NM	Nanomaterial
NMP	Nano- and Microplastics
NP	Nanoparticle
Nucleo	Nucleocounter
NUTS	No U-Turn Sampler
OECD	Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development
PBK	Physiologically based kinetic models
PBPK	Physiologically based pharmacokinetic models
PDB	Protein Data Bank
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
PFAS	Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances
PFBS	Perfluorobutanesulfonic acid
PFHxS	Perfluorohexanesulfonic acid
PFNA	Perfluorononanoic acid
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic acid
PFOS	Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid
PI	Propidium Iodide
POD	Point of Departure
PP	Polypropylene
PVA	Poly-Vinyl-Alcohol
QNAR	Quantitative Nanostructure-Activity
QSAR	Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship

QSPR	Quantitative Structure Property Relationship
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
REST	Representational State Transfer
RIVM	[Duch] National Institute for Public Health and the Environment
RPMI	Roswell Park Memorial Institute medium
SB4P	SimpleBox4Plastic
SDF	Spatial Data File
SDK	Software Development Kit
SGO	Small Graphene Oxide
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations
SMILES	Simplified Molecular Input Line Systems
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
STOT - RE	Specific Target Organ Toxicity – Repeated Exposure
STOT - SE	Specific Target Organ Toxicity – Single Exposure
TEM	Transmission Electron Microscopy
TDA	Toluene di-isocyanate metabolites
TDI	Toluene di-isocyanate
twPOD	Transcriptome-Wide Points of Departure
UI	User Interface
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
USGO	Ultra-Small Graphene Oxide
WP	Work Package
WST	Water-Soluble Tetrazolium
XGBoost	Extreme Gradient Boosting

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.2 documents the implementation, integration, and benchmarking of models that collectively form the INSIGHT model graph, building on the comprehensive model inventory established in Deliverable 2.1. A total of 43 tools have been integrated or updated, 21 of which are newly developed, covering key domains such as exposure assessment, physiologically based kinetic (PBK) modelling, quantitative structure activity relationship (QSAR)/quantitative structure property relationship (QSPR) prediction, toxicogenomics-based hazard evaluation, environmental fate, materials engineering, and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA).

A harmonised and modular implementation strategy was applied to ensure that all models operate as interoperable service nodes accessible through standardised representational state transfer (REST) application programming Interfaces (APIs) and graphical user interfaces (GUIs). Mechanistic models (e.g., PBK and environmental fate) are combined with artificial intelligence (AI)-based models (e.g., deep learning, QSAR) to provide comprehensive predictive and mechanistic coverage across human health, environmental, social, and sustainability dimensions. Dose-dependent toxicogenomics analysis tools (BMDx, AOPFingerprint, and the integrated BMDx2 platform) further enable mechanistic characterisation.

Benchmarking procedures were applied to evaluate model performance, robustness, and reliability. In parallel, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)-by-design principles guided the development and integration of all models. This includes consistent metadata, definition of input–output parameters, documented APIs, and hosting within established cloud platforms for easy access.

The result is a comprehensive modelling landscape that covers key Safe and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) indicators, including hazard, exposure, kinetic behaviour, and risk-related endpoints, while also incorporating tools for social and sustainability assessment. This modelling infrastructure interacts seamlessly with the WP3 data graph and feeds directly into the construction of Impact Outcome Pathways (WP4), thereby strengthening the mechanistic and predictive foundations of the INSIGHT SSbD framework.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Description of Task 2.2

Task 2.2 builds on the foundations established in Task 2.1, which focused on identifying, collecting, and cataloguing existing models relevant to the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework. The resulting compendium of models (D2.1) provided a detailed mapping of available tools, their input–output structures, their level of FAIRness, and their alignment with SSbD indicators.

The objective of Task 2.2 was to operationalize the models identified in Task 2.1 and to develop new models that extend the INSIGHT model graph. Collectively, these activities enhanced the predictive, and mechanistic dimensions of the INSIGHT framework, particularly in areas where Deliverable 2.1 revealed gaps in methodological coverage or endpoint representation. Task 2.2 also ensured that both existing and newly developed models are accessible through standardized Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and prepared for full integration and seamless interaction with the data graph and the Impact Outcome Pathway (IOP) framework.

Deliverable 2.2 therefore focuses on the following activities:

- Integrating existing models and developing new ones, including toxicogenomics analysis approaches, Physiologically-Based Kinetic (PBK) and Quantitative-Structure Activity-Relationship (QSAR) models, environmental fate assessment frameworks, and life Cycle Analysis (LCA) tools.
- Benchmarking model performance using standardized evaluation protocols.
- Applying ensemble and consensus learning strategies to improve predictive accuracy and strengthen uncertainty quantification.
- Ensuring models follow FAIR principles and are API-accessible.

Overall, Task 2.2 marks the transition from the collection and mapping of models (D2.1) to their operational integration, evaluation, and alignment with INSIGHT’s requirements.

1.2. The INSIGHT SSbD Framework

INSIGHT aims to integrate the current SSbD framework, by taking into account the mechanistic evaluation of the chemical impact based on integrated and mechanistic impact assessment. INSIGHT will expand the Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) framework to accommodate mechanistic considerations for impact assessment, by developing an integrated framework based on the novel concept of IOP. IOPs will be developed for each safety and sustainability area of concern (health, environment, society, economics) within the SSbD framework. The IOPs will support the development of an integrated SSbD framework including regulatory decision rules and visualization, and can facilitate organization of existing knowledge, identification of knowledge gaps, development of quantitative models, and systematic design of impact assessment strategies.

Figure 1: The INSIGHT framework for integrated impact assessment and SSbD

INSIGHT adopts a multi-layer structure comprising the data graph (WP3), the model graph (WP2), and the IOP graph (WP4), which collectively support the prediction and assessment of environmental, economic, social, and health impacts of chemicals and materials (Figure 1). Within this architecture, the model graph plays a central role. It serves as the computational engine that transforms raw data into meaningful predictions and mechanistic insights that are subsequently linked to impact pathways. Each model functions as a node, linked through defined inputs and outputs relationships, forming a coherent and interoperable modelling ecosystem. The model graph builds on the diverse data representations supplied by the data graph and integrates a broad range of modelling approaches. Advanced statistical, machine-learning, and mechanistic models - including QSAR, PBK, read-across, LCA, environmental fate and toxicogenomics-based approaches - are incorporated to generate predictions and to strengthen mechanistic understanding. Accordingly, the focus of this deliverable is

to document the construction, integration, and functionality of the nodes that make up the INSIGHT model graph.

2. Model and Tool implementation

2.1. Development Model Strategy

The model development strategy adopted in Task 2.2 was designed to transform the descriptive compendium established in Deliverable 2.1 into an operational, interoperable, and extensible modelling ecosystem. The overall objective was to develop or integrate new models and enhance existing ones so that the INSIGHT model graph provides comprehensive coverage of relevant impact dimensions - human health, environmental, social, and sustainability - while ensuring full compatibility with the SSbD framework and the IOP concept.

The approach follows a three-pillar strategy:

- Modular and harmonised implementation,
- Mechanistic and data-driven model integration
- FAIR-by-design deployment.

Each pillar is detailed below:

2.1.1. Modular and Harmonised Implementation

To ensure interoperability, every model - whether newly developed or adapted from existing tools - follows a common implementation strategy that harmonises input–output specifications and integration interfaces across all components. This includes exposing each model through a REST-compliant API for programmatic access and automated execution within INSIGHT workflows, providing graphical user interfaces where needed to support non-expert users, and applying consistent, well-defined input–output formats that allow models to reliably consume and produce compatible data objects (e.g., Simplified Molecular Input Line Systems (SMILES) strings, physicochemical descriptors, exposure concentrations etc.). This modular design ensures that each model functions as a self-contained service node within the model graph, interacting through well-defined interfaces while remaining replaceable or upgradable without disrupting the overall architecture.

2.1.2. Mechanistic and Data Driven Model Integration

INSIGHT brings together mechanistic and AI-based modelling to achieve a holistic understanding of chemical behaviour and impact. The models developed in Task 2.2 fall into three complementary categories. Mechanistic models - such as PBK and environmental fate models - simulate how substances distribute, transform, and accumulate in organisms and ecosystems, while toxicogenomics analysis tools, when integrated with AOP-based frameworks, help link dose-dependent molecular responses to the biological events that lead to adverse outcomes. Data-driven models (such as QSAR, read-across) predict various SSbD indicators and functional properties from structured data. Consensus models aggregate outputs from multiple models to produce more reliable and robust predictions. All models follow a common development pipeline. Data curation and harmonisation ensure that datasets collected from open sources and case studies are validated and consistent. Model validation involves internal cross-validation and external benchmarking with independent datasets, using standard performance metrics. Interpretability and transparency in many data-driven models are supported through explainable-AI methods (e.g., SHapley additive explanations-SHAP), which highlight the most influential descriptors and facilitate regulatory acceptance.

2.1.3. FAIR-by-Design Deployment

FAIRness principles were embedded in the model development process by building on the findings of Deliverable 2.1, which assessed the initial FAIRness status of the internal models and tools collected across the consortium. The gaps and strengths identified in D2.1 informed the design choices applied in Task 2.2, ensuring that all newly developed or integrated models moved toward a FAIR-by-design standard. During implementation, findability was improved by assigning stable identifiers and maintaining consistent metadata. Accessibility was addressed by deploying models through open, standard protocols and enabling programmatic interaction via REST APIs. Interoperability was strengthened through well defined input–output structures and the use of widely supported data formats that allow seamless data exchange. Reusability was enhanced by providing clear documentation and long-term hosting on stable platforms. Together, these actions ensured that the development, integration, and deployment of the models described in this deliverable resulted in a set of tools that are robust, transparent, and aligned with FAIR principles to support SSbD decision-making.

2.2. List of tools

The list of integrated tools presented in D2.1 has been revised and extended, and 43 tools have been updated (including 21 new tools). These tools comprise 2 environmental fate models, 4 exposure models, 9 PBK models, 16 QSAR and QSAR-type models, 2 models for hazard prediction based on new approach methodologies (NAMs)/in vivo, 14 materials engineering-oriented tools, 1 LCA software package, and 1 tool for standardized reporting of models (see also Figure 2 - modelling platforms are not included in the reported categories). The updated list includes 2 new external tools (MicroPlasticFate and INSIGHT LCA REST API). In Tables 1 (internal tools) and 2 (external) the tools are described, including their main objective, location (e.g., link to available code, to the download page or to the log-in page), type of tool and developer. The integrated tools further enrich the compendium of models and tools of the INSIGHT model graph, covering more computational areas (e.g., materials engineering tools).

Figure 2: Categories of tools integrated within the INSIGHT model graph.

Table I: Development of internal models

Tool Name	Objective	Location	APIs	Doc ker	GUI	Programming language/ application type	Category	Developer
BMDx package	BMDx is a software tool BMDx for easy benchmark dose (BMD) analysis on omics data across multiple time points and experiments	GitHub: https://github.com/fhaive/bmdx API: https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/insight/bmdx/docs/	Yes	Yes	Yes	R Shiny/R	Hazard based on NAMs/in vitro	TAU
AOP Fingerprint	A software tool for AOP-based chemical safety assessment	GitHub: https://github.com/fhaive/AOPfingerprintR API: https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/insight/aop_fingerprint/docs/	Yes	Yes	Yes	R Shiny/R	Hazard based on NAMs/in vitro	TAU
Enalos Cloud Platform	It is a web-based application that provides a suite of tools for predictive modeling and simulation in the fields of chemistry,	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/all.html	Yes	Yes	Yes	Ensemble of technologies	-	NovaM

		nanotechnology, and materials science							
Enalos Cloud Platform	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for blood-brain barrier permeability	Predict blood-brain barrier permeability of molecules using a deep learning model	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/bloodbrainbarrierpermeability/	Yes	No	Yes	Python/ML-based web app	QSAR and QSAR-type	NovaM
	AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for Caco-2 cell permeability prediction	AI/ML-based model suited for the prediction of Caco-2 cell permeability to estimate oral drug permeability.	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/caco2celllinepermeability/	Yes	No	Yes	Python/ML-based web app	QSAR and QSAR-type	NovaM
	ASCOT	Web tool for digital construction and energy minimization of Ag, CuO, TiO ₂ nanoparticles (NPs)	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/sabydoma/ascot/	Not yet	No	Yes	Web-based / Cloud platform	Materials engineering	NovaM
	Biokinetics Model	Prediction of nickel (Ni) release from cardiovascular devices to estimate exposure levels	http://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/Biokinetics/	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based	Exposure	NovaM

Consensus Predictive Model for Human K562 Cell Growth Inhibition	Prediction of K562 cell growth inhibition, potentially aiding in drug discovery for β -thalassemia treatment	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/k562/	Yes	No	Yes	KNIME Workflow/Web-based	QSAR and QSAR-type	NovaM
Easy-MODA	A web tool for the assisted generation of MODA standardised reports for the FAIR and harmonized documentation of materials modelling workflows, as proposed by the European Materials Modelling Council (EMMC).	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/insight/moda/	Not Yet	No	Yes	Java, Web-based	Other	NovaM
Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity	Predict toxicity of Iron Oxide NPs	http://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/QNAR_IronOxide_Toxicity/	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based	Materials engineering, QSAR and QSAR-type	NovaM
Enalos Zeta Potential Prediction Tool	Predict zeta potential of nanomaterials (NMs) based on transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images	http://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/ZetaPotential/	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based	Materials engineering, QSAR and QSAR-type	NovaM

In Vitro Dosimetry Web Application	The De Loid <i>et al.</i> multi-step <i>in vitro</i> dosimetry methodology to quantify delivered NMs dose metrics as a function of time	https://www.enalosccloud.novamechanics.com/riskgone/InVitroDosimetry/	Not Yet	No	Yes	Java, Web-based	Exposure	NovaM
INSIGHT Cheminformatics Suite	A suite of cheminformatics models developed under the INSIGHT project for the virtual screening of sets of compounds.	https://www.enalosccloud.novamechanics.com/insight/cheminf/	Not Yet	No	Yes	KNIME, Python, Web-based/Cloud platform	QSAR and QSAR-type	NovaM
ML-NANOCAT: PredMod CO	A trained machine learning (ML) model to predict the adsorption energy of CO molecules on Ni clusters, for the design of novel nanocatalytic materials	https://enalosccloud.novamechanics.com/EnaloscWebApps/mlnanocatco/	Yes	No	Yes	Java/Web-based	Materials engineering	NovaM
ML-NANOCAT: PredMod NO ₂	A trained ML model to predict the adsorption energy of NO ₂ molecules on Ni clusters, for the design of novel nanocatalytic materials	https://enalosccloud.novamechanics.com/EnaloscWebApps/mlnanocatno2/	Yes	No	Yes	Java/Web-based	Materials engineering	NovaM

ML-NANOCAT: PredMod O ₂	A trained ML model to predict the adsorption energy of O ₂ molecules on Ni clusters, for the design of novel nanocatalytic materials	https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/mlnanocato2/	Yes	No	Yes	Java/Web-based	Materials engineering	NovaM
ML-NANOCAT: PredMod SO ₂	A trained ML model to predict the adsorption energy of SO ₂ molecules on Ni clusters, for the design of novel nanocatalytic materials	https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/mlnanocatso2/	Yes	No	Yes	Java/Web-based	Materials engineering	NovaM
MouseTox	Online toxicity assessment tool for small molecules	http://enalos.insilicotox.com/MouseTox/	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based, KNIME integrated	QSAR and QSAR-type	NovaM
NanoConstruct	A toolbox for the digital reconstruction of energy minimized NPs based on their crystallographic information files (CIF) and the calculation of their atomistic descriptors	https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/riskgone/nanoconstruct/	Not Yet	No	Yes	Web-based / GUI	Materials engineering	NovaM
Nano Protein Corona Model	A predictive quantitative nanostructure-activity	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/n	Not Yet	No	Yes	Web-based, KNIME integrated	Materials engineering,	NovaM

	(QNAR) model of the cellular association of surface-modified gold NPs based on the acquired protein corona fingerprint and the NPs physicochemical properties	anocommons/NanoProteinCorona/						QSAR and QSAR-type	
NanoTube Construct	A tool for the digital construction of energy minimized nanotubes of single layer materials and calculation of their atomic descriptors	https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/diagonal/nanotube/	Not yet	No	Yes	Web-based	Materials engineering	NovaM	
Polis	A consensus model for the mutagenicity prediction of small molecules	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/insight/polis/	Not yet	No	Yes	Python, Isalos, KNIME/Web-based	QSAR and QSAR-type	NovaM	
Prediction of MNPs Uptake in PaCa2 Cancer Cells	A QNAR model that correlates the organic surface modifiers structural descriptors of metal-oxide NPs with the same core and the NPs cellular uptakes	https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/QNAR_PaCa2/	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based, KNIME integrated	Materials engineering, QSAR and QSAR-type	NovaM	

Safe-by-design tool for functionalised NMs	Two predictive QNAR/k-nearest neighbour (kNN) models for the assessment of decorated multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) biological and toxicological profile	http://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/CNT/	Yes	No	Yes	Java, Web-based	Materials engineering, QSAR and QSAR-type	NovaM
SafeNanoScope	A random forest model for the prediction of the adverse effects class (against HepaRG cell line) of Ag, TiO ₂ and CuO NPs based on their properties in atomistic level	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/sabydoma/safenanoscope/	Not yet	No	Yes	Random Forest model on SABYDOMA platform	Materials engineering, QSAR and QSAR-type	NovaM
THALAMOSS Platform for Chelation	AI/ML-based model to predict chelation outcomes for thalassemia patients	www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/chelation/	Yes	No	Yes	Web-based	Other	NovaM
UANanoDock	Prediction of protein adsorption onto NPs at selected pH levels	https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/compsafenano/uananodock/	Not yet	No	Yes	Web-based	Materials engineering	NovaM

Enalos Suite	Package any predictive model in a completely custom made, platform independent, standalone software	https://enalossuite.novamechanics.com/	No	No	Yes	Java	-	NovaM
Enalos+ KNIME nodes	Enalos+ nodes for KNIME analytics platform which offer a wide range of cheminformatics, bioinformatics and nanoinformatics functionalities into KNIME to enhance the solution of big data analysis, personalized medicine, clinical trials, computer aided drug discovery and material science problems	https://www.knime.com/community/enalos-nodes	No	No	Yes	Java	-	NovaM
Isalos Analytics Platform	Develop and deploy ML/AI models to identify patterns and make predictions without programming (zero code)	http://isalos.novamechanics.com/	No	No	Yes	Java	-	NovaM

INTEGRA (Multimedia model)		INTEGRA is a unified computational platform that integrates environmental fate, exposure, and internal dose dynamically over time.	https://www.parc-ssbd.eu/	Yes (multimedia model), Under development	Not yet	Yes (PARC SSbD toolbox)	R	Environmental fate, Exposure	AUTH
Jaqpot Infrastructure		Jaqpot is a web platform developed by NTUA for building, deploying, and sharing machine-learning and biokinetics models. Users can train models, run predictions, and access models via graphical user interfaces (GUIs) or REST API.	https://app.jaqpot.org	Yes	No	Yes	Ensemble of technologies	-	NTUA
Jaqpot Infrastructure	QSAR-ML model for the prediction of cell viability (%) in graphene-related materials	QSAR-ML model for the prediction of cell viability (%) in graphene-related materials	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/1881/description	Yes	No	Yes	Python, Web-Based	QSAR and QSAR-type	NTUA
	Machine Learning	These models predict the aquatic toxicity	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2188/	Yes	No	Yes	Python, Web-Based	QSAR and QSAR-type	NTUA

	Models for Aquatic Toxicity Prediction	(LC50) in fish species and EC50 Prediction on Crustacean Species for small organic molecules	description , https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2190/description .						
	PFOS PBK for humans (Chou & Lin, 2019)	This model reproduces the PBK model of Chou and Lin (2019) for describing the biodistribution of perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) in humans	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2126/description	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based	PBK	NTUA
	PFOA PBK (Worley et al., 2017)	PBK model for describing the biodistribution of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) in humans after intravenous or oral administration	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/1984/description	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based	PBK	NTUA
	PFOA/PFOS/PFHxS/PFNA I-compartment toxicokinetic (Chiu et al., 2022)	Toxicokinetics model for describing the serum concentration-time of PFOA, PFOS, perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA) or perfluorohexanesulfonic acid (PFHxS) in humans after ingestion	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/1985/description	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based	Exposure	NTUA

PFOA/PFOS PBK consensus model	The consensus PBK model integrates the predictions of several individual toxicokinetics models to describe the disposition of PFOA and PFOS in the serum and liver	Uses multiple PBK models	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based	PBK	NTUA
Toluene di-isocyanate (TDI) PBK	This PBK model simulates the biodistribution and urinary excretion of TDI and its metabolites (TDA) in humans following occupational exposure via inhalation and dermal routes.	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2207/description	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based	PBK	NTUA
Acetone PBK	This PBK model describes the uptake, distribution, metabolism, and excretion of acetone in humans, with a particular focus on inhalation exposure.	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2275/description	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based	PBK	NTUA
Ethylene Glycol PBK	This PBK model describes the absorption, distribution,	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2233/description	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based	PBK	NTUA

		metabolism, and excretion of ethylene glycol (EG) and its primary metabolite glycolic acid (GA) in humans, with a particular focus on inhalation exposure scenarios.							
PFBS PBK	This PBK model predicts the concentration-time profiles of perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS) in humans.	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2315/description	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based	PBK	NTUA	
PFHxA PBK	This PBK model predicts the concentration-time profiles of PFHxA in humans.	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2303/description	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based	PBK	NTUA	
In vitro kinetics	This model is a steady-state mass balance model that predicts the free chemical concentrations in the medium, that is in equilibrium with the free cellular concentration	https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2303/description	Yes	No	Yes	R, Web-Based	PBK	NTUA	

Table 2: Integration of external models and tools

Tool Name	Objective	Location	APIs	Docker	GUI	Programming language/application type	Category	Developer	Integrator
QSAR Toolbox	A software application for predicting and filling data gaps in (eco)toxicity data for chemical hazard assessment	<p>Calculator Integration: https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/6/description</p> <p>Model Integration: https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/1837/description</p> <p>Profiler Integration: https://app.iqpot.org/dashboard/models/1842/description</p>	Yes	No	Yes	Python	QSAR and QSAR-type	Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD)	NTUA

VEGA	VEGA is a freely available software that provides QSAR models for predicting physicochemical and (eco)toxicological properties of chemicals.	Integrated through QSAR toolbox: https://app.iagpot.org/dashboard/models/1837/description	Yes	No	Yes	Python	QSAR and QSAR-type	Mario Negri Institute for Pharmacological Research (IRFMN)	NTUA
MicroPlasticFate	This application replicates the core features of the SimpleBox4Plastic (SB4P) multimedia environmental fate model. It simulates the fate and behaviour of nano- and microplastics (NMPs) across multiple environmental scales, including regional, continental and global scale, each of which consists of compartments/media of air, soil, water and sediment.	https://enalscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/MicroPlasticFate/	Not Yet	No	Yes	Java, R/ Web-based	Environmental fate	(Duch) National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)	NovaM
INSIGHT LCA REST API	REST API providing Social LCA and Environmental LCA	https://insight.list.lu	Yes	Yes	No	Python	LCA	LIST	LIST

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3. Description of the models and tools developed internally

In the following sections, descriptions of the tools implemented and integrated in the INSIGHT compendium of models are provided, describing their main objectives, functionalities and how they can support the INSIGHT modeling framework.

3.1. Tools for toxicogenomics based dose dependent analysis and AOP-based mechanistic characterization of chemical effects

Quantifying dose dependency is key to toxicological risk assessment, as it identifies exposure levels where biological responses emerge. Benchmark dose (BMD) modeling provides a robust way to estimate these thresholds from transcriptomic data, but it does not reveal biological relevance or mechanisms. Omics technologies have advanced mechanistic toxicology, yet regulatory adoption of quantitative, mechanism-based metrics remains limited. Integrating BMD modeling with AOP-based enrichment analysis offers a promising solution by linking dose-dependent gene expression to established frameworks. To support this, we developed two modular R tools, BMDx and AOPFingerprintR, available as packages and RESTful APIs for flexible, scalable workflows. These can be used independently or together for comprehensive dose-response and mechanistic analyses. For accessibility, we combined them into BMDx2, an R-Shiny app enabling end-to-end toxicogenomic analysis without advanced coding.

3.1.1. BMDx package

The BMDx package is freely available at <https://github.com/fhaive/bmdx/>. Complete documentation of the R package functionalities is available at: <https://github.com/fhaive/bmdx/blob/main/manual.pdf>. In addition to the R package, we have implemented a RESTful API version of BMDx through R Plumer³ (Schloerke and Allen. 2025), allowing programmatic access to its core functionalities. To ensure reproducibility and portability, the API was containerized with Docker. The BMDx API are currently hosted and documented at: <https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/insight/bmdx/docs/>

³ <https://www.rplumber.io>

Table 3: BMDx input files

Name	Type	Description
Input files		
metadata	Dataframe	Metadata for omic data
experimental_data	Matrix	Preprocessed omic data
sample_id	String	Column names of metadata reporting samples id
concentration_id	String	Column names of metadata reporting concentrations
timepoint_id	String	Column names of metadata reporting timepoint
Prefiltering parameters (optional step)		
prefiltering	String	Type of prefiltering to be applied
anovaAdjustment	String	Method for p-value adjustment
<u>anovaPval.th</u>	Numeric [0, 1]	Threshold for p-value significance
trendAdjustment	String	Method for p-value adjustment
trendPval.th	Numeric [0, 1]	Threshold for p-value significance
fcAdjustment	String	Method for p-value adjustment
fcPval.th	Numeric [0, 1]	Threshold for p-value significance
fc.th	Numeric (>0)	Threshold for fold-change
Model fitting		
model_names	Vector of strings	Names of models to be fitted
max_iter	Integer (>0)	Max number of iteration
data_type	String	Type of response variable
deviation_type	String	Type of deviation
rl	Numeric [1, 2]	Response level
confidence_interval	Numeric [0,	Confidence interval

	1[
variance_type	String	Type of variance
Model filtering		
lower_bound_th	Numeric]0, 1[Threshold for BMD estimation
upper_bound_th	Numeric]0, 1[Threshold for BMD estimation
bmd_bmdl_th	Numeric	Threshold for BMD estimation
bmd_bmdl_th	Numeric	Threshold for BMD estimation
bmd_bmdl_th	Numeric	Threshold for BMD estimation
filter_lower_bound	Boolean	Boolean, if TRUE lower bound threshold is applied for filtering
filter_upper_bound	Boolean	Boolean, if TRUE upper bound threshold is applied for filtering
ratio_filter	Boolean	Boolean, if TRUE BMD/BMDL and BMDU/BMD threshold is applied for filtering
bmd_na_filter	Boolean	Boolean, if TRUE BMD values with NA are removed
bmdl_na_filter	Boolean	Boolean, if TRUE BMDL values with NA are removed
bmdu_na_filter	Boolean	Boolean, if TRUE BMDU values with NA are removed
ic50_na_filter	Boolean	Boolean, if TRUE IC50 values with NA are removed
r2_filter	Boolean	Boolean, if TRUE models with $R^2 < r2_th$ are removed
r2_th	Numeric [0, 1]	R^2 threshold
filter_by_monotonicity	Boolean	Boolean, if TRUE monotonicity filtering is applied
filter_by_negative_values	Boolean	Boolean, if TRUE removes models that estimates negative BMD
filter_by_unordered_values	Boolean	Boolean, if TRUE removes models that estimates unordered BMDL, BMD, BMDU

Table 4: BMDx output files.

Name	Units	Description
optimal_model_stats	dataframe	Point of departures (BMD/BMDL/BMDU) for dose-dependent genes

The analysis pipeline implemented in BMDx is reported in Figure 3. It begins with the import of preprocessed toxicogenomic datasets and their associated metadata. BMDx2 supports both microarray and RNA sequencing data, assuming log₂ normalization for microarrays and variance-stabilizing transformation for RNASeq (Figure 3A).

Since the dose-dependent analysis of genome-wide transcriptomic data can be computationally expensive, an optional pre-filtering step is available that allows users to focus on the analysis on genes that exhibit potential dose-dependent variation (Figure 3B). This can be achieved using ANOVA, trend tests, or differential expression analysis via the limma R package⁴. Filtering parameters are fully customizable, and the step can be skipped if prior filtering has been performed externally or if all modelling should be performed on all the molecular features present in the datasets.

Following filtering, the pipeline proceeds to BMD modeling (Figure 3C). For each gene, multiple dose-response models can be fitted. The complete list of models available is provided in *Serra et al., 2025*. Once models are fitted, BMDs and their confidence intervals (BMDL and BMDU) are estimated (Figure 3D). The benchmark response (BMR), the threshold defining biologically meaningful changes, is user-defined and can be calculated using absolute, relative, or standard deviation-based methods. The standard deviation method uses a default BMRF of 1.349, corresponding to an 11% tail shift, as recommended by Thomas et al., (2007). To ensure robust dose estimation, BMDx applies multiple quality control filters (Figure 3E). These include thresholds for model fit (e.g., R²), BMD/BMDL and BMDU/BMD ratios, and monotonicity checks. Models failing to meet these criteria can be excluded. Among the remaining models, the best-fitting one is selected using either the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) or a model averaging approach (Figure 3F). Finally, the genes deemed dose-dependent are the ones that passed all the filtering and their corresponding BMD, BMDL and BMDU values are the ones obtained from the optimal selected model (Figure 3G).

The pipeline also supports the estimation of transcriptome-wide points of departure (twPODs), which summarizes the overall sensitivity of the transcriptome to chemical exposure (Figure 3H). The final output includes a comprehensive summary of dose-response metrics for each gene, including the estimated PODs (BMD, BMDL, and BMDU) and information on the model fitting from which these were derived.

⁴ <https://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/limma.html>

Figure 3: Pipeline implemented in BMDx for dose-dependent analysis. Figure from Serra et al., (2025)

3.1.2. AOPFingerprint package

The AOPfingerprintR package is freely available at: <https://github.com/fhaive/AOPfingerprintR>. Complete documentation of the R package functionalities is provided at: https://github.com/fhaive/AOPfingerprintR/blob/main/AOPfingerprintR_0.0.1.pdf.

In addition to the R package, we have implemented a RESTful API version of BMDx through R Plumer, allowing programmatic access to its core functionalities. To ensure reproducibility and portability, the API was containerized with Docker. The BMDx API are currently hosted and documented at: https://enanoscloud.novamechanics.com/insight/aop_fingerprint/docs/

The analysis pipeline implemented in AOPfingerprintR is illustrated in Figure 4. It begins with the import of gene lists and background genes provided as Excel files (Figure 4A). These gene lists typically represent relevant genes identified from toxicogenomics experiments, such as differentially expressed genes or dose-dependent genes. The first analytical step involves Key Event (KE) enrichment (Figure 4B), where the genes are tested for overrepresentation in KEs using Fisher's exact test. The same statistical approach is applied to perform AOP enrichment (Figure 4C), where genes are tested against AOP-related genes.

Following enrichment, the pipeline diverges into two complementary analyses. The KE-KE network analysis (Figure 4D) uses KE enrichment results to visualize mechanistic relationships between enriched KEs and their connecting nodes, enabling exploration of potential pathways and comparison between experimental conditions. In parallel, AOP fingerprints are generated (Figure 4E) by integrating both KE and AOP enrichment results. These fingerprints summarize the biological pathways most impacted by the experimental conditions and provide a structured representation of mechanistic evidence.

The underlying annotations for KEs and AOPs are based on curated mappings from Saarimäki et al., (2023), leveraging data from AOP-Wiki and supporting multiple species (human, mouse, rat) and gene identifiers. Enrichment p-values can be adjusted using False Discovery Rate (FDR) or Bonferroni correction, and user-defined thresholds determine AOP significance (default: $\geq 33\%$ of enriched KEs or

≥2 KEs for short AOPs). This workflow ensures that transcriptomic changes are systematically linked to regulatory-relevant biological mechanisms, facilitating interpretation in the context of human health and chemical safety assessment.

Figure 4: Pipeline implemented in AOPFingerprintR for AOP analysis.

3.1.3. BMDx2: Integrated GUI

The two packages BMDx and AOPFingerprint, have been integrated into a unified tool, called BMDx2, to offer an easy-to-use framework for the AOP-based mechanistic characterization of chemical exposure based on dose dependent genes. BMDx2 is available at: <https://github.com/fhaive/bmdx2>. BMDx2 is an R-Shiny software with a user-friendly interface, designed to support comprehensive, mechanistically informed, and reproducible exploration and evaluation of dose-dependent effects in toxicogenomic datasets (Figure 5). It accommodates multiple data types, including transcriptomics, DNA methylation and targeted *in vitro* test data. The platform requires data where multiple doses have been tested and supports the joint analysis of multiple experimental conditions. BMDx2 uniquely integrates benchmark-dose modeling with AOP mapping, extending beyond pathway enrichment to deliver regulatory-relevant insights.

Figure 5: The BMDx2 tool includes four main modules: a) BMD analysis, b) comparative analysis of different experimental conditions c) AOP analysis d) co-dose dependence analysis. Figure from Serra et al., 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.202501728>

To showcase the functionalities of the BMDx2 tool, we used a multi-dose omics dataset related to GBMs (Graphene based materials) exposure, GSE146482. This dataset comes from study of Mukherjee et al. (2020) and includes RNA-seq transcriptomic exposure data of lung cell lines (*i.e.*, BEAS-2B) to graphene oxide of different lateral sizes, namely ultra-small (USGO), small (SGO), and larger (LGO) graphene oxide at different timepoints. The multiple dose setup is essential for identifying dose-response relationships, which allows to identify BMDs for transcriptional changes (*i.e.*, twPODs). With multiple timepoints, it also supports the analysis of temporal dynamics in response to dose, offering insights into immediate and late responses. The dataset contains three replicates per condition ensuring statistical robustness and data quality and compares each condition to a non-exposed control enabling differential expression analysis. Overall, it covers 87 experimental conditions making a good source for evaluating dose-dependent molecular responses to GBMs.

Initially, the metadata of this dataset has been curated using ESPERANTO tool (Lieto et al., 2023). The dataset was preprocessed following the same approach described in Saarimäki et al. (2021). Briefly, quality check of the RNA sequencing data was carried out using FastQC, then reads were aligned against the human reference genome GRCh38. The alignment was done using the HISAT2 algorithm. Raw read counts for the RNA-seq data were computed using Rsubread package from R package. Transcripts with low expression levels in the samples were removed using a proportion test implemented in the Bioconductor NOISeq package. Normalization was performed using the DESeq2

package from Bioconductor applying median of ratios method. Finally, differential expression analysis was performed comparing each specific experimental condition to its corresponding control (Saarimäki et al., 2021). Relevant genes were filtered based on whether a gene differentially altered in at least one of the conditions considering an absolute \log_2 fold change higher than 0.58 and FDR-adjusted p-value lower than 0.05.

To identify genes whose expression values show an increasing or decreasing pattern across doses, dose-dependency analysis was performed using the BMDx2 tool. BMDx2 implements a multi-step pipeline that consists of the following stages though with the user are guided in the GUI: setting the mode, loading phenotype data, loading experimental data, filtering, computing BMD, performing functional enrichment with FunMappOne tool, analyzing gene pairs, conducting AOP and KE enrichment, and downloading the report (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Main dashboard of the BMDx2 tool.

For the BMD analysis, default parameters were applied to fit the models and filter the results. The tool provides the option to select the optimal model by means of the lowest AIC. All the genes that passed the filtering and had at least one model been deemed dose dependent (Figure 7).

Experiment	timepoint	Feature	Model	BMR	BMDL	BMD	BMDU	AC50	Adverse_direction	AIC	Lack_of_	
All	All	All		/	/	/	/	/	All	A	All	
1	USGO	1	ENSG00000142583	linear	7.412206	13.422952	34.091122	56.722665	40	-1	-2.413539	0.02
2	USGO	1	ENSG00000142583	poly2	7.39839	13.378355	40.422486	67.351845	46.322006	-1	-0.545794	0.00
3	USGO	1	ENSG00000142583	exp2	7.424539	11.57534	30.765577	49.996137	39.200214	-1	-2.203064	0.02
4	USGO	1	ENSG00000287727	poly2	6.135018	1.306945	10.95924	23.436686	16.901469	1	-0.608309	0.45
5	USGO	1	ENSG00000162444	poly2	7.49528	1.116588	10.050202	37.082531	14.221742	-1	-7.05941	0.62
6	USGO	1	ENSG00000130770	linear	11.394136	11.669597	30.834076	49.173506	40	-1	-8.212266	0.00
7	USGO	1	ENSG00000130770	poly2	11.485742	1.357547	11.082184	23.075249	19.389593	-1	-10.504496	0.00
8	USGO	1	ENSG00000126698	poly2	12.874348	0.908881	8.601594	16.354012	15.819588	-1	-5.001736	0.00
9	USGO	1	ENSG00000169403	linear	7.030716	9.026613	25.524116	39.196179	40	1	-27.044291	0.65
10	USGO	1	ENSG00000169403	poly2	7.027514	6.160875	23.208491	49.551004	37.269898	1	-25.086479	0.40

Showing 1 to 10 of 32,951 entries

Previous 1 2 3 4 5 ... 3,296 Next

Figure 7: BMDx results from dose-dependency analysis.

After obtaining the final dose-dependent genes, genes of interest can be selected and visualized (Figure 8).

Figure 8: BMDx model fitting of a specific gene altered after exposure to USGO.

After the BMD analysis, the user can compare different experiments in terms of number of dose-dependent genes and distribution of BMD values. In this study, we investigate if there is any temporal trend in the quantity of dose-dependent and material-specific patterns. For example, the number of dose-dependent and significantly altered genes (DD-DEGs, differentially expressed genes) in response to USGO appears to decline over time, whereas no clear trend is observed for the other materials. Figure 9 shows the number of DD-DEGs after exposure to different exposure conditions.

Figure 9: Number of DD-DEGs after exposure to USGO, SGO and LGO at 1, 7, and 28 days.

By analyzing the BMD distribution across materials, LGO seems to require a higher dose (i.e, average BMD) to trigger molecular alterations compared to USGO and SGO, indicating an influence of the dimension in shaping the response (Figure 10).

Figure 10: BMD distribution and model used to estimate BMD.

Furthermore, we used the AOPFingerprint functionality embedded in BMDx2 to extract mechanistic insights and twPODs at the level of KEs, thereby supporting hypothesis driven testing and interpretation. For KE enrichment, an adjusted p-value below 0.05 using the false discovery method was statistically significant. For gene level aggregation the median BMD values were used.

Table 5: AOPFingerprint input files.

Name	Type	Description
Inputs		
gene list for one or multiple chemicals	Excel sheet (or Dataframe)	List of genes to be enriched for multiple chemicals

experiment_id_variable	String	Name of the experiment (e.g. chemical)
time_point_variable	String	Time point for each gene list
organism	String	Either human, mouse or rat genes
gene_id	String	Type of gene identifiers provided (symbols, ensembl, entrez)
Filtering results & Plotting		
only_significant	Boolean	Return only significant enrichment
pval_th	Numeric [0, 1]	P-value threshold
adj_method	String	P-value adjustment method
numerical_properties	Vector of strings	Numerical properties names associated to gene in the input lists (e.g. BMD, fold-change)
min_aop_length	Integer (>0)	Number of KE in AOPs
percentage_enriched_ke	Numeric [0, 1]	Percentages of KE in AOPs to be enriched
group_by	String	AOPs can be grouped by SSbD hazard categories or by System

Table 6: AOPFingerprint output files.

Name	Type	Description
enrichedKE	dataframe	enriched Key Event
enrichedAO	dataframe	enriched AOP
AOP_fingerprint	bubbleplot/dataframe	AOP fingerprint
KEKE enrichment network	Html file	plot AOP fingerprint html as pdf

After the KE enrichment, the user can analyze the twPOD distribution across KEs. By analyzing BMD values across exposures with respect to biological level (Figure 11) and type of KE (Figure 12), users can gain multiscale insights into dose-response dynamics at a multiscale level. In this dataset, a notable trend emerges. Over time, the dose necessary to activate responses across biological levels tends to decrease (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Boxplot of BMD across exposures by biological level of enriched KEs.

This reduction may be driven by anticipatory mechanisms arising from biological sensitization or priming where repeated exposure to stress leads to accumulated signaling that lowers the activation threshold. This phenomenon can be more pronounced in chronic exposure scenarios (Deans, 2021). Once molecular changes are initiated, they are amplified across biological levels reducing the need for initially higher doses. This pattern is also observed in Figure 12 across KE types.

Figure 12: Boxplot of BMD across exposures by type of enriched KEs.

Finally, the KE enrichment results are mapped to the KE-KE network to better investigate the comprehensive mechanism of exposure of the chemicals. Users can visualize mechanistic connections and identify the most impacted pathways summarizing the findings. Figure 13 shows the KE-KE network for LGO after 1 day of exposure.

Figure 13: KE-KE network of mechanisms induced in BEAS-2B after 1 day exposure to LGO.

3.2. Enalos Cloud Platform

The Enalos Cloud Platform (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/>) developed by NovaM is a comprehensive suite of predictive models and tools offered as ready-to-use web services across cheminformatics, nanoinformatics, and materials engineering (Varsou et al., 2020). Developed using the ZK framework (an open-source Ajax web application framework), JavaScript, and Java, the platform integrates robust open-source libraries and software, including Python, R, LAMMPS, OpenKIM, NGL Viewer, MD Analysis, KNIME, WEKA, ImageJ, and ParaView, along with proprietary tools, such as Isalos and Enalos+ nodes. These web services do not require authorization (logging-in) and programming expertise, which means that any user can generate reliable predictions to assess the toxicity and/or environmental fate of small molecules and materials. They come with thorough learning resources, including user guides and video tutorials, and often are supported by scientific publications explaining their development (e.g., modelling steps, validation results, data resources, used software). This openness allows users to understand the underlying scientific models and the creation process, fostering trust in the service's results. Conceived to broaden access, through a free-to-use and intuitive GUI, the platform facilitates access to advanced computational tools to reduce extensive experimental work and favor alternatives to animal testing, thus further promoting informed decision-making in scientific research and innovation. The computational tools and models (72 in total at the time of writing) are supported by 14 EU-funded projects. These web-services, categorized for easy exploration (i.e., cheminformatics, nanoinformatics, materials engineering, image analysis, exposure and biokinetics models), allow users of all backgrounds to leverage advanced models for tasks like material property simulation, virtual drug candidate screening, and sustainable material design. Within the next sections the Enalos Cloud models included in the INSIGHT model graph are briefly described.

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Associated Partners from (a) Switzerland, (b) United Kingdom, (c) Korea, (d) Brazil, (e) Australia, and (f) USA received national funding from (a) the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), (b) Innovate UK (UKRI), (c) The National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF), and (d) the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAESPE).

3.2.1. Enalos Cloud Platform: AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for blood-brain barrier permeability

A robust Message-Passing Neural Network (MPNN) model with an atom-attention (AA) layer is developed as described by Koutroumpa et al., 2025. This deep learning model combines the well-performed Directed MPNN with an atom transformer to highlight critical substructures of the molecular graph to the desired chemical property. The atom-attention MPNN encoder is first pre-trained on a large unlabeled dataset (ZINC15) to capture rich semantic information about molecular structures. The pre-trained MPNN encoder is followed by a feed-forward network and is fine-tuned on the blood-brain barrier permeability task. The model can be accessed through a user-friendly GUI (Figure 14) on the Enalos Cloud Platform (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/bloodbrainbarrierpermeability/>). The user can design the molecule of interest, import the SMILES notation, or upload a spatial data file (SDF). The output of the model is a classification of the molecule as either permeable or non-permeable. With the atom-attention layer, we also obtain the attention weight scores and depict them as heat maps on the molecule. Atoms with positive contributions to blood-brain barrier permeability (positive attention weight scores) are colored in green, while atoms with negative contributions (negative attention weight scores) are colored in red. The intensity of the color indicates the absolute value of the attention weights.

Figure 14: GUI of the AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for blood-brain barrier permeability model.

Table 7: AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for blood-brain barrier permeability model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Chemical sketcher	-	Compound structure drawing
SMILES string	-	SMILES strings list of query compounds
SDF	-	Spatial data file with query compounds

Table 8: AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for blood-brain barrier permeability model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
SMILES	-	Input compounds SMILES representation
Prediction	-	Permeability prediction class (permeable/not permeable)
Probability	-	Permeability prediction class probability
Image	-	An image representing the atom-attention weights calculated by the model

3.2.2. Enalos Cloud Platform: AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for Caco-2 cell permeability prediction

A robust MPNN model with an atom-attention layer is developed as described by Koutroumpa et al., 2025. This deep learning model combines the well-performed Directed MPNN with an atom transformer to highlight critical substructures of the molecular graph to the desired chemical property. The atom-attention MPNN encoder is first pre-trained on a large unlabeled dataset (ZINC15) to capture rich semantic information about molecular structures. The pre-trained MPNN encoder is followed by a feed-forward network and is fine-tuned on the human intestinal absorption with the Caco-2 permeability task. The model can be accessed through a user-friendly GUI on the Enalos Cloud Platform (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/caco2cellinepermeability/>). The user can design the molecule of interest, import the SMILES notation, or upload an SDF file (Figure 15). The output of the model is a classification of the molecule as either permeable or non-permeable. With the atom-attention layer, we also obtain the attention weight scores and depict them as heat maps on the molecule. Atoms with positive contributions to Caco-2 cell permeability (positive attention weight scores) are colored in green, while atoms with negative contributions (negative attention weight scores) are colored in red. The intensity of the color indicates the absolute value of the

Figure 15: GUI of the AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for Caco-2 cell permeability prediction model.

Table 9: AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for Caco-2 cell permeability prediction model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Chemical sketcher	-	Compound structure drawing
SMILES string	-	SMILES strings list of query compounds
SDF	-	Spatial data file with query compounds

Table 10: AA-MPNN Deep Learning model for Caco-2 cell permeability prediction model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
SMILES	-	Input compounds SMILES representation
Prediction	-	Permeability prediction class (permeable/not permeable)
Probability	-	Permeability prediction class probability
Image	-	An image representing the atom-attention weights calculated by the model

3.2.3. Enalos Cloud Platform: ASCOT

Ag-Silver, Copper Oxide, Titanium oxide - ASCOT (Figure 16) is a user-friendly web tool (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/sabydoma/ascot/>) for digital construction of electrically neutral, energy-minimized spherical NPs of Ag, CuO, and TiO₂ (both Anatase and Rutile forms) in vacuum. ASCOT's automated backend requires minimal user input in order to construct the digital NPs: that is the material type (Ag, CuO, TiO₂-Anatase, TiO₂-Rutile), the NP diameter, a Force-Field from a pre-validated list, and the energy minimization parameters, with the tool providing a set of default values for novice users. ASCOT calculates critical atomistic descriptors such as the average potential energy per atom, the average coordination number, the common neighbour parameter (used for structural classification in simulations of crystalline phases), and the hexatic order parameter (which measures how closely the local environment around a particle resembles perfect hexatic symmetry) for both core (over 4 Å from the surface) and shell (within 4 Å of the surface) regions of the NPs. These atomistic descriptors assist in predicting the most stable NP size based on lowest per atom energy and serve as inputs for developing ML models to predict the toxicity of these NPs. More information can be found in the work of Kolokathis et al., 2024b.

[User Guide](#)

Figure 16: GUI of the ASCOT web-tool.

Table 11: ASCOT inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Load the material	-	Material type (Ag, CuO, TiO ₂) selection
Construct Nanoparticle without Force-Field	a nm	NP diameter

Construct an Energy Minimized Nanoparticle/Calculation of Atomistic Descriptors	-	Force Field (pre-validated list) Energy Tolerance Force Tolerance Maximum Iterations Maximum number of Force/Energy evaluation
---	---	--

Table 12: ASCOT output files.

Name	Units	Description
Geom_NP.xyz	-	XYZ file of the geometrically constructed NP
Minim_NP.xyz	-	XYZ file of the energy-minimized NP
lammps.data	-	LAMMPS datafiles for both geometrically constructed and energy-minimized NPs
descriptors.txt descriptors.csv	-	Descriptor files in .csv and .txt formats, see the full list of descriptors in the work of Kolokathis <i>et al.</i>
Stage1.png Stage2.png Stage3.png	-	Image files of the unit cell, the geometrically constructed and energy-minimized NPs

3.2.4. Enalos Cloud Platform: Biokinetics Model

This online tool (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/Biokinetics/>) is used for the prediction of the rate at which Nickel (Ni) is released from cardiovascular devices following implantation of the body, using the biokinetics model proposed by Saylor et al., 2016. This model (Figure 17) combines a traditional toxicokinetic compartment model with a physics-based model to estimate Ni release from an implanted device and links the rate of *in vitro* Ni release from a cardiovascular device to serum nickel concentrations. Furthermore, the software can simulate a system given an appropriate set of parameters. The software can be used in two ways: 1. To predict the release of Ni from an implanted device using the analytical model (Section 1: Solving mode), 2. To fit experimental data to the model (Section 2: Fitting mode).

Figure 17: Biokinetics Model GUI.

Table 13: Biokinetics model inputs

Name	Units	Description
Solving mode		
Time	days	The time range of interest
Process of surface treatment	-	The type of Ni release from the device surface that has been treated with one of the available methods in the respective dropdown menu (oxidized tube, mechanical police, salt pot, air furnace, electropolish).
Transfer coefficient of Ni from local tissue into the serum	l/day	The first order transfer coefficient of nickel from the local tissue into the serum

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Associated Partners from (a) Switzerland, (b) United Kingdom, (c) Korea, (d) Brazil, (e) Australia, and (f) USA received national funding from (a) the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), (b) Innovate UK (UKRI), (c) The National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF), and (d) the São Paulo Research Foundation (FAESPE).

Fraction of nickel released directly into the serum (the remaining fraction is released into the local tissue)	-	The Ni fraction from the nitinol device which is released directly into the serum while the remaining nickel partitions into the local tissue surrounding the device
Surface area of nitinol device	cm ²	The surface area of the nitinol device
Ratio of serum-to-tissue and tissue-to-serum Ni exchange transfer coefficient	-	The ratio of first order transfer coefficients of serum-to-tissue and tissue-to-serum exchange rates
Fitting mode		
Time	days	The time range of interest
Process of surface treatment	-	The type of Ni release from the device surface that has been treated with one of the available methods in the respective dropdown menu (oxidized tube, mechanical police, salt pot, air furnace, electropolish).
Timepoints of serum sampling and Ni concentration	µg/L	Experimental data of Ni concentration over time in serum
Timepoints of urine sampling and Ni concentration	µg/L	Experimental data of Ni concentration over time in urine

Table 14: Biokinetics model outputs

Name	Units	Description
Solving mode		
Ni concentration in serum	µg/L	Time evolution plot
Ni concentration in urine	µg/L	Time evolution plot
Local Ni mass	µg	Total Ni mass local to the device over time
Ni mass in serum	µg	Total Ni mass in the serum compartment over time
Ni mass in tissue	µg	Total Ni mass in the tissue compartment over time
Fitting mode		
First order transfer coefficient	l/day	First order transfer coefficient of nickel from the local tissue into the serum
Fraction of the nickel	-	Ni fraction from the nitinol device which is released directly into the serum while the remaining nickel partitions into the local tissue surrounding the device
Surface area of nitinol device	cm ²	Surface area of the nitinol device

Ratio of first order transfer coefficient	-	Ratio of first order transfer coefficients of serum-to-tissue and tissue-to-serum exchange rates
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3.2.5. Enalos Cloud Platform: Consensus Predictive Model for Human K562 Cell Growth Inhibition

Mutations in the β -globin gene lead to decreased production of adult hemoglobin (HbA), resulting in the development of a group of hereditary hematologic diseases, known as β -thalassemias. Notably, the inhibition of human K562 cell proliferation has been associated with fetal hemoglobin (HbF) production through de novo activation of γ -globin gene transcription. This mechanism presents a promising therapeutic strategy for the treatment of β -thalassemia. To further advance research in this field, the THALAMOSS: Assessment of the inhibition of human K562 cell growth web-application (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/k562/>) provides robust predictive capabilities for identifying promising inhibitor compounds, using a consensus predictive model. This user-friendly, web-based tool (Figure 18) enables researchers -regardless of computational expertise- to predict the chemical compounds inhibition class (active or inactive), by combining the predictions of three highly accurate and thoroughly validated models (a k NN, Random Forest, and Random Tree model), demonstrating a strong predictive performance (consensus accuracy = 0.84). In addition to uptake predictions, the application provides an Applicability Domain (APD) assessment to help users interpret the reliability of the predictions. Within this web-tool, users can import compounds of interest by either drawing molecules using an integrated sketcher or uploading a list of molecules in SMILES format. The required input consists of atomistic descriptors, which are automatically calculated via the Enalos Mold2 tool from the SMILES strings representing the decorative compounds. The platform can also be used for high-throughput virtual screening through batch processing: users can upload SDF files and process multiple compounds with one query. More information can be found in the work of Afantitis et al., 2018.

THALAMOSS Assessment of the inhibition of human K562 cell growth Powered by Enalos Cloud Platform

The screenshot displays the THALAMOSS web application interface. On the left, there is a 'Design a molecule' section with a chemical sketcher showing a complex organic molecule. Below it are buttons for 'Execute' and 'Write SMILES to text'. In the center, the 'User Guide' section prompts the user to 'Enter SMILES separated by newline' and provides a list of SMILES strings. Below this is an 'Execute' button and an 'Upload an SDF file (.sdf)' section with an 'upload' button and a message 'Please select an sdf file'. On the right, the 'Description' section provides information about β -Thalassemia. Below the description is a 'Download files' button and a table of predictions.

Row ID	Consensus Prediction	Reliability
Row0	"active"	"reliable"
Row1	"active"	"reliable"
Row2	"active"	"reliable"
Row3	"active"	"reliable"
Row4	"active"	"reliable"

Figure 18: Human K562 Cell Growth Inhibition model GUI.

Table 15: Consensus Predictive Model for Human K562 Cell Growth Inhibition inputs

Name	Units	Description
Chemical sketcher	-	Compound structure drawing
SMILES string	-	SMILES strings list of query compounds
SDF	-	Spatial data file with query compounds

Table 16: Consensus Predictive Model for Human K562 Cell Growth Inhibition outputs

Name	Units	Description
Consensus Prediction	-	Inhibition class prediction (active/inactive) per input structure
Reliability	-	Reliability of the prediction (reliable/unreliable) per input structure

3.2.6. Enalos Cloud Platform: Easy-MODA

Modelling Data (MODA) reporting guidelines have been proposed for common terminology and for recording metadata for physics-based materials modelling and simulations in a European Committee for Standardization (CEN) Workshop Agreement (CWA 17284:2018). Easy-MODA web tool (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/insight/moda/>) streamlines the creation of detailed MODA documentation, for simple or more complex multi-model workflows, and facilitates the registration of MODA workflows and documentation in a database, thereby enhancing the compliance of nanoinformatics and material informatics models, and their underpinning datasets, with the FAIR principles. Through the provided GUI (Figure 19) stakeholders are guided step-by-step through the documentation process and every relevant detail is captured in a harmonised and standardised manner, enhancing clarity and consistency across the scientific community. More information can be found in the work of Kolokathis et al., 2024a.

Easy-MODA

Simplifying Standardized Registration of Scientific Simulation Workflows through MODA [Template Guidelines](#) powered by the [Enalos Cloud Platform](#)

Green ▾

[User Guide](#) Load version from: Local or Cloud Search OK

MODA: MODELLING DATA GENERALISATION

Please fill in the boxes

Short title of the project

Acronym of the project

Description of the project

Is there a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) of the project?

Yes

No

Provide the models/data transformations of the project

Add

<input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="construction of energy minimized NP"/>	<input type="text" value="Physics based Model"/>	Edit	Delete
<input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="autoML"/>	<input type="text" value="Data based Model"/>	Edit	Delete
<input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="construction of geometrically constructe"/>	<input type="text" value="Data Transformation"/>	Edit	Delete

Workflow Image uploaded: image from cloud

Access Conditions

The workflow of the models is:

Owner of the workflow

The workflow can be accessed through the link

Describe and justify the selection of the workflow

Create Document Export

Save in Cloud

Figure 19: Easy-MODA GUI.

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Table 17: Easy-MODA inputs

Name	Units	Description
Data and transformations	-	Various fields describing the reported models according to the MODA guidelines
Workflow	-	MODA workflow (image)

Table 18: Easy-MODA outputs

Name	Units	Description
Create Document	-	MODA report in PDF format
Export	-	MODA report in JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format (compatible with Easy-MODA)

3.2.7. Enalos Cloud Platform: Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity

To support NPs toxicity evaluation, a fully validated predictive classification tool for iron oxide NPs' toxicity (summarized after considering 64 bioactivity measures) is developed on KNIME platform using the J48 modeling methodology (accuracy in external validation 84.6%) and is available online via the Enalos Cloud Platform (www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/QNAR_IronOxide_Toxicity/). Through this web service (Figure 20), the user can insert the indicated properties (NP size, zeta potential, relaxivities R1 and R2) and choose among three alternative coating options (Poly-vinyl-alcohol-PVA, cross-linked dextran or other) for multiple NP entries. Input properties can be provided either by filling in the given form or by uploading a comma-separated values (CSV) file. Afterwards, a toxicity prediction is generated, classifying each input NP as “active” or “inactive”, accompanied by an indication of its reliability based on the APD. There is an additional option to download output results in different formats (CSV or Hypertext Markup Language-HTML file). More information can be found in the work of Melagraki and Afantitis, 2015.

Figure 20: Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity GUI.

Table 19: Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity model inputs

Name	Units	Description
Size	nm	Size of each input NP
ZP	mV	Zeta potential of each input NP
R1	mM ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	Relaxivity R1 of each input NP
R2	mM ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	Relaxivity R2 of each input NP
Coating	-	The coating of each input NP (cross-linked dextran/poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA)/other)

Table 20: Enalos QNAR Iron Oxide Toxicity outputs

Name	Units	Description
Prediction	-	Toxicity prediction for each input NP
Domain	-	Reliability of the prediction (reliable/unreliable) for each input NP

3.2.8. Enalos Cloud Platform: Enalos Zeta Potential Prediction Tool

A validated kNN model (external validation $R^2_{\text{pred}}=0.898$) is made freely released through the Enalos Cloud platform (<http://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/ZetaPotential/>) for the prediction of NPs zeta-potential as described by Varsou et al., 2020. Based on the NP type of core, their main elongation, and the pH of interest, stakeholders in NP design, can import different NP datasets and examine the effects of different inputs on the zeta-potential value, a decisive step during the design process of novel NPs. The type of core and the pH are not measured experimentally, thus they can be easily provided without any cost. The requested image nanodescriptor (main elongation) encodes a geometrical characteristic and can be also easily retrieved from NPs TEM images using a free-to-use web-service such as the [NanoXtract tool](#) or an image analysis tool of their choice. The produced results include the predicted zeta-potential values for each NP sample as well as a warning on the prediction reliability according to the APD limits. The neighbours of each NP in the training set are also available through the web-service, to explore similarity patterns between NPs (Figure 21).

Row ID	Type of core	pH	Main Elongation
1	oxide	6.5	
2	oxide	6.5	
3	oxide	6.5	
4	oxide	6.5	
5	oxide	6.5	
6	oxide	6.5	
7	oxide	6.5	
8	oxide	6.5	
9	oxide	6.5	
10	oxide	6.5	
11	oxide	6.5	
12	oxide	6.5	
13	oxide	6.5	
14	oxide	6.5	
15	oxide	6.5	
16	oxide	6.5	
17	oxide	6.5	
18	oxide		
19	oxide		
20	oxide		

Row ID	Predicted zeta potential [mV]	Reliability
"IO166E Gold 12 nm PEG-OH"	-0.5815616505801628	"reliable"
"AgNPs PEG 10nm"	-23.554501736363807	"reliable"
"AgNPs PEG 20nm"	-27.79291401386539	"unreliable"
"AgNPs PVP 7nm"	-29.631770892835036	"reliable"
"TiO2 103"	23.107595387224467	"reliable"
"prom ZnO"	18.615889644766884	"reliable"
"Ce NM 211"	38.20268062475627	"reliable"
"S40"	-28.832095935920286	"reliable"
"IO003"	-10.691819408446678	"unreliable"

Figure 21: Enalos Zeta Potential Prediction Tool GUI.

Table 21: Enalos Zeta Potential Prediction Tool inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Type of core	-	The NPs type of core (oxide/pure metal)
pH	-	The pH (6.5/7) of the solution where the experimental measurement of the zeta potential would have been made
Main Elongation	-	Image nanodescriptor expressing the NP lengthening

Table 22: Enalos Zeta Potential Prediction Tool outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Predicted zeta potential [mV]	mV	The predicted zeta potential value per input NP
Reliability	-	Reliability of the zeta potential prediction (reliable/unreliable) per input NP
Neighbours	-	List of neighbours and respective distances per input NP (downloaded files)

3.2.9. Enalos Cloud Platform: In Vitro Dosimetry Web Application

A web application was developed (Cheimarios et al., 2022) for the numerical transport of NMs modelling (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/riskgone/InVitroDosimetry/>), based on a multi-step in vitro dosimetry methodology developed by De Loid et al., 2015 & 2017 (Figure 22). For initiating the process, the user needs to select one of the nine alternative materials and one of the distribution types on the particle parameter section. In case the user wants to define a different NM, they must provide a density value. After that, the application requires specific solvent parameters, such as density, viscosity, and temperature. Simulation parameters must also be provided by the user; suspension column height, initial total concentration of material, centrifugation, total time of simulation in hours and time interval for simulation need to be determined (default values available). Eventually, the web service presents three graphs after calculations are completed: position from the top, bottom concentration, and deposited fraction as functions of time (output results can be downloaded as an excel file).

Figure 22: In Vitro Dosimetry GUI.

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Table 23: In Vitro Dosimetry model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Particle parameters		
Material	-	Selection of material from predefined list or definition of a custom material
Density	g/cm ³	Automatically updated based on the selected material. For custom materials, the value must be provided by the user
Distribution type	-	A CSV file with size distribution data
Effective density	g/cm ³	Automatically updated based on the selected material. For custom materials, the value must be provided by the user
Solvent parameters		
Density	g/cm ³	The density of the suspension medium
Viscosity	P	The viscosity of the suspension medium
Temperature	°C	The temperature of the <i>in vitro</i> system
Simulation parameters		
Suspension column height	mm	Typically reflecting the volume of medium in the experimental well. For example, 100 µL in a 96-well plate translates to approximately 3 mm
Initial total concentration of material	mg/cm ³	The starting concentration of the ENM in the suspension
Centrifugation	-	A boolean parameter indicating whether centrifugation is applied during the experiment
Total time of simulation	h	The total duration of the simulated experiment
Time interval for simulation	s	The time step at which the model should calculate and output results

Table 24: In Vitro Dosimetry model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Output Graphs	-	Visual representations of the simulation results, illustrating the fate and transport of the ENMs over time
Downloadable Excel File	-	A primary form of output is an Excel file containing the numerical results of the simulation

3.2.10. Enalos Cloud Platform: INSIGHT Cheminformatics Suite

INSIGHT Cheminformatics Suite (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/insight/cheminf/>) hosts the cheminformatics models developed under the Insight Project for the virtual screening of sets of chemical compounds (Table 25). This web-tool allows users -regardless of their computational

expertise- to utilize highly accurate and thoroughly validated computational models through a user-friendly interface (Figure 23). Users can import compounds of interest by either drawing molecules using an integrated sketcher or uploading a list of molecules in SMILES format. Users can also inspect a 3D visualization of their molecular structures post-drawing. The platform can be also used for high-throughput virtual screening through batch processing: users can upload SDF files and process multiple compounds with one query. The results include the predicted property value(s) and/or toxicity class. Apart from the predictions for each model their reliability according to the corresponding APD is presented.

The screenshot displays the INSIGHT Cheminformatics Suite interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs for 'About', 'Sketcher Mode', and 'Virtual Screening Mode'. The main workspace is divided into three sections: 'Chemical Sketcher' with a drawing tool and a 3D visualization window, 'List of SMILES' with a list of chemical structures and 'Import Smile'/'Delete Selected' buttons, and '3D Visualization' showing a ball-and-stick model of a molecule. Below the workspace, there are 'Execute' and 'Open in NGL viewer' buttons. On the left, there are two panels: 'Execution model' with various prediction models (logS, PPAR-gamma, Mouse Tox, Fish Aquatic Toxicity, Vapor Pressure, Henry's law Constant, Ready Biodegradability, OVERALL OZONE Half-life) and 'Properties' with 'Molecular Properties' and 'Medicinal Chemistry Properties' checkboxes. On the right, there is a 'Predictions per molecule' table and a 'Download results' button.

Molecule	Molecular Weight	logS	PPAR-gamma	Mouse Tox	Fish Aquatic Toxicity (LC50)	Vapor Pressure (EPISUITE)	Henry's law Constant (Group Method)	Ready Biodegradability Prediction	OVERALL OZONE Half-life
CC1=CC(C(CCC1)C)C=CC(=CC(=CC)C)C	228.34	2.84	active	active	160 mm Hg	0.241	3.091	11.2 mm Hg	4.15
C1C(C(CO1N2C=C(C(=O)N2=O)C(F)(F)F)CO)O	284.27	-1.54	active	active	2100 mm Hg	0.808	0.000	0.000	0.000

Figure 23: INSIGHT Cheminformatics Suite GUI.

Table 25: List of models included in the INSIGHT Cheminformatics Suite web-application.

Endpoint	Model description
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logS

A kNN/read-across model for the prediction of water solubility at 25°C (expressed as logS) of small molecules based on their 2D structural descriptors. In the downloaded output the training neighbours and their distances from the input substances are presented, allowing the evaluation of structural similarity patterns. The dataset used for model development can be found in the [ChemPharos DB](#). For more information on model development refer to the corresponding publication (Koutroumpa et al., 2025). The model is developed by NovaMechanics Ltd under the EU H2020 project SCENARIOS (grant agreement No. 101037509).

PPAR- γ potency

A synergistic consensus model for the prediction of small molecule cytotoxicity to PPAR γ . The model is specifically designed for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). The dataset used for model development can be found in the [ChemPharos DB](#). For more information on model development refer to the corresponding publication (Antoniou et al., 2025). The model is developed by NovaMechanics Ltd under the EU H2020 project SCENARIOS (grant agreement No. 101037509).

MouseTox

A random forest model that predicts the cytotoxic effects of small molecules to NIH/3T3 (mouse embryonic fibroblast) cells, based on calculated structural descriptors. For more information on model development refer to the corresponding publication (Varsou et al., 2017). The model is developed by NovaMechanics Ltd under the EU FP7 project SysVirDrug (grant agreement No. KOINA/ERASysAPP-ERA.NET/1113).

Fish Aquatic Toxicity

This model predicts the aquatic toxicity in fish species using a benchmark dataset derived from ADORE, which is built upon the ECOTOX database. The toxicity endpoint, lethal concentration 50 (LC50), is expressed in log(LC50) units (mol/L). The dataset includes only experiments conducted over 96 hours and contains 1,640 SMILES–LC50 data points. Full documentation of the model is available at Jaqpot: <https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2183/description>. The model is developed by NTUA under the Horizon Europe project INSIGHT (grant agreement No. 101137742).

Vapor Pressure

This model refers to the estimation of a chemical's vapor pressure, which is the pressure exerted by a substance when it is in equilibrium between its liquid and vapor phases. It helps predict the volatility of a substance and its potential to evaporate into the atmosphere, influencing its environmental fate and transport. The model has the key value "aee3c2be-eb11-4abc-8cf8-2c2175568d3b" and is provided by the QSAR Toolbox through the QSAR Toolbox calculator service by the Jaqpot cloud platform: <https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/6/description>.

Henry's Law Constant

Henry's Law Constant is a value that describes the solubility of a gas in a liquid at a given temperature. This property helps predict the tendency of a chemical to partition between the air and water phases. The group method estimates the constant based on the molecular structure of the substance, and it is used to predict how chemicals behave in aquatic environments and the atmosphere. The model has the key value "bcaf3d05-13b1-4adf-ae2-0ace456a4cd7" and is provided by the QSAR Toolbox through the QSAR Toolbox calculator service by the Jaqpot cloud platform: <https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/6/description>.

Ready Biodegradability

This model estimates a chemical's potential to undergo biodegradation under aerobic conditions. This property helps assess the persistence of a substance in the environment and its likelihood of breaking down into less harmful substances, which is crucial for environmental risk assessments. The model has the key value "8a60f10c-d448-415f-80e7-2410234d2dc3" and is provided by the QSAR Toolbox through the QSAR Toolbox calculator service by the Jaqpot cloud platform: <https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/6/description>.

Overall Ozone Half-life

Overall Ozone Half-life refers to the time it takes for a chemical to degrade by half in the presence of ozone in the atmosphere. This property is important for understanding the atmospheric lifetime of a compound and its potential impact on the ozone layer. It is particularly relevant for assessing the environmental fate of chemicals that may contribute to ozone depletion. The model has the key value "11d0eb5c-c12c-4454-b0d3-f941518ec8d4" and is provided by the QSAR Toolbox through the QSAR Toolbox calculator service by the Jaqpot cloud platform: <https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/6/description>.

RatTox

A robust kNN model for the prediction of PFAS acute oral toxicity class (“High” or “Low”) in rats. The model was trained on PFAS compounds categorised according to their LD₅₀ (mg/kg) values and the toxicity thresholds established by the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). The downloadable output provides the predicted class, a reliability indication, and the three closest training set neighbours with their distances to the query compound, enabling structural similarity analyses. The dataset used for model development can be found in the [ChemPharos DB](#). The model is developed by NovaMechanics Ltd under the Horizon Europe project INSIGHT (grant agreement No. 101137742).

Table 26: INSIGHT Cheminformatics Suite inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Chemical sketcher	-	Compound structure drawing
SMILES string	-	SMILES strings list of query compounds
SDF	-	Spatial data file with query compounds
Execution model	-	Model(s) to be executed see Table 25
Properties	-	List of Molecular and Medicinal Chemistry Properties to be calculated

Table 27: INSIGHT Cheminformatics Suite outputs (depending on user input).

Name	Units	Description
Molecule	-	Input compounds SMILES representation
logS	-	Water solubility at 25°C prediction per input structure
PPAR-γ potency	-	PPAR-γ potency class prediction (active/inactive) per input structure
MouseTox	-	Cytotoxicity class prediction (toxic/non-toxic) per input structure
Fish Aquatic Toxicity	mol/L	Lethal concentration 50 (LC50), expressed in log(LC50) per input structure
Vapor Pressure	mm Hg	The vapour pressure per input structure
Henry's Law Constant	atm.m ³ /mol	Henry's Law constant per input structure
Ready Biodegradability	-	Ready/Not Ready Biodegradability per input structure

Overall Ozone Half-life		Overall Ozone Half-life per input structure
Molecular Properties	-	Molecular weight (MW) Formula Number of hydrogen bond donors (Num H-Donors) Number of hydrogen bond acceptors (Num H-Acceptors) Number of rings (Num Rings) Number of rotatable bonds (Num Rotatable Bonds) Topological polar surface area (TPSA)
Medicinal Chemistry Properties	-	Drug-likeness (QED) ranging in [0,1] Synthetic Accessibility score (SAscore) transformed in range [0,1] Lipinski's Rule of five (True/False) PAINS (Pan-Assay Interference compounds) alerts (True/False)

3.2.11. Enalos Cloud Platform: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod CO

To predict the adsorption energy of gases such as CO on nickel-based nanoclusters of varying sizes, ranging from Ni₁ to Ni₁₅, and across different ionization states (neutral, anionic, cationic). The predictive model has been trained using quantum-chemical and physicochemical descriptors derived from density functional theory (DFT) calculations, and experimental data, processed and structured within the nanoPharos database and analysed via the Isalos Analytics Platform. The model has been rigorously validated and checked. The web tool developed enables users to either upload their own data or select from predefined data and receive immediate predictions of gas-cluster interaction energies, electronic properties, and adsorption profiles. Figure 24 illustrates the user interface of the 'PredMod CO' web application, developed. This web application, which can be accessed through the following uniform resource locator (URL) link: <https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/mlnanocatco/>, enables users to predict the adsorption energy of CO molecules on nickel nanoclusters of varying size (Ni₁–Ni₁₅) and charge states using a ML model trained on DFT-derived descriptors. Through an intuitive, form-based input grid and batch upload option, the tool delivers rapid, reliable prediction.

Figure 24 ML-NANOCAT: PredMod CO GUI.

Table 28: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod CO model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Nickel Cluster Size	-	Number of nickel atoms in the cluster
SCF Energy	Hartrees	Total energy from self-consistent field (quantum mechanical) calculations
Nuclear Repulsion	Hartrees	Energy from repulsion between atomic nuclei
Dipole Magnitude	Debye	Overall strength of the molecular dipole moment
Dipole X/Y/Z	Debye	Components of the dipole moment along the X, Y and Z axes
Ni-C Distance	Å	Distance between a nickel atom and a carbon atom
Ni-O Distance	Å	Distance between a nickel atom and an oxygen atom
Charge Transfer	e ⁻	Amount of electron transfer from the adsorbate to the nickel surface
Type	-	Charge state of the adsorbate (anion, cation or neutral)

Table 29: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod CO model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Prediction	Hartrees	The estimated adsorption energy for each sample
Domain	-	The APD distance, which indicates how close each sample is to the model's known chemical space
Reliability	-	A binary indicator showing whether the sample falls within the model's APD

3.2.12. Enalos Cloud Platform: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod NO₂

To predict the adsorption energy of gases such as NO₂ on nickel-based nanoclusters of varying sizes, ranging from Ni₁ to Ni₁₅, and across different ionization states (neutral, anionic, cationic). The predictive model has been trained using quantum-chemical and physicochemical descriptors derived from DFT calculation. The model has been rigorously validated and checked. The web tool developed enables users to either upload their own data or select from predefined data and receive immediate predictions of gas-cluster interaction energies, electronic properties, and adsorption profiles. Figure 25 illustrates the user interface of the ‘PredMod NO₂’ web application, developed. This web application, which can be accessed through the following link: <https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/mlnanocatno2/>, enables users to predict the adsorption energy of NO₂ molecules on nickel nanoclusters of varying size (Ni₁–Ni₁₅) and charge states using a ML model trained on DFT-derived descriptors. Through an intuitive, form-based input grid and batch upload option, the tool delivers rapid, reliable prediction.

Figure 25: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod NO₂ GUI.

Table 30: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod NO₂ model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Nickel Cluster Size	-	Number of nickel atoms in the cluster
SCF Energy	Hartrees	Total energy from self-consistent field (quantum mechanical) calculations
Nuclear Repulsion	Hartrees	Energy from repulsion between atomic nuclei
Dipole Magnitude	Debye	Overall strength of the molecular dipole moment
Dipole X/Y/Z	Debye	Components of the dipole moment along the X, Y and Z axes
Ni-O Distance	Å	Distance between a nickel atom and an oxygen atom
Ni-N Distance	Å	Distance between a nickel atom and a nitrogen atom
Charge Transfer	e ⁻	Amount of electron transfer from the adsorbate to the nickel surface

Type	-	Charge state of the adsorbate (anion, cation or neutral)
------	---	--

Table 31: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod NO₂ model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Prediction	Hartrees	The estimated adsorption energy for each sample
Domain	-	The APD distance, which indicates how close each sample is to the model's known chemical space
Reliability	-	A binary indicator showing whether the sample falls within the model's APD

3.2.13. Enalos Cloud Platform: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod O₂

To predict the adsorption energy of gases such as O₂ on nickel-based nanoclusters of varying sizes, ranging from Ni₁ to Ni₁₅, and across different ionization states (neutral, anionic, cationic). The predictive model has been trained using quantum-chemical and physicochemical descriptors derived from DFT calculation. The model has been rigorously validated and checked. The web tool developed enables users to either upload their own data or select from predefined data and receive immediate predictions of gas-cluster interaction energies, electronic properties, and adsorption profiles. Figure 26 illustrates the user interface of the 'PredMod O₂' web application, developed. This web application, which can be accessed through the following link: <https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/mlnanocato2/>, enables users to predict the adsorption energy of O₂ molecules on nickel nanoclusters of varying size (Ni₁–Ni₁₅) and charge states using a ML model trained on DFT-derived descriptors. Through an intuitive, form-based input grid and batch upload option, the tool delivers rapid, reliable prediction.

Figure 26: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod O₂ GUI.

Table 32: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod O₂ model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Nickel Cluster Size	-	Number of nickel atoms in the cluster
SCF Energy	Hartrees	Total energy from self-consistent field (quantum mechanical) calculations
Nuclear Repulsion	Hartrees	Energy from repulsion between atomic nuclei
Dipole Magnitude	Debye	Overall strength of the molecular dipole moment
Dipole X/Y/Z	Debye	Components of the dipole moment along the X, Y and Z axes
Ni-O Distance	Å	Distance between a nickel atom and an oxygen atom
Charge Transfer	e ⁻	Amount of electron transfer from the adsorbate to the nickel surface
Type	-	Charge state of the adsorbate (anion, cation or neutral)

Table 33: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod O₂ model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Prediction	Hartrees	The estimated adsorption energy for each sample
Domain	-	The APD distance, which indicates how close each sample is to the model's known chemical space
Reliability	-	A binary indicator showing whether the sample falls within the model's APD

3.2.14. Enalos Cloud Platform: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod SO₂

To predict the adsorption energy of gases such as SO₂ on nickel-based nanoclusters of varying sizes, ranging from Ni₁ to Ni₁₅, and across different ionization states (neutral, anionic, cationic). The predictive model has been trained using quantum-chemical and physicochemical descriptors derived from DFT calculation. The model has been rigorously validated and checked. The web tool developed enables users to either upload their own data or select from predefined data and receive immediate predictions of gas-cluster interaction energies, electronic properties, and adsorption profiles. Figure 27 illustrates the user interface of the 'PredMod SO₂' web application, developed. This web application, which can be accessed through the following link: <https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/mlnanocatso2/>, enables users to predict the adsorption energy of SO₂ molecules on nickel nanoclusters of varying size (Ni₁–Ni₁₅) and charge states using a ML model trained on DFT-derived descriptors. Through an intuitive, form-based input grid and batch upload option, the tool delivers rapid, reliable prediction.

Figure 27: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod SO₂ GUI.

Table 34: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod SO₂ model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Nickel Cluster Size	-	Number of nickel atoms in the cluster
SCF Energy	Hartrees	Total energy from self-consistent field (quantum mechanical) calculations
Nuclear Repulsion	Hartrees	Energy from repulsion between atomic nuclei
Dipole Magnitude	Debye	Overall strength of the molecular dipole moment
Dipole X/Y/Z	Debye	Components of the dipole moment along the X, Y and Z axes
Ni-O Distance	Å	Distance between a nickel atom and an oxygen atom
Ni-S Distance	Å	Distance between a nickel atom and a sulfur atom
Charge Transfer	e ⁻	Amount of electron transfer from the adsorbate to the nickel surface
Type	-	Charge state of the adsorbate (anion, cation or neutral)

Table 35: ML-NANOCAT: PredMod SO₂ model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Prediction	Hartrees	The estimated adsorption energy for each sample
Domain	-	The APD distance, which indicates how close each sample is to the model's known chemical space
Reliability	-	A binary indicator showing whether the sample falls within the model's APD

3.2.15. Enalos Cloud Platform: MouseTox

The MouseTox application (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/MouseTox/>) provides robust predictive capabilities for cytotoxicity predictions, using a QSAR model. This user-friendly, web-based tool (Figure 28) enables researchers -regardless of computational expertise- to predict the cytotoxic class (active or inactive) of the tested chemical compounds to NIH/3T3 (mouse embryonic fibroblast) cells, by leveraging a highly accurate and extensively validated Random Forest (n_trees = 12) model as described by Varsou et al., 2017 demonstrating a strong predictive performance (test set accuracy = 0.832). In addition to uptake predictions, the application provides an APD assessment to help users interpret the reliability of the predictions. Within this web-tool, users can import compounds of interest by either drawing molecules using an integrated sketcher or uploading a list of molecules in SMILES format. The required input consists of nine molecular descriptors, which are automatically calculated via the Enalos Mold2 tool from the SMILES strings representing the compounds. The platform can also be used for high-throughput virtual screening through batch processing: users can upload SDF files and process multiple compounds with one query.

MouseTox: Prediction of small molecules cytotoxic effect to NIH/3T3 cells through Enalos Cloud Platform

The screenshot displays the MouseTox web application interface. On the left, there is a 'Design a molecule' section with a chemical sketcher showing a complex organic molecule. Below it are buttons for 'Execute' and 'Write smiles to text'. In the center, the 'Enter SMILES separated by newline' section contains a list of SMILES strings and an 'Execute' button. Below that is an 'Upload an SDF file (.sdf)' section with an 'upload' button and a file selection prompt, and another 'Execute' button. On the right, the 'Description' section provides a detailed explanation of the in silico predictive model and its results. Below the description is a 'Download files' button and a table of predictions.

Row ID	Prediction (Class)	Prediction
Row0	"active"	"reliable"
Row1	"active"	"reliable"
Row2	"active"	"reliable"
Row3	"inactive"	"reliable"
Row4	"inactive"	"reliable"
Row5	"inactive"	"reliable"

Figure 28: MouseTox GUI.

Table 36: MouseTox model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Chemical sketcher	-	Compound structure drawing
SMILES string	-	SMILES strings list of query compounds
SDF	-	Spatial data file with query compounds

Table 37: MouseTox model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Prediction (Class)	-	Cytotoxicity class prediction (toxic/non-toxic) per input structure
Prediction	-	Reliability of the toxicity prediction (reliable/unreliable) per input structure

3.2.16. Enalos Cloud Platform: NanoConstruct

NanoConstruct (<https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/riskgone/nanoconstruct/>) is a state-of-the-art computational tool that enables a) the digital construction of spherical and ellipsoidal neutral energy minimized NPs in vacuum through its graphical user-friendly interface (Figure 29), and b) the calculation of NPs atomistic descriptors. It allows the user to upload the NP material CIF and select its shape and size by inserting its ellipsoidal axes and rotation angle. To investigate the stability of materials not yet synthesised, NanoConstruct allows the substitution of the chemical elements of an already synthesized material with chemical elements that belong into the same group and neighbouring rows of the periodic table. The process is divided into three stages: 1) digital construction of the unit cell, 2) digital construction of NP using geometry rules and keeping its stoichiometry and 3) energy minimization of the geometrically constructed NP and calculation of its atomistic descriptors. More information about the tool can be found in the work of Kolokathis et al., 2024d.

User Guide

Download demo cif file

The screenshot displays the NanoConstruct web-tool interface, organized into three stages:

- Stage 1: Load the material***
 - Buttons: "Load your CIF file"
 - Input: CeO2_1562989.cif
 - Atom Types Found: Ce, O
 - Dropdowns: Ce, O
 - Image: 3D crystal structure of CeO2 with lattice parameters: $HM: P m \bar{3} m \#225 : a, b, c$, $a=5.407\text{\AA}$, $b=5.407\text{\AA}$, $c=5.407\text{\AA}$, $\alpha=90.000^\circ$, $\beta=90.000^\circ$, $\gamma=90.000^\circ$.
- Stage 2: Construct a Nanoparticle without Force-Field**
 - Select shape: Sphere, Ellipse
 - Insert the length of ellipsoid axes in nm: Axis X: 5, Axis Y: 4, Axis Z: 4
 - Rotation vector of ellipse in degrees (°): Axis X: 0, Axis Y: 0, Axis Z: 1, Rotation Angle: 0
 - Button: "Nanoparticle Construction without Force-Field"
 - Image: 3D model of a spherical nanoparticle.
- Stage 3: Construct an Energy Minimized Nanoparticle/Calculation of Atomistic Descriptors**
 - The Available Force-Fields: Sim_LAMMPS_Buckingham_Arim
 - Energy Tolerance = 0.01
 - Force Tolerance = 0.000001
 - Maximum Iterations = 1000
 - Maximum number of Force/Energy evaluation = 100000
 - Button: "Apply Energy Minimization to the Nanoparticle"
 - Image: 3D model of an energy-minimized nanoparticle.

Figure 29: GUI of the NanoConstruct web-tool.

Table 38: NanoConstruct inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Load the material	-	CIF file of the query material
Construct Nanoparticle	a nm	Sphere/Ellipse NP size Axes and rotation vector (for ellipsoid NPs)

Funded by the European Union

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without Force-Field		
Construct an Energy Minimized Nanoparticle/Calculation of Atomistic Descriptors	-	Force Field (pre-validated list) Energy Tolerance Force Tolerance Maximum Iterations Maximum number of Force/Energy evaluation

Table 39: NanoConstruct output files.

Name	Units	Description
Geom_NP.xyz	-	XYZ file of the geometrically constructed NP
Minim_NP.xyz	-	XYZ file of the energy-minimized NP
lammmps.data	-	LAMMPS datafiles for both geometrically constructed and energy-minimized NPs
descriptors.txt descriptors.csv	-	Descriptor files in .csv and .txt formats, see the full list of descriptors in the work of Kolokathis et al., 2024d
Stage1.png Stage2.png Stage3.png	-	Image files of the unit cell, the geometrically constructed and energy-minimized NPs

3.2.17. Enalos Cloud Platform: Nano Protein Corona Model

The development of safe-by-design NMs is closely linked to -and often constrained by- our understanding of the complex interactions between nanostructures and biological systems. In particular, the phenomenon of “protein corona” formation -where NPs undergo surface modification through adsorption of proteins upon exposure to biological media- remains insufficiently explored. To further advance research in this field, the Nano Protein Corona Model (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/nanocommons/NanoProteinCorona/>) provides robust predictive capabilities for the assessment of the cellular association (which can include both internalized NPs and those attached to the cell surface) of surface-modified gold NPs. A dataset of 105 unique gold NPs, fully characterized in terms of their physicochemical properties, protein corona compositions, and cellular association to A549 human lung epithelial carcinoma cells, was utilized to develop a QNAR model for cellular association predictions. A highly accurate and extensively validated kNN model ($k = 6$), demonstrating a strong predictive performance (validation set $R^2 = 0.832$) is offered through this user-friendly, web-based tool. In addition to cellular association predictions, the application provides an APD assessment to help users interpret the reliability of the predictions. The intuitive interface (Figure 30) ensures accessibility for users from diverse scientific backgrounds, streamlining the integration of computational modelling into NM research and development. Within this web-tool, users

can import in tabular format NPs physicochemical characteristics (measured on the NPs dispersed in serum) and corona protein fingerprints, to rapidly acquire normalized cellular association predictions in log2mL/mg(Mg). The platform can also be used for high-throughput virtual screening through batch processing: users can upload CSV files and process multiple NPs with one query. More information can be found in the work of Afantitis et al., 2018.

Figure 30: Nano Protein Corona Model GUI.

Table 40: Nano Protein Corona Model model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Z-AHD	nm	Z-Average Hydrodynamic Diameter of NPs dispersed in serum
ZP	mV	Zeta Potential of NPs dispersed in serum
LSPR	-	Localized Surface Plasmon Resonance (LSPR) index of NPs dispersed in serum
P01024	-	Complement C3 (ratio of total surface proteins)
P02766	-	Transthyretin (ratio of total surface proteins)
P08697	-	Alpha-2-antiplasmin (ratio of total surface proteins)
PI9823	-	Inter-alpha-trypsin inhibitor heavy chain (ratio of total surface proteins)
Q13103	-	Secreted phosphoprotein 24 (ratio of total surface proteins)
Q9UK55	-	Protein Z-dependent protease inhibitor (ratio of total surface proteins)
P02788	-	Lactotransferrin (ratio of total surface proteins)
P02775	-	Platelet basic protein (ratio of total surface proteins)
PI4625	-	Endoplasmin (ratio of total surface proteins)
Q96KN2	-	Beta-Ala-His dipeptidase (ratio of total surface proteins)

Table 41: Nano Protein Corona Model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Prediction (log ₂ -transformed cell association)	log ₂ mL/ mg(Mg)	Normalized cellular association predictions per input NP
Domain	-	Reliability of the prediction (reliable/unreliable) per input NP

3.2.18. Enalos Cloud Platform: NanoTube Construct

NanoTube Construct (<https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/diagonal/nanotube/>) enables users, regardless of computational expertise, to digitally construct nanotubes based on real and hypothetical (i.e., theoretically possible, but not yet synthesized) single layer materials, including carbon-based and non-carbon materials (Figure 31). Within the intuitive GUI (Figure 32), researchers can perform nanotube construction and apply energy minimization techniques without extensive knowledge of the underlying computational theory. Importantly, NanoTube Construct calculates atomistic descriptors for both the original nanosheets and the constructed nanotubes. These descriptors can be used as input for predictive models, enabling advanced data analysis and property optimization -offering a powerful alternative to time-consuming experimental studies in the field of material discovery.

Figure 31: Single layer materials options available in NanoTube Construct. Carbon, hydrogen, silicon, oxygen, germanium, boron, nitrogen, tungsten, sulphide and molybdenum atoms are illustrated with brown, pink, bright blue, red, dark blue, green, light blue, dark grey, yellow and light magenta respectively.

Briefly, the most significant features offered by NanoTube Construct include:

- Flexibility in material selection: it is not limited to zero-thickness materials with specific symmetries.
- Energy minimization: it uses atomistic Force-Fields and applies Energy Minimization to geometrically constructed nanotubes generating physically realistic structures.
- Descriptor generation: it calculates atomistic descriptors.
- Primitive unit cell extraction: it provides the primitive unit cell of the constructed nanotube corresponding to the selected rolling vector (i.e., the direction in which the nanosheet is rolled into a tube).
- Energetic stability analysis: it assesses whether the nanotube or the corresponding nanosheet is more energetically stable.
- Chirality flexibility: it allows the use of negative chirality indices enabling the user to construct all possible nanotube configurations

More information about the tool and the descriptors can be found in the work of Kolokathis et al., 2024c.

Figure 32: NanoTube Construct tool GUI.

Table 42: NanoTube Construct tool inputs

Name	Units	Description
Select material	-	Selection among seven carbon-based and seven non-carbon 2-D materials
Construct geometrically the Nanosheet and the corresponding Nanotube	Å	Wrap direction Periodicity Length of nanotube
Construct an Energy Minimized Nanoparticle/Calculation of Atomistic Descriptors	-	Force Field (pre-validated list) Energy Tolerance Force Tolerance Maximum Iterations Maximum number of Force/Energy evaluation

Table 43: NanoTube Construct tool output files.

Name	Units	Description
nanosheet.xyz Nanotube.xyz	-	XYZ file of the geometrically constructed nanotube and nanosheet
Minim-Nanosheet.xyz Minim-Nanotube.xyz	-	XYZ file of the energy-minimized nanotube and nanosheet
Nanotube-lammps.data Nanosheet-lammps.data data_nanotube.after_minimization.data data_nanosheet.after_minimization.data	-	LAMMPS datafiles for both geometrically constructed and energy-minimized nanotube and nanosheet
descriptors_Nanosheet.txt descriptors_Nanotube.txt descriptors_tot.txt descriptors_tot.csv	-	Descriptor files in .csv and .txt formats, see the full list of descriptors in the work of Kolokathis et al., 2024c.
Stage1_az_0_el_0.png Stage1_az_0_el_4.png Stage2.png Stage3_az_0_el_3.png Stage4-Nanosheet.png Stage5_az_0_el_3.png	-	Image files of the unit cell, the geometrically constructed and energy-minimized nanotube and nanosheet

3.2.19. Enalos Cloud Platform: Pólis

This web-tool (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/insight/polis/>) hosts a consensus predictive scheme for the assessment of small molecules mutagenicity class. This scheme incorporates three models: a read-across type ('guided-kNN'), a QSAR-type (Extreme Gradient Boosting, XGBoost) and a deep learning model (based on Graph Convolutional Neural Networks, GCNNs). These models are built upon different molecular featurization approaches (2D and 3D descriptors, molecular fingerprints and molecular graphs) considering compound stereochemistry whenever possible. The mutagenicity predictions from the three models are integrated in a majority voting scheme to enhance the overall predictive accuracy (83% in external validation) and reduce individual model biases.

Users can input one or more compounds of interest either by drawing them using the built-in sketcher or by uploading a list of molecules in SMILES or SDF format. For critical decisions, users are advised to submit fully specified stereochemistry to achieve maximal reliability. The platform provides multiple visualization options, allowing users to inspect compounds in both 2D and 3D. Upon submission, mutagenicity predictions for each input structure ("mutagen" or "non-mutagen") are generated within seconds. The results include individual predictions from each model, a consensus prediction, and an assessment of reliability based on the models' APD (Figure 33). All results can be downloaded for further analysis, offering flexibility for various research needs. The downloadable files include: the predictions of each model and the consensus outcome, the reliability assessments based on the corresponding APD, the nine nearest training neighbours used in the guided-kNN model, and the canonical SMILES representations of each input compound (sanitized and standardized), to enhance reproducibility.

Figure 33: Pólis web service GUI.

Table 44: Pólis model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Chemical sketcher	-	Compound structure drawing
SMILES string	-	SMILES strings list of query compounds
SDF	-	Spatial data file with query compounds

Table 45: Pólis model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Prediction (guided-kNN)	-	Mutagenicity class prediction (mutagen/non-mutagen) per input structure based on the guided-kNN model
AD similarity	-	APD limits considering compounds fingerprint similarity to the training set
Prediction (GCNN)	-	Mutagenicity class prediction (mutagen/non-mutagen) per input structure based on the GCNN model
Prediction (XGBoost)	-	Mutagenicity class prediction (mutagen/non-mutagen) per input structure based on the XGBoost model
AD distance	-	APD limits considering compounds distances from the training set
Consensus	-	Mutagenicity class prediction (mutagen/non-mutagen) per input structure based on the voting scheme

Reliability	-	Reliability of the prediction (low/moderate/high) per input structure considering the two APD limits
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3.2.20. Enalos Cloud Platform: Prediction of MNPs Uptake in PaCa2 Cancer Cells

To facilitate the *in silico* analysis of numerous NPs, the Prediction of MNPs Uptake in PaCa2 Cancer Cells web-based application -offered by the Enalos Cloud Platform (https://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/QNAR_PaCa2/)- provides robust predictive capabilities for magnetofluorescent NPs functionalized with a variety of synthetic small molecules, using a QNAR model as described by Melagraki and Afantitis, 2014. This user-friendly, web-based tool enables researchers -regardless of computational expertise- to predict the uptake of these NPs in PaCa2 (pancreatic cancer) cells, by leveraging a highly accurate and extensively validated kNN model ($k = 2$), demonstrating a strong predictive performance ($R^2 = 0.848$). In addition to uptake predictions, the application provides an APD assessment to help users interpret the reliability of the predictions. The intuitive interface (Figure 34) ensures accessibility for users from diverse scientific backgrounds, streamlining the integration of computational modelling into NM research and development. Within this web-tool, users can import compounds of interest by either drawing molecules using an integrated sketcher or uploading a list of molecules in SMILES format. The required input consists of nine molecular descriptors, which are automatically calculated via the Enalos Mold2 tool from the SMILES strings representing the decorative compounds. The platform can also be used for high-throughput virtual screening through batch processing: users can upload SDF files and process multiple compounds with one query.

 Prediction of MNPs Uptake in PaCa2 Cancer Cells through Enalos Cloud Platform

The screenshot shows the Enalos Cloud Platform interface. On the left is a chemical sketcher with a toolbar and a drawing area containing a complex organic molecule. In the center, there is a text input field for SMILES strings, with a list of example strings: C1=CC=C2C(=C1)C(=O)C3=C(C2=O)C(=C(C=C3)O)O, COC1=CC=C(C=C1)C(C2=CC=C(C=C2)C)C(C)C1, C1C(O)C(C1O)N2C=NC3=C(N=CN=C32)N)CO, C1=CC=C2C(=C1)C(=CN2)C(C(=O)O)N, and C1=NC2=NC=NC(=C2N1)N. Below the input field are buttons for 'Execute', 'Upload an SDF file (.sdf)', and 'Write smile to text'. On the right, a 'Description' box explains the QNAR model. Below that is a 'Download files' button and a table with the following data:

Row ID	PaCa2 cellular uptake	Domain of Applicability Prediction
"Row0"	2.6300888298053935	"reliable"
"Row1"	3.738886599066064	"reliable"
"Row2"	3.536279178609997	"reliable"
"Row3"	3.2367380195958475	"reliable"
"Row4"	3.7146276460413357	"reliable"

Figure 34: Prediction of MNPs Uptake in PaCa2 Cancer Cells model GUI.

Table 46: Prediction of MNPs Uptake in PaCa2 Cancer Cells model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Chemical sketcher	-	Compound structure drawing
SMILES string	-	SMILES strings list of query compounds
SDF	-	Spatial data file with query compounds

Table 47: Prediction of MNPs Uptake in PaCa2 Cancer Cells model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
PaCa2 cellular uptake	log ₁₀ [NP in pM]/cell	PaCa2 cellular uptake predicted value per input structure
Domain of Applicability Prediction	-	Reliability of the cellular uptake prediction (reliable/unreliable) per input structure

3.2.21. Enalos Cloud Platform: Safe-by-design tool for functionalised NMs

MWCNTs are currently used in numerous industrial applications and products, therefore fast and accurate evaluation of their biological and toxicological effects is of greatest importance. In this course, two predictive QNAR/kNN models for the assessment of decorated MWCNTs biological (accuracy 85.7%) and toxicological profile (accuracy 84.2%) are developed (Varsou et al., 2019), validated, and released as a web-service through Enalos Cloud Platform (<http://enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/CNT/>). This web-service is a ready-to-use, user-friendly application whose purpose is to facilitate decision making, by reducing expensive and time-consuming experimental procedures (Figure 35). During a safe-by-design process, different data sets with decorators of interest can be imported, and their effects on the biological and toxicity behavior of the resulting decorated MWCNTs can be studied. The kNN model is based only on the structure of the MWCNT decorating molecules, which can be provided easily to the model using different input methods (SMILES list, SDF file, structure drawing). The predictions of the MWCNTs toxicity and biological activity (protein binding of carbonic anhydrase), and their reliability are produced and presented to the user within seconds, as well as the neighbours in the training set of each decorating molecule.

3.2.22. Enalos Cloud Platform: SafeNanoScope

The SafeNanoScope web-service (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/sabydoma/safenanoscope/>) hosts a random forest model for the prediction of the adverse effects class (against HepaRG cell line) of Ag, TiO₂ and CuO NPs based on their properties in atomistic level. Nanoinformatics models were developed using data on the *in vitro* toxicity of Ag, TiO₂, and CuO NPs generated under the NanoMILE project. Specifically, the human hepatoma HepaRG cell line was treated with 89 NPs at 10 different concentrations, and 14 imaging endpoints were measured through a High Throughput Screening (HTS) – High Content Imaging (HCI) study to initially classify NP hazards and identify candidates for further toxicological assessment. From this NP library, endpoint and dose-response data on 11 Ag, TiO₂, and CuO NPs was used to develop the current model (a total of 110 treatments – combinations of NP samples and concentrations). The main type of experiments assessed the mitochondrial health and cell viability by measuring 9 features/endpoints and the results of the HTS-HCI screening were normalized following the signal-to-noise ratio approach. The normalized values were presented in a color-coded heatmap, which reflected the degree of difference in behavior from the control (red and blue for decreased or increased response, respectively) or indicated that the response was similar to that of the negative control (green color).

To perform the *in silico* assessment of the toxicity of NPs on the HepaRG cell line, the results of the 9 toxicity features were summarized into a single endpoint (“overall”) class as follows: NP treatments were classified as “low” effect if they had a similar response to the negative controls (green labels) in at least 5 measured features. Otherwise, NP treatments were classified as “high” effect (red and/or blue label). In the present work, the dataset of dose-response data was enriched with atomistic descriptors, considering the core of the NPs in vacuum. The dataset can be found in the [nanoPharos](#) database. Based on an automated ML (autoML) scheme, a random forest model was developed to predict the adverse effect profile of NP treatments on the HepaRG cell line considering the NPs concentration and their structure properties expressed as atomistic descriptors (accuracy 88% in external validation). To assess the adverse effect class of untested NPs, users should provide for each untested NP the values of the necessary set of descriptors, as well as the concentration of NPs. The atomistic descriptors for each NP can be calculated using the [ASCOT](#) tool provided by the Enalos SABYDOMA cloud platform or another software of choice (e.g., LAMMPS). To perform the simulations and acquire the computational descriptors, the size, the shape, and the phase of the NPs are needed. The SafeNanoScope web-service (Figure 36) produces the prediction of the effect profile of the input NPs (“low” or “high” effect) along with an indication of the predictions’ reliability based on the APD of the background model. More information can be found in the work of Varsou et al., 2024.

Figure 36: SafeNanoScope model GUI.

Table 50: SafeNanoScope model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Concentration	µg/mL	Concentration of NPs
AD1	-	Log10 of all atoms in the NP
AD3	-	Log10 of all atoms in the surface
AD7	eV	The average difference of the potential energy between core and shell atoms
AD9	-	The average coordination parameter of all atoms
AD14	-	The average coordination parameter (3Ang) of all atoms
AD16	-	The average coordination parameter (3Ang) of the shell atoms
AD17	-	The average difference of the coordination parameter (3Ang) between core and shell atoms
AD22	-	The average difference of the coordination parameter (4Ang) between core and shell atoms
AD27	-	The average difference of the coordination parameter (5Ang) between core and shell atoms
AD45	-	The average difference of the CNP (3Ang) between core and shell atoms

Table 51: SafeNanoScope model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Prediction (effect)	-	Adverse effects class (high/low toxicity on the HepaRG cell line) per input NP
Domain (leverage)	-	A binary value indicating whether the NP is located within the APD limits based on the leverage methodology
Domain (range)	-	A binary value indicating whether the NP is located within the APD limits based on the bounding-box methodology
Domain (similarity)	-	A binary value indicating whether the NP is located within the APD limits based on the local similarity methodology
Score	-	Weighted score to assess the overall reliability of each prediction
Reliability	-	Reliability of the generated predictions per input NP based on the model's APD limits (good/moderate/poor)

3.2.23. Enalos Cloud Platform: THALAMOSS Platform for Chelation

This web service hosts a validated model to predict the chelation outcome for thalassemia patients by applying clustering-based and machine-learning-based stratification techniques to a comprehensive clinical dataset from thalassemia patients. Data and biomarkers values were collected from 92 thalassemia patients of the Limassol Hospital (Cyprus). Patient ages ranged from 3 to 68 years, and the following variables were considered for model input: biological sex, age, vitamin D levels, T2 liver score, T score spine, T score femur, and diabetes presence. The patients were categorized into two groups based on chelation outcome: 47 patients with successful chelation (ferritin values < 1000 ng/mL) and 45 patients with unsuccessful chelation (ferritin values > 1000 ng/mL). The data were divided into training and test sets, comprising 64 and 28 patients, respectively. Attribute selection was based on training data, using Gain Attribute Evaluator and Ranker as the search method. The modeling methodology employed the classification algorithm kNN. The produced models were subsequently evaluated for their accuracy in predicting patient class outcomes using the independent test set.

The developed classification model was fully validated in accordance with the principles of model validation for accepting QSAR models as described by the Organization for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD). The model was both internally and externally validated as represented by goodness-of-fit, robustness and predictivity. The statistics for the training set are the following: precision = 94.3%, sensitivity = 100%, specificity = 93.5% and accuracy = 96.9%. By applying the model to the external test set, the following statistical results were obtained: precision = 80%, sensitivity = 85.7%, specificity = 78.6% and accuracy = 82.1%. The proposed model is made publicly available online through the Enalos Cloud Platform (Figure 37). Enalos Cloud Platform can host several validated predictive models that can be utilized for thalassemia patient's stratification (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/chelation/>).

THALAMOSS Platform for chelation prediction outcome (thalassemia patients) Powered by Enalos Cloud Platform

[User Guide](#) *Detailed information about the columns can be found at the bottom of the website*

Patient N.	Age	Sex	Vitamin D	T2* Liver	T Score Spine	T Score Femur	Diabetes
1	32	Male	600	0.13	0.11	0.1	YES
2	45	Female	583	0.1	0.1	0.11	NO
3		Male					NO
4		Male					NO
5		Male					NO
6		Male					NO
7		Male					NO
8		Male					NO
9		Male					NO
10		Male					NO
11		Male					NO
12		Male					NO
13		Male					NO
14		Male					NO
15		Male					NO
16		Male					NO
17		Male					NO
18		Male					NO
19		Male					NO
20		Male					NO

Execute computations

Upload csv file CSV name

Row ID	Age	Sex	Vitamin D	T2* liver	T score spine	T score femur	Diabetes	Prediction (Chelation)
"1"	32.0	"Male"	600.0	0.13	0.11	0.1	"YES"	"Unsuccessful"
"2"	45.0	"Female"	583.0	0.1	0.1	0.11	"NO"	"Unsuccessful"

Execute computations

Figure 37: THALAMOSS Platform for Chelation model GUI.

Table 52: THALAMOSS Platform for Chelation model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Age	Years	Patient's age
Sex	-	Patient's biological sex [female/male]
Vit. D	IU	Vitamin D level
T2* liver	ms	T2* relaxation time of the liver
T score spine	-	The standard deviation from the mean bone mineral density at the lumbar spine of healthy young adults of the same sex and age
T score femur	-	The standard deviation from the mean bone mineral density at the femoral neck of healthy young adults of the same sex and age
Diabetes	-	Diabetes presence [yes/no]

Table 53: THALAMOSS Platform for Chelation model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Age	Years	Patient's age
Sex	-	Patient's biological sex [female/male]
Vit. D	IU	Vitamin D level
T2* liver	ms	T2* relaxation time of the liver

T score spine	-	The standard deviation from the mean bone mineral density at the lumbar spine of healthy young adults of the same sex and age
T score femur	-	The standard deviation from the mean bone mineral density at the femoral neck of healthy young adults of the same sex and age
Diabetes	-	Diabetes presence [yes/no]
Chelation	-	Chelation prediction outcome per patient: Successful/Unsuccessful. A successful chelation is considered if the Ferritin values are below 1000 ng/mL.

3.2.24. Enalos Cloud Platform: UANanoDock

UANanoDock is a web-based application accessible via the Enalos Cloud Platform (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/compsafenano/uananodock/>) engineered for modelling protein-NM interactions (Figure 38). At its core lies the UnitedAtom multiscale model, a methodology previously established for predicting the adsorption energies of biopolymers and small molecules onto NPs. The fundamental concept involves a coarse-grained (CG) representation of the bio-nano interface, where proteins are modelled as rigid bodies composed of CG amino acid beads centred at the alpha-carbon positions. NPs are also treated as rigid, homogeneous or composite bodies with a defined shape (currently spherical in the web tool's release), specified surface potential (ζ -potential), and geometric dimensions (radius for spheres). More information about the tool can be found in the publication of Subbotina et al., 2025.

Figure 38: UANanoDock GUI.

Table 54: UANanoDock inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Protein preparation	-	Protein Coordinates: A Protein Data Bank (PDB) file containing the 3D coordinates of the protein.

		pH of the Solvent: A numerical value specifying the pH of the solution surrounding the NP and the protein.
Define Nanomaterial	-	<p>Nanoparticle Material: Selection from a dropdown list of available materials, including Ag, Au, Fe₂O₃, PEG, SiO₂ (amorphous and quartz), TiO₂ (anatase and rutile)</p> <p>Ionic Strength of the Solvent: A numerical value representing the ionic strength</p> <p>Temperature of the System: A numerical value indicating the temperature in Kelvin</p> <p>Nanoparticle Radius: A numerical value specifying the radius of the spherical NP in nm</p> <p>Electrostatic (ζ) Potential of the Material: A numerical value in millivolts (mV) defining the surface potential of the NP.</p> <p>hkl Plane of the NP (for crystalline materials): A text input for the Miller indices (hkl) of the NP's surface. For amorphous materials, the default is "000"</p> <p>Angular Resolution (optional): Users can adjust the angle step δ (in degrees) for sampling protein orientations and the number of samples used for energy weighting within each angular bin</p>

Table 55: UANanoDock output files.

Name	Units	Description
heatmap.png	-	A PNG image visually representing the average Boltzmann adsorption energy (in kJ/mol) for each sampled protein orientation defined by the ϕ and θ rotational angles.
prop-Ka2UA.uam	-	A text file containing the ϕ and θ angles used in the calculations, the corresponding adsorption energy for each orientation, and the minimum surface distance of any protein bead from the NP surface.
material.dat	-	A text file holding the Hamaker constants used for the selected NP material and crystal plane.
NP_protein_CG_min.pdb NP_protein_CG_min.xyz	-	These files provide the atomic (PDB) and coarse-grained (XYZ) coordinates of the protein in its predicted preferred orientation when adsorbed onto the NP surface.
UAAutorun_configautogen.config	-	A text file that can be used directly with the desktop version of the UnitedAtom software for more advanced simulations.

3.3. INTEGRA (Multimedia model & drinking water model)

Introduction

INTEGRA is a unified computational platform that integrates environmental fate, exposure, and internal dose dynamically in time. The INTEGRA modelling framework (Sarigiannis et al., 2014) brings together all available information for assessing the source-to-dose continuum for the entire life cycle of substances covering an extensive chemical space. One of the main modelling components of the INTEGRA platform is the multimedia model, which accounts for multi-scale (far field exposure) interactions affecting the environmental transport and fate of chemicals. The multimedia environmental modelling framework for INTEGRA, follows the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment (ECHA, 2016). All different spatial scales (local, regional, continental and global), media exchange (air, soil, water, sediment and transfer to food items such as crops, meat, milk and fish) and environmental processes (emissions, advection, diffusion, and degradation) (Lijzen and Rikken, 2004) were taken into account.

Modelling information

Table 56: Input and output requirements of the INTEGRA multimedia model.

Inputs	Values
Chemical name	e.g., BPA
CAS Number	e.g., 80-05-7
Kow	Log value
Molecular Weight	Numeric value in g/mol
Vapor Pressure	Numeric value in Pa
Density	Numeric value in kg/m ³
Enthalpy of vaporization	Numeric value in j/mol
Melting point	Numeric value in K
Theta constant	Numeric value
Enthalpy of solubility	Numeric value in j/mol
Henry Constant	Numeric value in Pa m ³ mol ⁻¹
Degradation constant for soil	Numeric value in h ⁻¹
Degradation constant for water	Numeric in h ⁻¹
Degradation constant for sediment	Numeric value in h ⁻¹
Degradation constant for air	Numeric value in h ⁻¹
Biodegradability	Yes or No
Geographical area	Definition of the continental, regional or local scale
Environmental emissions (continental, regional, local scale)	Numeric value in tn/year

Predicted No-Effect Concentrations (PNECs)	Numeric value for: freshwater, marine water, freshwater sediment, marine water sediment, soil and air
Outputs	Values
Concentration in gaseous phase at regional scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in particles phase at regional scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in surface waters sediment at regional scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in sea water sediment at regional scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in surface waters at regional scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in natural soil at regional scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in agricultural soil at regional scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in urban industrialized soil at regional scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in natural vegetation at regional scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in agricultural vegetation at regional scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in gaseous phase at continental scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in particles phase at continental scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in surface waters sediment at continental scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in sea water sediment at continental scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in surface waters at continental scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in natural soil at continental scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in agricultural soil at continental scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in urban industrialized soil at continental scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in natural vegetation at continental scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$

Concentration in agricultural vegetation at continental scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in gaseous phase at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in particles phase at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ Concentration in surface waters sediment at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in sea water sediment at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in surface waters at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in natural soil at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in agricultural soil at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in urban industrialized soil at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in natural vegetation at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in agricultural vegetation at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in small fishes	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in fishes – predators	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in fish	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in meal	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration sausage	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in milk	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in yogurt	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration cheese	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in animal fats	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in poultry	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in eggs	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in vegetable oils	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in vegetables	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in potatoes	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in fruit	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in nuts	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in urban industrialized soil at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in natural vegetation at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$

Concentration in agricultural vegetation at local scale	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
Concentration in small fishes	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in fishes – predators	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in fish	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in meal	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration sausage	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in milk	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in yogurt	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration cheese	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in animal fats	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in poultry	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in eggs	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in vegetable oils	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in vegetables	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in potatoes	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in fruit	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$
Concentration in nuts	Numeric value in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$

Table 57: Input and output requirement of the INTEGRA multimedia model for drinking water.

Inputs	Values
Years	Numeric value
Mean contaminant concentration	Numeric value in mg/L
SD of concentration	Numeric value
Mean total daily intake	Numeric value in L/day
SD of daily intake	Numeric value
Average number of drinking events per day	Numeric value
Outputs	Values
Concentration median	Numeric value in mg/L
Intake median	Numeric value in mg
Hourly exposure (lower, median, upper)	Numeric value in mg
Cumulative exposure (lower, median, upper)	Numeric value in mg

Modelling implementation

Implementation of API for the INTEGRA multimedia model: The INTEGRA Multimedia model API enables seamless integration with external systems for data retrieval interoperability with the model. The INTEGRA Multimedia model is part of the INTEGRA platform, which provides concentrations across various environmental media dynamically over time. Within the project, an API of the INTEGRA Multimedia model was developed, as a model that can provide estimates of the environmental exposure

to chemicals, including environmental concentrations to different environmental media (water, air, soil) and at different scales (local, regional, continental). The multimedia model of INTEGRA has been implemented as a RESTful API and developed using the plumber R package. The API is available internally within the project.

3.4. Enalos Suite

Enalos Suite, designed and developed by NovaM, is a stand-alone platform that gives access -via a user-friendly GUI- to various cheminformatics tools and models that may be of use in the areas of drug discovery and computational toxicology (Varsou et al., 2018). Through the Enalos Suite users can have access to multiple chemical databases (e.g., PubChem, UniChem, SureChEMBL, IBM patents, etc.), retrieve easily information for thousands of chemical compounds (e.g., structures, tests Assays, patents, etc.) and transform the structural information of the molecules into mathematical representations (“descriptors”) that can be used as inputs to other cheminformatics tools. Different cheminformatics models are available within the Enalos Suite and extension with additional models is permitted based on the special field of interest of each user, including, for instance, nanoinformatics, biomedical, and other applications. The user-oriented character of the software allows the data mining, manipulation of chemical information, automated analysis and prediction of properties through different UI compounds (e.g., menus, buttons, check-boxes, etc.) that any computer user is familiar with (Figure 39). Thus, researchers that do not have a strong computational background can benefit from the different cheminformatics functionalities without any need for complex scripting capabilities. In addition, the Enalos Suite workspace offers three different importing options: users can design a molecule using the drawing tool, they can import a SMILES list or they can import the chemical structures in SDF format. In fact, the chemical sketcher allows users to first draw a compound and later convert it to SMILES format. Thus, users can modify multiple structures and generate a large list of SMILES, ready for further analysis.

Figure 39: Screenshot of the Enalos Suite platform.

3.5. Enalos+ KNIME nodes

Enalos+ KNIME nodes developed by NovaM are a useful extension of the KNIME Analytics Platform when dealing with cheminformatics, bioinformatics and nanoinformatics tasks, personalized medicine, design of experiments, and text mining (Varsou et al., 2018a). In brief, Enalos+ nodes (Figure 40) enhance data mining of chemical databases (PubChem, UniChem, NCI, etc.), and molecular descriptors' calculation (Mold2). Especially for PubChem, Enalos+ includes a full and complete range of nodes: search for similar compounds, search for patents, extract compounds from patents, search for vendors, extract compounds from assays, etc. Several Enalos+ nodes support QSAR model development, e.g., for data pre-processing (Remove Columns), partitioning (Kennard-Stone), and validation (Y-randomization, Model Acceptability Criteria). Systematic review processes can be also facilitated through the Enalos+ text mining nodes that offer a group of tools that search over one or more written resources of interest and retrieve text passages, tables, and figures from any input text document. Statistical experimental design can be also performed in KNIME through the Enalos+ nodes which offer a wide range of methodologies, including screening, factorial and space filling design. Finally, the

Asclepios KNIME nodes offer advanced computational chemistry functionalities, including molecular docking as well as molecular dynamics simulations. All these nodes are under the same interface with the option to apply in real time a predictive model or other analysis tools.

Figure 40: Exemplary KNIME workflow using the Enalos+ nodes.

3.6. Isalos Analytics Platform

The Isalos Predictive Analytics Platform (Isalos) developed by NovaM is a simple, user-friendly software designed to facilitate data manipulation and model development without requiring programming skills (Varsou et al., 2023). This platform empowers non-programmers to engage in data analytics through an intuitive interface, which leverages commonly used computer functions such as menus, buttons, and spreadsheets. Isalos is designed to streamline the development of predictive models by allowing users to manipulate and process data in an accessible, visual format. The platform's primary goal is to enable data analysis without needing to write code, making it highly accessible to business professionals, analysts, or anyone with basic computer skills. The software provides users with an intuitive tool for the development of robust and validated models through menus, buttons, tabs, and spreadsheets; functions that are used regularly by any computer user. The core concept in the operation of Isalos is that each tab acts like a node, where data are imported and exported in a tabular format, following processing and transformation using specific functions (Figure 41).

Figure 41: Operational concept of Isalos platform. Isalos tabs act like nodes, where data are imported and exported in tabular format. In between they are processed and transformed using specific functions.

Interested users can leverage of the platform’s comprehensive set of tools for data pre-processing (including normalization, filtering, variable selection, and data partitioning), model development (with autoML support for both regression and classification tasks) and model validation, design of experiments, statistical analysis, and business intelligence within the same GUI. In addition, models developed within Isalos can be easily deployed via the Enalos Cloud Platform. More information can be found in the Isalos online documentation: <https://www.docs.isalos.novamechanics.com/>

3.7. Jaqpot cloud platform

Jaqpot is an open-source, cloud-based platform created by NTUA to support the fast development, deployment, and distribution of predictive models as web services. It is widely used in chemistry, toxicology, and materials science (Figure 42).

Figure 42: The landing page of the Jaqpot cloud platform.

For model developers, Jaqpot provides an intuitive environment for uploading, managing, and publishing models. The platform integrates tools for versioning, documentation, and automated performance assessment, helping streamline the entire lifecycle from model creation to deployment. Once published, each model can be accessed programmatically through a RESTful API and is enriched with comprehensive metadata, including details on provenance, uncertainty, APD, and validation. These features ensure that deployed models meet high standards of transparency, reproducibility, and regulatory compliance.

Jaqpot's RESTful APIs (Figure 43) follow the OpenAPI specification, enabling seamless integration into external workflows, pipelines, and software applications. For instance, a computational toxicology or risk assessment workflow can automatically query Jaqpot models to obtain predictions and incorporate them into broader SSbD evaluation processes.

Figure 43: Jaqpot API.

For non-technical end-users, such as material designers, regulators, industry professionals and decision makers, Jaqpot provides a web-based GUI that allows them to input data, run or re-run predictions, and view results without requiring programming skills. Outputs can be presented in interactive tables, downloadable reports, or visual dashboards, enabling quick interpretation and seamless integration into existing workflows. The platform also supports authentication, access control, and role-based usage, ensuring suitability for both open-access and controlled environments.

Within the INSIGHT project, Jaqpot serves as a central infrastructure component for hosting and operationalising computational models. All models deployed on the platform can be semantically linked to the broader INSIGHT knowledge base, enabling them to be easily discovered, combined, and reused within interoperable SSbD workflows. To facilitate project-specific development and management, a dedicated INSIGHT organisation has been established within Jaqpot, which hosts the models developed or integrated into the platform as part of the INSIGHT project (Figure 44).

INSIGHT

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Description People Shared Edit

INSIGHT is a project funded by Horizon Europe (GA101137742). The Project aims to:

- Develop an integrated framework for mechanistic impact assessment based on the novel concept of IOP;
- Provide curated and user-friendly FAIR data and computational models and workflows that support the development of the next generation SSGO chemicals and materials;
- Provide open, accessible and interactive guidelines, enabling end users and stakeholders to access and operate the framework.

For more information visit <https://insight-project.org/>

Title	Model Description
Cell viability in graphene-related materials	QSAR-ML model for the prediction of cell viability (%) in graphene-related materials
Aquatic toxicity in fish species	This model predicts the aquatic toxicity (LC50) in fish species for small organic molecules
QSAR toolbox Calculator integration	This service provides access to the calculators included in the QSAR toolbox
QSAR Toolbox Model integration	This service provides access to the QSAR models included in the QSAR toolbox
QSAR Toolbox Profiler integration	This service provides access to the profilers included in the QSAR toolbox
Extended PFOA male rat PBK - NTUA (2024)	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFOA in rats after oral exposure or IV injection
PFOA rat - Worley and Fisher (2015)	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFOA in rats after oral exposure or IV injection
PFASs Human PBPK - Fabrega et al. (2025)	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFBS, PFHxS, PFOS, PFDS, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA or PFTeDA in humans after oral exposure
PFASs Protein-Binding Fish PBK - Ng et al. (2013)	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFOS, PFOA, PFDA, PFUnA, PFDaA or PFHxS in fish after waterborne exposure
PFOS/PFOA Human PBPK (Oral exposure) - Fabrega et al. (2016)	This is a PBPK model that predicts the accumulation of PFOS or PFOA in humans after oral exposure
PFOS Rainbow trout PBTK - Vidal et al. (2020)	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFOS in R. trout after oral or waterborne exposure
PFOS/PFOA Human PBK - Loccisano et al. (2011)	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFOS or PFOA in humans after oral exposure or IV injection
PFOA rat PBK - Loccisano et al. (2012)	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFOA in rats after oral exposure or IV injection
PFOS rat PBK - Loccisano et al. (2012)	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFOS in rats after oral exposure or IV injection
PFHxS rat PBK - Kim et al. (2018)	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFHxS in rats after oral exposure or IV injection
PFNA rat PBK - Kim et al. (2019)	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFNA in rats after oral exposure or IV injection
PFDA rat PBK - Kim et al. (2019)	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFDA in rats after oral exposure or IV injection
PFAS PBK Zebrafish - Golosovskala et al. (2024)	This is a PBK model that predicts the biodistribution of PFOA, PFHpA, PFNA, PFHxS, or PFBS in zebrafish through waterborne exposure
PFOA PBK Humans - Worley et al. (2017)	PBK model for describing the biodistribution of PFOA in humans after intravenous or oral administration
Toluene di-isocyanate (TDI) PBK for humans - Scholten et al. (2023)	This PBK model simulates the biodistribution and urinary excretion of toluene diisocyanate (TDI) and its metabolites (TDA) in humans following occupational exposure via inhalation and dermal routes
Acetone PBK for humans - Mork and Johanson (2006)	This PBK model describes the uptake, distribution, metabolism, and excretion of acetone in humans, with a particular focus on inhalation exposure
Ethylene Glycol PBK for humans - Corley et al. (2005)	This PBK model describes the absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion of ethylene glycol (EG) and its primary metabolite glycolic acid (GA) in humans, with a particular focus on inhalation exposure scenarios
PFOS PBK for humans -Chou and Lin (2019)	This model reproduces the PBK model of Chou and Lin (2019) for describing the biodistribution of PFOS in humans
PFAS toxicokinetics model-Chiu et al. (2022)	Toxicokinetics model for describing the serum concentration-time of PFOA, PFOS, PFNA or PFHxS in humans after ingestion
PFBS Human PBK -NTUA (2025)	This PBK model predicts the biodistribution of PFBS in humans after oral exposure

Figure 44: The INSIGHT organisation in Jaqpot and list of the publicly available models developed or integrated

The following sections of this deliverable provide detailed descriptions of the functionality, content, and technical characteristics of each model. The emphasis is placed on describing the models and their availability through the GUI. However, as mentioned earlier, all models can also be accessed via the Jaqpot APIs, enabling their integration into computational pipelines and, ultimately, into the INSIGHT knowledge graph. Section 3.7.13 addresses this explicitly, providing examples of how to use Jaqpot models through the APIs.

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3.7.1. Jqpot Infrastructure: QSAR-ML model for the prediction of cell viability (%) in graphene-related materials

Graphene-related materials (GRM) are carbon-based NMs that can be oxidized, reduced or functionalized. While their mechanical and electrical properties have shown promising results in many applications such as biomedicine or energy storage, they also pose potential risks for human health in exposed populations. This creates a need to create models that model the correlation between GRM exposure and health. For this reason, we employed a data and modelling approach (Romeo et al., 2022) proposed in the literature to predict the cell viability percentage after exposure to graphene-based materials. In that study, In vitro cytotoxicity data were obtained from experimental studies using lung cells. For each experiment, dose-response curves were fitted using a quadratic model of the form $ax^2 + bx + c$. Subsequently, 10 equally spaced doses ranging from 10 to 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ were used to calculate the corresponding cell viability percentage. The resulting dataset consists of 519 instances and its features are the type-substance of the material (graphene, graphene oxide, reduced graphene oxide), functionalization, size of the GRM, number of layers, exposure time, the media used in the cytotoxicity test, the type of assay, cell type (epithelial, macrophage), cell species and the dose.

Initially, the categorical features were one-hot encoded, and the continuous ones were scaled to be in the range of 0-1. Then the dataset was split randomly into a train and testing set with an 0.80:0.20 ratio. According to the original publication, Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) stood out as the best predictive model in cross-validation, thus it is chosen as the predictive algorithm for cell viability. The model was grid-searched in order to find the optimal parameters while also performing 10-fold cross validation. Upon training, the best model achieved an $R_{train}^2 = 0.84$ and a $Q^2(cv) = 0.78$. In the unseen test set, the model reached $R_{test}^2 = 0.81$, indicating good generalizability and predictive performance. Upon training, SHAP values were once again computed on the test set data points to inspect the features that influence prediction the most. As seen in Figure 45, the feature Substance_rGO which corresponds to the reduced Graphene Oxide material, contributes the highest into the model's prediction along with other categorical features like assay or media and the numerical feature dose.

Figure 45: Mean Shapley Values for the best features of the graphene model

The detailed inputs and outputs from the model are shown in Tables 58 and 59.

Table 58: Inputs to the model predicting cell viability (%) in graphene-related materials.

Name	Units	Description
Substance	Graphene, Graphene Oxide, Reduced Graphene Oxide	GRM type (Categorical)
Size	S, M, L	Size of GRM (Categorical) (Lateral size of the GRM: S (<500nm), M (500<size<1000nm), L (>=1000nm))
Layer	1-6	The number of layers of the GRM (Integer)
Time	hr	Exposure time
Functionalization	No functionalisation, poly-acrylamide, NH ₂ , PEG, COOH, poly acrylic acid, Amin	Functionalization of the GRM (Categorical)
Cell_type_general	Epithelial, macrophage	Type of cell (Categorical)
Species	Human, Rodent	Species (Categorical)
Assay	ldh, mtt, pi, cck, ez_cyto, nucleo, wst	Type of assay (Categorical)
Media	RPMI + 10% FBS, DMEM + F12 + 10% FBS, DMEM + 10% FBS, F12 + 10% FBS, DMEM	The media used in the cytotoxicity test, indicating the main media (e.g. RPMI, DMEM) and the percentage of fetal bovine serum (FBS)

	+ F12	(Categorical)
Dose	10 - 100 (µg/ml)	GMB Concentration (Integer)

Table 59: Outputs from the model predicting cell viability (%) in graphene-related materials.

Name	Units	Description
Lung Cell Viability	%	Lung Cell Viability

The model was deployed as a Jaqpot service, with three different APD approaches, which are the Leverage approach, the Mean Variance method, and the Bounding Box, along with majority voting for all of them to assess the reliability of the predictions. The model can be accessed at <https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/1881/description>.

3.7.2. Jaqpot Infrastructure: Machine Learning Models for Aquatic Toxicity Prediction

To assess the toxic effects of chemicals on animals generally, extensive in vivo testing is typically required. Regarding ecotoxicity in aquatic environments, these tests often involve experiments on fish or crustacean species. However, those tests are costly and rely on animal testing. To address these issues, ML can be applied to predict the ecotoxicological effects and identify potentially harmful chemicals. By accumulating chemical data over the years with measured toxicity values, datasets can be introduced to model structure-property relationships, where a property can be defined as a concentration related to ecotoxicity (e.g., Lethal Concentration 50 LC50, Effective Concentration 50 EC50). Such predictive models can serve as alternatives to conventional testing, reducing both time, cost, and ethical concerns associated with animal experiments while also accelerating the evaluation of chemical safety. For that reason, two models were created to predict the ecotoxicology in fish and crustacean species.

Before developing accurate and reliable ML models, curated datasets must be created that capture the desired chemical space. In this attempt, we utilized the recently developed Adore Dataset⁵ to predict toxicity concentrations in fish and crustacean species. For fish, toxicity is determined by the LC50, which is the concentration of a substance in water that is expected to kill 50% of a test animal population when administered as a single exposure. This effect is measured experimentally according to the OECD test No. 203, in which toxicity values are recorded over 24, 48, 72, or 96 hours of

⁵ https://gitlab.renkulab.io/mltox/adore/-/tree/master/data/processed?ref_type=heads

exposure to the test substance. For crustaceans, the EC50 is used to describe the concentration that induces a 50% effect level, compared to a negative and/or positive control treatment. According to the OECD test No. 202 used for that matter, EC50 values are calculated based on the immobilization effect.

Both datasets contain SMILES representations and endpoint information along with experimental features, including exposure time (24h, 48h, 72h, 96h), Concentration type (Active Ingredient, Formulation, Total), Exposure type (Static, Flow Through, Renewal, Not Reported), and Media Type (Fresh water, Salt Water) and the corresponding endpoint in mg/L and on logarithmic scale (logLC50, logEC50). In some chemicals, Exposure Type was not reported, and thus those datapoints were discarded from the dataset. Furthermore, there are several entries in which SMILES and experimental features are identical but differ in the toxicity values. In such cases, the median toxicity value was used to represent the final endpoint.

The modelling procedure was the same for both the LC50 and the EC50 datasets. First, the experimental categorical features (exposure time, concentration type, exposure type, media type) were one-hot encoded. To incorporate information about the chemical structure, molecular descriptors and fingerprints were generated as additional features for the models. Specifically, these were calculated using the RDKit cheminformatics package, which provides more than 200 features with structural-derived descriptors (LogP, MW). Descriptors that contained NaN values or could not be calculated were automatically removed from the feature pool.

In the dataset, a given Chemical may have multiple entries with different features and endpoint values. To prevent the same chemical from appearing in both the training and test sets, the data were split based on unique SMILES. This approach ensures that the model cannot overfit by memorizing chemicals it has already seen during training.

To avoid the use of redundant computational descriptors, feature selection was applied to reduce the feature pool. The feature selection process was performed on the training dataset and then applied to the test set. Initially, features with a variance lower than 0.001 were discarded. Additionally, highly correlated features were removed based on the Pearson correlation coefficient, using a threshold of 0.85. After this process, the final number of features (including the one-hot encoded experimental features) was 155 for the LC50 dataset and 144 for the EC50 dataset.

XGBoost is chosen as the model to predict the toxicity values for fish and crustacean species. XGBoost is a powerful and efficient ML algorithm based on gradient boosting that builds an ensemble of decision trees to optimize predictive performance, and is particularly well-suited for structured data. Grid

search was implemented with cross-validation to choose the best-performing parameter values of *n_estimators*, *max_depth*, *learning_rate*, *subsample*, *colsample_bytree*, *min_child_weight*, *gamma*, *reg_alpha*, and *reg_lambda*. Cross-validation was also based on SMILES occurrence, similar to the split of training and testing sets. In Figure 46, we observe the goodness of fit of the LC50 fish model, where R2 on the test set is calculated at 0.616. In Figure 47, the EC50 crustaceans model's predictions are seen with an R2 of 0.739. These results indicate a moderate to strong predictive ability, especially for the crustacean dataset. The higher R² of the EC50 model may reflect lower variability or more consistent experimental conditions in the underlying data.

Figure 46: True vs Predicted values of log(LC50) model.

Figure 47: True vs Predicted values of log(EC50) model.

Upon training, we computed the mean SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values to identify the most important features contributing to the predictions. SHAP values quantify the impact of each feature on the model's output, allowing a transparent interpretation of how individual features influence toxicity estimates. For both models, Molecular LogP (octanol–water partition coefficient) was found to be the top contributing feature, as shown in Figures 46 and 47. This suggests that hydrophobicity plays a major role in determining chemical toxicity toward both fish and crustaceans, which is consistent with the known tendency of hydrophobic compounds to bioaccumulate in organisms. Other important features include molecular weight and several more computational descriptors.

Figure 48: Mean Shap Values for the best features of the LC50 model

Figure 49: Mean Shap Values for the best features of the EC50 model

The detailed inputs and outputs from the models are shown in Tables 60 and 61.

Table 60: Inputs to the LC50, LD50 models for fish species.

Name	Units	Description
SMILES		Generation of RDKit descriptors

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Concentration	Active ingredient, Formulation, Total	Concentration Type (Categorical)
Experimental Duration	24,48,72,96 hrs	Experimental Duration (Categorical)
Exposure Type	Static, Flowthrough, Renewal	Exposure Type (Categorical)
Media Type	Fresh water, Salt Water	Media Type (Categorical)

Table 61: Outputs from the LC50, EC50 models for fish species.

Name	Units	Description
LC50, EC50	mg/l	log (LC50), log (EC50)

Model Implementation

Both models are uploaded to the Jaqpot Platform under the INSIGHT organisation, along with the APD being the Leverage and Bounding Box functions. The URLs of the models are in

<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2188/description>,

<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2190/description>.

On the landing model page, both models are provided with a brief description of their endpoint, the dataset used, and modelling methodology as seen in Figure 50.

LC50 Prediction for Fish Species

giannis savvas @john_savvas 2 months ago SKLEARN_ONNX

Description Features Predict Metrics Edit Discussion

Endpoint and Dataset

This model predicts the Lethal Concentration 50 (LC50) for fish species. **LC50** refers to the concentration of a substance in air or water that is expected to kill 50% of a test animal population when administered as a single exposure. The endpoint is described in **mg/L** and on a logarithmic scale (log(LC50)). We utilize the benchmark dataset in ecotoxicology **ADORE**, which provides experimental data on acute aquatic toxicity based on the **OECD Test 203**.

Modelling Details

- The features of the model comprise **RDKit** Descriptors and **experimental** data (exposure_type, media_type, observed_duration, concentration_type) that were one-hot encoded. Any chemical with a non-reported exposure type was discarded. Also, Descriptors with NaN values were automatically removed.
- For chemicals with the same experimental conditions, SMILES and descriptors that had varied target values, we considered the median value.
- The dataset was split into training and testing based on the **occurrence** of chemicals. This means that a chemical cannot occur at both sets to avoid overfitting. The training dataset consists of 5094 chemicals, and the test dataset consists of 1028.
- To avoid redundant features, we removed correlated features based on a **Pearson's** coefficient of 0.85. Additionally, the **Variance Threshold** is used with a 0.001 value to retain representative features. The feature selection was based on the training set and applied to the test set. The final features remaining are 155.
- We trained an **XGBoost** Model with an extensive hyperparameter search and cross-validation based on the split occurrence of the training set.
- For the Domain Of Applicability, **Leverage**, **Bounding Box**, and majority voting are used to detect outliers.

EC50 Prediction on Crustacean Species

giannis savvas @john_savvas 2 months ago SKLEARN_ONNX

Description Features Predict Metrics Edit Discussion

Endpoint and Dataset

This model predicts the Effective Concentration 50 (EC50) for crustacean species. **EC50** describes the induction of a 50% effect level, compared to a negative and/or positive control treatment. The endpoint is described in **mg/L** and on a logarithmic scale (log(eC50)). We utilize the benchmark dataset in ecotoxicology **ADORE**, which provides experimental and taxonomic data on acute aquatic toxicity.

Modelling Details

- The features of the model comprise **RDKit** Descriptors and **experimental** data (exposure_type, media_type, observed_duration, concentration_type) that were one-hot encoded. Any chemical with a non-reported exposure type was discarded. Also, Descriptors with NaN values were automatically removed.
- For chemicals with the same experimental conditions, SMILES and descriptors that had varied target values, we considered the median value.
- The dataset was split into training and testing based on the **occurrence** of chemicals. This means that a chemical cannot occur at both sets to avoid overfitting. The training dataset consists of 1466 chemicals, and the test dataset consists of 309.
- To avoid redundant features, we removed correlated features based on a **Pearson's** coefficient of 0.85. Additionally, the **Variance Threshold** is used with a 0.001 value to retain representative features. The feature selection was based on the training set and applied to the test set. The final features remaining are 144.
- We trained an **XGBoost** Model with an extensive hyperparameter search and cross-validation based on the split occurrence of the training set.
- For the Domain Of Applicability, **Leverage**, **Bounding Box**, and majority voting are used to detect outliers.

Figure 50: Description page of the developed jaqpot models for LC50 (left) and EC50(right).

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Additionally, in the Feature Page presented in Figure 51, the independent features used to make predictions are listed, along with the dependent feature that corresponds to the toxicity endpoint, each feature accompanied by a brief summary.

Independent Features				
Name	Units	Range	Description	Type
SMILES	-		A valid SMILES...	SMILES
Concentration Type	-			CATEGORICAL
Experimental Duration	Hours			CATEGORICAL
Exposure Type			The method ...	CATEGORICAL
Media Type	-		The liquid, in which...	CATEGORICAL

Dependent Features				
Name	Units	Description	Type	Actions
log(LC50)	mg/L		FLOAT	👁️ ✎️

Independent Features				
Name	Units	Range	Description	Type
SMILES	-		A valid SMILES...	SMILES
Concentration Type	-			CATEGORICAL
Experimental Duration	Hours			CATEGORICAL
Exposure Type			The method ...	CATEGORICAL
Media Type	-		The liquid, in which...	CATEGORICAL

Dependent Features				
Name	Units	Description	Type	Actions
log(EC50)	mg/L		FLOAT	👁️ ✎️

Figure 51: Feature page of the Jaqpot models for LC50 (left) and EC50 (right).

Finally, to make predictions online, one can navigate in the Predict Page. By entering the necessary features that the model requires, such as a valid SMILES string and external descriptors, a prediction can be obtained. The predictions are also accompanied by the APD to access if the chemical is covered in the trained chemical space. An example of predicting a chemical's LC50 and EC50 are shown in Figures 52,53, respectively.

[Description](#)
[Features](#)
[Predict](#)
[Metrics](#)
[Edit](#)
[Discussion](#)

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form
 or
 Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

SMILES:

Concentration Type*:

Experimental Duration*:

Exposure Type*:

Media Type*:

[Submit](#)

[Result](#)

ID 27082 [Success](#)

[1 minute ago](#)
[less than 5 seconds](#)

[Export CSV](#)

Total 1 result Rows per page: 25

SMILES	Concentration Type	Experimental Duration	Exposure Type	Media Type	log(LC50)	Applicability Domain
CCCC	Active Ingedient	24 hours	Static	Fresh Water	2.4389824867248535	In Domain

Figure 52: Predict page of Jaqpot LC50 model

[Description](#)
[Features](#)
[Predict](#)
[Metrics](#)
[Edit](#)
[Discussion](#)

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form
 or
 Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

SMILES:

Concentration Type*:

Experimental Duration*:

Exposure Type*:

Media Type*:

[Submit](#)

[Result](#)

ID 27084 [Success](#)

[less than a minute ago](#)
[less than 5 seconds](#)

[Export CSV](#)

Total 1 result Rows per page: 25

SMILES	Concentration Type	Experimental Duration	Exposure Type	Media Type	log(EC50)	Applicability Domain
CCCC	Active Ingedient	24	Static	Fresh Water	2.2529025077819824	Out of Domain

Figure 53: Predict page of Jaqpot EC50 model

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3.7.3. Jaqpot Infrastructure: PFOS PBK (Chou & Lin, 2019)

The present model is an implementation of the Physiologically Based Kinetic (PBK) model presented in the publication by Chou & Lin (2019) entitled “Bayesian evaluation of a physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model for perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) to characterize the interspecies uncertainty between mice, rats, monkeys, and humans: Development and performance verification”.

This PBK model simulates the biodistribution of perfluorooctane sulfonic acid (PFOS) in humans following oral ingestion. The structural model is based on the model of Worley et al. (2017) and is presented in Figure 54. The oral dose is inserted in the stomach compartment. Part of the dose is absorbed in the blood stream, while the remaining dose is emptied to the small intestine. From there, a fraction of the dose is absorbed and the unabsorbed dose is excreted to feces. The serum compartment connects the liver, kidneys and rest-of-the-body compartments. A detailed representation of the tubular reabsorption through transporters in the proximal tubule cells is employed for accurately describing the renal clearance of PFOS. Apart from filtration, the chemical can also be excreted from the liver to feces through the bile .

The model considers constant input intervals through an ingestion input vector that encodes both drinking-water sources and non drinking-water sources (Table 62). Specifically, ‘ingestion’ is used to encode the daily rate of PFOS ingestion, and ‘ingestion_time’ represents the corresponding time points where this ingestion rate changes.

Model outputs include the predicted mass and concentration of PFOS across all compartments, as well as the cumulative mass in urine and feces (Table 63). A full description of the model structure and parameterization is available in Chou & Lin. (2019). Figure 55 presents an input example through the model’s UI in the Jaqpot Platform.

The model is exposed as a ready to use web application on the Jaqpot platform (<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2126/description>). The R implementation of the model is available in a public GitHub repository (https://github.com/ntua-unit-of-control-and-informatics/PFAS_PBK_models) that hosts several published PBK models for different compounds and organisms.

Figure 54. Schematic representation of the PFOS PBK model (Figure from Chou & Lin, 2019).

Table 62: PFOS PBK model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
BW	kg	Total body weight of simulated individual
ingestion	ug/day	Daily ingestion rate of PFOA from non-drinking sources
ingestion_time	days	Days at which ingestion rate changes
sim.start	h	Initial time point of simulation
sim.end	h	Final time point of simulation
sim.step	h	The integration step of simulation

Table 63: PFOS PBK model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
AR	ug	Mass of PFOA in rest-of-the-body
Adif	ug	Mass of PFOS translocating through diffusion in the kidneys
A_baso	ug	Mass of PFOS translocating through active basolateral transporters in the kidneys
Akb	ug	Mass of PFOS in kidney blood
ACI	ug	Mass of PFOS cleared via glomerular filtration
Aefflux	ug	Mass of PFOS translocating from PTCs to blood

A_apical	ug	Mass of PFOS translocating through active apical transporters in the kidneys
APTC	ug	Mass of PFOS in proximal tubule cells
Afil	ug	Mass of PFOS in filtrate
Aurine	ug	Cumulative mass of PFOS in urine
AST	ug	Mass of PFOS in the stomach
AabsST	ug	Mass of PFOS absorbed through the stomach
ASI	ug	Mass of PFOS in the small intestine
AabsSI	ug	Mass of PFOS absorbed through the small intestine
Afeces	ug	Cumulative mass of PFOS in feces
AL	ug	Mass of PFOS in liver
Abile	ug	Mass of PFOS in bile
Aplas_free	ug	Mass of free PFOS in plasma
CR	ug/L	Concentration of PFOS in rest-of-the-body
CVR	ug/L	Concentration of PFOS in venous blood leaving the rest-of-the-body
CKb	ug/L	Concentration of PFOS in kidneys blood
CVK	ug/L	Concentration of PFOS in venous blood leaving the kidneys
CPTC	ug/L	Concentration of PFOS in proximal tubule cells
Cfill	ug/L	Concentration of PFOS in filtrate
CL	ug/L	Concentration of PFOS in liver
CVL	ug/L	Concentration of PFOS in venous blood leaving the liver
CA_free	ug/L	Concentration of free PFOS in plasma
CA	ug/L	Concentration of PFOS in plasma
time	days	Simulation time vector

PFOS Human PBK - Chou & Lin (2019)

 Periklis Tsiros
 @periklists 6 months ago R_PBPk

Description Features **Predict** Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form or Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

BW *	ingestion *	ingestion_time *	sim.start *
70	10	0	0
sim.end *	sim.step *		
365	1		

Submit

Figure 55. Prediction tab of the PFOS PBK model.

3.7.4. Jaqpot Infrastructure: PFOA PBK (Worley et al., 2017)

The present model is an implementation of the Physiologically Based Kinetic (PBK) model presented in the publication by Worley et al. (2017) entitled “Physiologically based pharmacokinetic modeling of human exposure to perfluorooctanoic acid suggests historical non drinking-water exposures are important for predicting current serum concentrations”.

This PBK model simulates the biodistribution of perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) in humans following oral ingestion. The intake is distinguished between drinking water and non drinking-water sources. The structural model is presented in Figure 56. The oral dose is inserted in the stomach compartment. Part of the dose is absorbed in the blood stream, while the remaining dose is emptied to the small intestine. From there, a fraction of the dose is absorbed and the unabsorbed dose is excreted to feces. The serum compartment connects the liver, kidneys and rest-of-the-body compartments. A detailed representation of the tubular reabsorption through transporters in the proximal tubule cells is employed for accurately describing the renal clearance of PFOA. Apart from filtration, the chemical can also be excreted from the liver to feces through the bile .

The model considers constant input intervals through dedicated input vectors that distinguish drinking-water sources from non drinking-water sources (Table 64). Specifically, ‘C_water’ is used to encode the concentration of PFOA in drinking water, and ‘C_water_time’ represents the corresponding time points where the concentration in the water changes. The daily water consumption is set to 2 L/day. Oral ingestion sources that are not associated to water are represented by the ‘ingestion’ and ‘ingestion_time’ vectors. Finally, the model supports intravenous (IV) administration of PFOA through ‘admin_dose_iv’ and ‘admin_time_iv’

Model outputs include the predicted mass and concentration of PFOA across all compartments, as well as the cumulative mass in urine and feces (Table 65). A full description of the model structure and

parameterization is available in Worley et al. (2017). Figure 57 presents an input example through the model's UI in the Jaqpot Platform.

The model is exposed as a ready to use web application on the Jaqpot platform (<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/1984/description>). The R implementation of the model is available in a public GitHub repository (https://github.com/ntua-unit-of-control-and-informatics/PFAS_PBK_models) that hosts several published PBK models for different compounds and organisms.

Figure 56. Schematic representation of the PFOA PBK model (Figure from Worley et al., 2017).

Table 64: PFOA PBK model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
BW	kg	Total body weight of simulated individual

admin_type	-	Type of administration. Supports oral and IV
admin_dose_iv	ug	Administered dose via IV
admin_time_iv	days	Time points when IV administration occurred
C_water	ug/L	Concentration of PFOA in drinking water
C_water_time	days	Days at which water concentration changes
ingestion	ug/day	Daily ingestion rate of PFOA from non-drinking sources
ingestion_time	days	Days at which ingestion rate changes
sim.start	h	Initial time point of simulation
sim.end	h	Final time point of simulation
sim.step	h	The integration step of simulation

Table 65: PFOA PBK model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
AR	ug	Mass of PFOA in rest-of-the-body
Adif	ug	Mass of PFOA translocating though diffusion in the kidneys
A_baso	ug	Mass of PFOA translocating through active basolateral transporters in the kidneys
Akb	ug	Mass of PFOA in kidney blood
ACI	ug	Mass of PFOA cleared via glomerular filtration
Aefflux	ug	Mass of PFOA translocating from PTCs to blood
A_apical	ug	Mass of PFOA translocating through active apical transporters in the kidneys
APTC	ug	Mass of PFOA in proximal tubule cells
Afil	ug	Mass of PFOA in filtrate
Aurine	ug	Cumulative mass of PFOA in urine
AST	ug	Mass of PFOA in the stomach
AabsST	ug	Mass of PFOA absorbed through the stomach
ASI	ug	Mass of PFOA in the small intestine
AabsSI	ug	Mass of PFOA absorbed through the small intestine
Afeces	ug	Cumulative mass of PFOA in feces
AL	ug	Mass of PFOA in liver
Abile	ug	Mass of PFOA in bile

Aplas_free	ug	Mass of free PFOA in plasma
CR	ug/L	Concentration of PFOA in rest-of-the-body
CVR	ug/L	Concentration of PFOA in venous blood leaving the rest-of-the-body
CKb	ug/L	Concentration of PFOA in kidneys blood
CVK	ug/L	Concentration of PFOA in venous blood leaving the kidneys
CPTC	ug/L	Concentration of PFOA in proximal tubule cells
Cfill	ug/L	Concentration of PFOA in filtrate
CL	ug/L	Concentration of PFOA in liver
CVL	ug/L	Concentration of PFOA in venous blood leaving the liver
CA_free	ug/L	Concentration of free PFOA in plasma
CA	ug/L	Concentration of PFOA in plasma
time	days	Simulation time vector

PFOA PBK Humans - Worley et al. (2017)

Periklis Tsiros @periklists 11 months ago R_PBPk

Description Features **Predict** Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form or Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

Figure 57. Prediction tab of the PFOA PBK model.

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3.7.5. Jaqpot Infrastructure: PFOA/PFOS/PFHxS/PFNA I-compartment toxicokinetic model (Chiu et al., 2022)

The present model is an implementation of the I-compartment toxicokinetic model presented in the publication by Chiu et al. (2022) entitled “Bayesian Estimation of Human Population Toxicokinetics of PFOA, PFOS, PFHxS, and PFNA from Studies of Contaminated Drinking Water”.

This model simulates the serum concentrations of PFOA, PFOS, perfluorohexane sulfonic acid (PFHxS), and perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA) and in humans following oral ingestion. The intake is distinguished between drinking water and non drinking-water sources. The structural model is presented in Figure 58. The model used two parameters for each congener, the clearance rate and the volume of distribution.

Simulations are performed for a selected congener among the four available ones, and end-users can select the chemical of interest through the “Substance” variable. The model considers constant input intervals through dedicated input vectors that distinguish drinking-water sources from non drinking-water sources (Table 66). Specifically, ‘C_water’ is used to encode the concentration of the chemical in drinking water, and ‘C_water_timeS’ represents the corresponding time points where the concentration in the water changes. The daily water consumption is defined through ‘DW_rate’. Oral ingestion sources that are not associated with drinking water are represented by the ‘non_DW_intake’ and ‘ingestion_times’ vectors. Finally, the initial serum level of each simulation is defined through ‘Cserum_init’.

Model outputs include the predicted serum concentration of the selected congener (Table 67). A full description of the model structure and parameterization is available in Chiu et al. (2022). Figure 59 presents an input example through the model’s UI in the Jaqpot Platform.

The model is exposed as a ready to use web application on the Jaqpot platform (<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/1985/description>). The R implementation of the model is available in a public GitHub repository (https://github.com/ntua-unit-of-control-and-informatics/PFAS_PBK_models) that hosts several published PBK models for different compounds and organisms.

Figure 58. Schematic representation of the I-compartment toxicokinetic model presented in Chiu et al. (2022).

PFAS toxicokinetics model -Chiu et al. (2022)

Creator: Periklis Tsiros (@periklists) 11 months ago R_PBPk

Description Features Predict Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method: Fill out the form Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

substance* PFNA BW* 70 DW_rate* 2 Cwater* 1

Cwater_times* 0 non_DW_intake* 2 ingestion_times* 0 Cserum_init* 1

sim.start* 0 sim.end* 100 sim.step* 1

Figure 59. Prediction tab of the I-compartment toxicokinetic model.

Table 66: PFOA/PFOS/PFHxS/PFNA I-compartment toxicokinetic model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
BW	kg	Total body weight of simulated individual
Substance	-	PFAS congener (PFOA/PFOS/PFHxS/PFNA)
Cserum_init	ug/L	Initial concentration in serum
DW_rate	L/day	Drinking water rate
C_water	ug/L	Concentration of PFOA in drinking water
Cwater_times	days	Days at which water concentration changes
non_DW_intake	ug/day	Daily ingestion rate of PFOA from non-drinking sources
ingestion_times	days	Days at which ingestion rate changes
sim.start	h	Initial time point of simulation
sim.end	h	Final time point of simulation
sim.step	h	The integration step of simulation

Table 67: PFOA/PFOS/PFHxS/PFNA I-compartment toxicokinetic model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Cserum	ug/L	Concentration of the selected PFAS congener in serum
time	days	Simulation time vector

3.7.6. Jaqpot Infrastructure: PFOA/PFOS PBK consensus model

The consensus PBK model integrates the predictions of several individual toxicokinetics models to describe the disposition of PFOA and PFOS in the serum and liver, which comprise major PFAS accumulation sites Perez et al., (2013); Nielsen et al., (2023). Several literature models are available for describing the biodistribution of PFOA and PFOS, including mechanistic multi-organ PBK models and simple one-compartment toxicokinetic models that focus on predicting serum concentration. Instead of validating each of the models and selecting a single model per chemical, a consensus modelling framework was implemented using Bayesian model averaging (BMA), allowing us to address structural variability among models and data variability, leading to more reliable predictions (Figure 60).

Figure 60. Schematic representation of the BMA framework.

In the BMA approach followed, all available models were first reproduced using either the code provided in the original publications or by implementing the reported equations. For each chemical, four models with variable structural complexity and compartmental representation were integrated within the BMA framework. Two PBPK models described by Loccisano et al. (2011) and Fàbrega et al. (2014) that include compartments for plasma, gut, liver, fat, skin, kidney, and a rest-of-the-body, were incorporated into the BMA framework and used to simulate both PFOA and PFOS. A third PBPK model, developed by Worley et al. (2017), consisting of serum, stomach, small intestine, liver, kidney, and rest-of-the-body compartments, was used specifically for PFOA. A fourth PBPK model, developed by Chou & Lin. (2019), consisting of the same compartments, was used for simulating PFOS. In addition to these PBK models, a simpler, one-compartment toxicokinetic model representing serum was used for both PFOA and PFOS (Chiu et al., 2022). The PBK models were used to predict both the liver and

serum concentrations, while the one-compartment model was applied only to serum concentration predictions.

The reproduced models were used to simulate serum and liver concentrations of PFOA and PFOS under conditions consistent with the identified literature biodistribution data. Both the model predictions and the corresponding experimental observations were then incorporated into the BMA framework. For the serum models, the studies of Olsen et al. (2007), Haug et al. (2009) and Abraham et al. (2024) were incorporated. For the liver BMA models, serum-liver pairs were reported in the literature: Olsen et al. (2003); Maestri et al., (2006); Baumert et al., (2003); Nielsen et al., (2023). The serum BMA models for PFOA and PFOS served as the best available serum predictors, and through reverse dosimetry, were used to estimate the external exposure level required to reach a steady-state serum concentration equal to that reported in the serum-liver pair. The derived external exposure was then applied to the PBK models via forward dosimetry to estimate the corresponding liver concentration. The generated prediction-observation pairs for each compartment and each organ constituted the training dataset for developing the BMA models. For each BMA model, the average prediction of compartment k of study i , denoted by \hat{y}_{ik} , was acquired by multiplying the predictions of model j , P_{kj} , by the corresponding model weight, w_j , through the following equation:

$$\hat{y}_{ik} = \sum_j (w_j * P_{kj})$$

where $j = 1, \dots, 3$ for liver and $j = 1, \dots, 4$ for serum. A proportional error model was used to encode the observed variability in the concentration data:

$$\log(y_{ik}) = \text{Normal}(\log(\hat{y}_{ik}), \sigma/\sqrt{N_i})$$

where N_i is the sample size of study i . This formulation scales the residual variability according to the degree of data aggregation, assigning smaller variance to study means that were based on larger sample sizes and larger variance to individual-level observations. An informative truncated normal prior, restricted to positive values, was assigned to the residual variance, to steer the posterior towards lower values. For the model weight vector, an auxiliary variable vector, denoted by θ , was introduced and assigned an uninformative prior. The auxiliary variable was transformed into the model weight vector using softmax transformation, ensuring that for each compartment, the weights are positive and sum to unity.

$$\sigma \sim \text{truncated Normal}(0, 0.1)$$

$$\theta_i \sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)$$

$$w_i = \exp(\theta_i) / \sum_i (\exp(\theta_i))$$

The posterior weights and residual variance were employed to integrate individual model predictions, thereby producing consensus dose metrics that balance contributions across structurally distinct models. The posterior distributions of the weights assigned to the individual model predictions, together with the corresponding residual standard deviations are shown in Figure 61. The results indicate that no single model dominated across cases. Instead, the BMA procedure combined contributions from different models depending on the compound and the biological matrix. In the case of PFOA serum data, the BMA model assigned weights relatively evenly across the available models, while for PFOS serum data, the models of Chiu et al. (2022) and Chou & Lin (2019) contributed most strongly to the overall predictions. For the liver data, the predictions were primarily driven by a single model, namely Chou & Lin (2019) for PFOS and Worley et al. (2017) for PFOA.

Figure 61. Violin plots illustrating the posterior distributions of the model weights and the residual standard deviation for the four BMA models corresponding to PFOA and PFOS concentrations in serum and liver. Model weights ‘weight_Loccisano’, ‘weight_Fabrega’, ‘weight_Worley’, ‘weight_Chou’ and ‘weight_Chui’ correspond to the publication models presented in Loccisano et al. (2011), Fabrega et al. (2015), Worley et al. (2017), Chou & Lin (2019) and Chui et al. (2022), respectively.

For the serum data, all individual models demonstrated good predictive performance, with predictions lying mostly within the two-fold error range (Figure 62). All models showed a tendency to underpredict, as indicated by the left-skewed tails in the violin plots. The BMA predictions, which integrate the predictions of the individual models, showed excellent agreement with the observed data. The 95% posterior credible interval of the BMA models was relatively narrow and closely encompassed the observed data, with the 2.5th and 97.5th percentile fold errors lying near the two-fold boundaries and the median centred around zero bias. This indicates that the BMA model produced consistent predictions while maintaining compact uncertainty bounds for both PFOA and PFOS. The performance of individual models presented in Figure 62 can be directly related to the posterior weight distributions in Figure 61, which provide an explanation for their relative contributions.

Figure 62. Violin plots of model prediction fold error, expressed as the \log_{10} ratio of predicted to observed concentrations, for PFOA and PFOS serum data from Olsen et al. (2007), Haug et al. (2009), and Abraham et al. (2024). The solid vertical line denotes zero fold error, and the dashed lines indicate the twofold error limits. Each shaded area represents the distribution of prediction fold error from individual models (Loccisano, Fabrega, Worley, Chou, and Chiu, corresponding to the models presented in Loccisano et al. (2011), Fabrega et al. (2015), Worley et al. (2017), Chou & Lin (2019), and Chiu et al. (2022), respectively) or from the BMA model. For the BMA model, the median and 95% posterior credible interval are represented by the 50th, 2.5th, and 97.5th percentiles of the posterior distribution.

For predicting the liver concentration, three PBK models were employed for each congener, and performance tracked the ability of each model to convert an external exposure into the corresponding liver steady-state concentration. The BMA model combined individual model predictions into a single posterior distribution. Figure 63 illustrates the predictive performance of each model. The predicted median of the BMA model is almost identical to the Worley et al. (2017) model prediction for PFOA and to the Chou & Lin (2019) model for PFOS, in alignment with the assigned weights presented in Figure 61. The 95% posterior credible interval (pink band) encompasses all data points, with its width differing between PFOA and PFOS, in accordance with the observed data variability. Therefore, in addition to identifying the best performing models for each chemical and each compartment through model weight assignment, the BMA framework enables the quantification of prediction uncertainty through the residual variability, which in this context reflects all of the observed data variability. This uncertainty quantification builds confidence and reliability in prediction outcomes and allows for

probabilistic assessment of the underlying exposure risk, even when the individual models provide single point concentration estimates.

Figure 63. Simulated liver concentrations against observed liver concentrations. Data points represent average liver concentrations calculated using an average liver-plasma partition coefficient derived from the studies of Olsen et al. (2003), Maestri et al. (2006), Nielsen et al. (2023), Baumert et al. (2023), multiplied by an assumed serum concentration equal to 10 µg/L. The BMA serum models for PFOA and PFOS were used in reverse dosimetry mode to estimate the external exposure that corresponds to a steady state serum concentration of 10 µg/L. This external exposure was then used as input to individual models through forward dosimetry to predict the liver concentration at steady state

3.7.7. Jaqpot Infrastructure: Toluene di-isocyanate (TDI) PBK

The model applied here is an implementation of the PBK model developed by Scholten et al. (2023) in their paper “A physiologically-based kinetic (PBK) model for work-related diisocyanate exposure: Relevance for the design and reporting of biomonitoring studies.”

This PBK model simulates the biodistribution and urinary excretion of TDI and its metabolites (TDA) in humans following occupational exposure via inhalation and dermal routes. The model is structured into multiple compartments, including the lungs (interstitial and vascular), skin, arterial and venous blood, kidney, gut lumen, and the remaining tissues. A key feature is the explicit representation of

unbound, albumin-bound, and macromolecule-bound fractions within each compartment, capturing the rapid protein-binding behavior of diisocyanates (Figure 64).

The model is designed to reproduce chronic occupational exposure scenarios (e.g., 8 hours per day, 5 days per week) and accounts for the biphasic elimination of TDI: a rapid phase reflecting recent exposure, and a slower phase reflecting degradation of protein adducts.

For inhalation exposure, the input parameters "inhalation", "inhalation_time", and "Fabs" are specified as vectors describing the exposure profile (Table 68). In the case of chronic occupational exposure, this typically involves alternating periods of exposure during working hours and no exposure during evenings, nights, and weekends. Importantly, the model explicitly incorporates weekend breaks, reflecting realistic workplace conditions.

An example exposure scenario could be the inhalation of 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{h}$ TDI for 8 working hours per day, 5 days per week, over 26 weeks. The fraction absorbed in the lungs (Fabs) can be user-defined; however, Scholten et al. (2023) applied a value of 0.2 (Figure 65).

Model outputs include the predicted mass and concentration of TDI across all compartments, as well as the urinary mass and concentration of TDA (Table 69, Figure 66-67). The model also estimates the levels of TDA conjugates, which are ultimately converted to amines and excreted in urine. These results are expressed as $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$ creatinine, the standard biomarker used in occupational biomonitoring. A full description of the model structure, parameterization, and validation against human biomonitoring data is available in Scholten et al. (2023).

The R implementation of the model, together with the code for deploying it on the Jaqpot platform (<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2207/description>), is available in a public GitHub repository (<https://github.com/ntua-unit-of-control-and-informatics/Insight-PBK/tree/bd7f799641f4ceadb5ef90fc5dbcf88bc23747d/Scholten%20et%20al.2023>) that hosts several published PBK models for different compounds and organisms.

Figure 64. Schematic representation of the PBK model for TDI (Scholten et al., 2023)

Table 68: TDI model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
BW	kg	Total body weight of human
inhalation	ug/h	Inhalation rate (amount of the substance in which the individual is exposed per hour)
inhalation_time	h	Time at which the subject is exposed to the selected substance
Fabs	-	Fraction absorbed in lungs after inhalation exposure
sim.start	h	Initial time point of simulation
sim.end	h	Final time point of simulation
sim.step	h	The integration step of simulation

Table 69: TDI model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Alung_int_ub	ug	Amount of unbound TDI in lung interstitial compartment
Alung_int_alb	ug	Amount of TDI bound to albumin in lung interstitial compartment

Alung_int_mcr	ug	Amount of TDI bound to macromolecules in lung interstitial compartment
Alung_vas_ub	ug	Amount of unbound TDI in lung vascular compartment
Alung_vas_alb	ug	Amount of TDI bound to albumin in lung vascular compartment
Alung_vas_mcr	ug	Amount of TDI bound to macromolecules in lung vascular compartment
Aart_ub	ug	Amount of unbound TDI in arterial blood compartment
Aart_alb	ug	Amount of TDI bound to albumin in arterial blood compartment
Aart_mcr	ug	Amount of TDI bound to macromolecules in arterial blood compartment
Aven_ub	ug	Amount of unbound TDI in venous blood compartment
Aven_alb	ug	Amount of TDI bound to albumin in venous blood compartment
Aven_mcr	ug	Amount of TDI bound to macromolecules in venous blood compartment
Asurf_ub	ug	Amount of unbound TDI in skin surface compartment
Ascve_ub	ug	Amount of unbound TDI in skin barrier compartment
Ascve_alb	ug	Amount of TDI bound to albumin in skin barrier compartment
Ascve_mcr	ug	Amount of TDI bound to macromolecules in skin barrier compartment
Askn_ub	ug	Amount of unbound TDI in skin tissue compartment
Askn_mcr	ug	Amount of TDI bound to macromolecules in skin tissue compartment
Alum	ug	Amount of TDI in gut lumen compartment
Akid_ub	ug	Amount of unbound TDI in kidney tissue compartment
Akid_mcr	ug	Amount of TDI bound to macromolecules in kidney tissue compartment
Auri_amine	ug	Amount of amine metabolite TDA in urine compartment
Aurine	ug	Amount of TDI in urine compartment
Afeces	ug	Amount of TDI in feces compartment
Arem_ub	ug	Amount of unbound TDI in remaining tissues compartment
Vuri	L	Urine volume
Clung_int_ub	ug/L	Concentration of unbound TDI in lung interstitial compartment
Clung_int_alb	ug/L	Concentration of TDI bound to albumin in lung interstitial compartment
Clung_int_mcr	ug/L	Concentration of TDI bound to macromolecules in lung interstitial compartment
Clung_vas_ub	ug/L	Concentration of unbound TDI in lung vascular compartment
Clung_vas_alb	ug/L	Concentration of TDI bound to albumin in lung vascular compartment
Clung_vas_mcr	ug/L	Concentration of TDI bound to macromolecules in lung vascular compartment
Cart_ub	ug/L	Concentration of TDI bound to albumin in arterial blood compartment

Cart_alb	ug/L	Concentration of TDI bound to albumin in arterial blood compartment
Cart_mcr	ug/L	Concentration of TDI bound to macromolecules in arterial blood compartment
Cven_ub	ug/L	Concentration of unbound TDI in venous blood compartment
Cven_alb	ug/L	Concentration of TDI bound to albumin in venous blood compartment
Cven_mcr	ug/L	Concentration of TDI bound to macromolecules in venous blood compartment
Curine	ug/L	Concentration of TDI in urine compartment
Curine_amine	ug/L	Concentration of amine metabolite TDA in urine compartment
Time	h	Simulation time vector

Dashboard > Models > TDI Human PBK

TDI Human PBK

Evie Papakyriakopoulou

@eviep

28 days ago

R_PBPBK

Description Features Predict Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form or Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

inhalation*

Inhalation: 20 Remove

Inhalation: 20 Remove

Inhalation: 20 Remove

Add value

inhalation_time*

Inhalation_time: 0 Remove

Inhalation_time: 8 Remove

Inhalation_time: 24 Remove

Add value

BW*

85

Fabs*

0.2

sim.start*

0

sim.end*

96

sim.step*

0.5

Submit

Figure 65. Prediction example from GUI using TDI Human PBK model

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Figure 66. Plot of TDI amount (ug) in different compartments of the model applying the exposure scenario described in figure 65.

Figure 67. Plot of TDI concentration (ug/L) in different compartments of the model applying the exposure scenario described in figure 65.

3.7.8. Jaqpot Infrastructure: Acetone PBK

The model applied here is an implementation of the PBK model for acetone in humans, adapted from the structure described by Mörk & Johanson (2006) in their paper “A human physiological toxicokinetic model for acetone uptake, distribution, and elimination”.

This PBK model describes the uptake, distribution, metabolism, and excretion of acetone in humans, with a particular focus on inhalation exposure. The model was designed to link external air concentrations to internal acetone kinetics in blood and tissues produced at different levels of physical exercise, thereby supporting risk assessment and biomonitoring studies in occupational and environmental settings. Specifically, the built model is able to explain the toxicokinetics of an inhaled polar volatile substance in arterial blood, and mixed-exhaled air at various workloads.

Two different model structures were implemented to represent pulmonary uptake and distribution of acetone: the inert-tube model and the washin–washout model. The inert-tube model is a simplified approach that treats the airways as passive conduits, assuming that inhaled acetone passes directly to the alveolar region without any significant exchange in the conducting airways. Consequently, only alveolar uptake and exhalation are explicitly represented, and the airway compartments are not included as distinct exchanging spaces. By contrast, the washin–washout model introduces explicit bronchial and mucosal compartments, thereby capturing transient storage and delayed release (“washin” during inhalation, “washout” during exhalation) of acetone in the conducting airways. This added complexity enables simulation of the early, non-steady-state phases of exposure and recovery, when airway absorption and desorption contribute significantly to exhaled concentrations. Thus, the main difference between the two models lies in the inclusion of bronchial and mucosal compartments in the washin–washout version, whereas the inert-tube model routes the inhaled gas directly to the alveolar compartment. In both model types the arterial blood compartment serves as the central distributing pool to peripheral tissues (Figure 68).

Metabolic clearance of acetone is represented as a saturable process occurring in the liver. In addition to metabolism, elimination occurs through exhalation, with cumulative exhaled acetone tracked over time. The model also includes cumulative metabolism as a separate output variable.

For inhalation exposure, the model requires the specification of inhalation and inhalation_time vectors, which define the administered dose at each time step. This allows for simulation of continuous exposures, intermittent pulses, or workload-dependent scenarios (e.g., rest versus exercise, where pulmonary ventilation and cardiac output are adjusted accordingly) (Table 70).

The outputs of the model include predicted acetone amounts and concentrations in each tissue compartment (fat, richly perfused, resting muscle, working muscle, liver, bronchial tissue, mucosa, alveoli, arterial blood), as well as the cumulative amounts exhaled and metabolized (Table 71). These outputs can be directly compared with experimental data from controlled human exposure studies, for example blood acetone concentrations or breath acetone elimination kinetics.

A detailed description of the model assumptions, parameterization, and validation is given in Mörk & Johanson (2006), including comparisons to observed acetone kinetics during exposure and recovery phases. Validation focused on reproducing time courses of acetone in blood, under both resting and exercise conditions.

In the simulation shown in Figure 69, the model is driven by an inhalation-exposure scenario representative of a controlled human chamber study. A constant acetone concentration in inspired air is applied for a defined exposure duration (e.g., 120 min), followed by a post-exposure recovery phase in clean air. The physiological state of the individual corresponds to *resting workload* (workload = “Rest”), which determines the values of pulmonary ventilation, cardiac output and perfusion distribution used during the simulation. The inhalation pattern is specified through the *inhalation* and *inhalation_time* input vectors, which administer a steady inhaled concentration during the exposure window and zero thereafter. Anthropometric inputs (e.g., 70 kg body weight, 181 cm height) define organ volumes and flows for the simulated individual, while the selected model type (inert-tube or washin–washout) determines how acetone exchanges within the airways. Figures 70 and 71 illustrate the resulting internal dosimetry under the exposure scenario of Figure 69.

The R implementation of the model, together with scripts for deployment on the Jaqpot platform (<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2275/description>), is available in a public GitHub repository (<https://github.com/ntua-unit-of-control-and-informatics/Insight-PBK/tree/bd7f799641f4ceadb5ef90fc5dbcfa88bc23747d/Mork%20and%20Johanson%2C2006>), which contains multiple published PBK models for various compounds and organisms.

Figure 68. Schematic representation of the PBK model for Acetone (Mörk & Johanson, 2006)

Table 70: Acetone model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
BW	kg	Total body weight of human
height	cm	Height of human
Cendo	mg/L	Average endogenous concentration of acetone in blood
workload	Light, Medium or High	Physical exercise
model_type	Washin-washout or Inert-tube	Type of model structure
inhalation	mg/min	Inhalation rate (amount of the substance in which the individual is exposed per min)
inhalation_time	min	Time at which the subject is exposed to the selected substance
sex	Male or Female	Sex of the human
sim.start	h	First point of the simulation time vector
sim.end	h	Last point of the simulation time vector
sim.step	h	Time increment of the simulation time vector

Table 71: Acetone model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
A_fat	mg	Amount of acetone in fat
A_rich	mg	Amount of acetone in richly perfused tissues
A_rest	mg	Amount of acetone in resting muscle and skin
A_work	mg	Amount of acetone in working muscle
A_liv	mg	Amount of acetone in liver
A_bro	mg	Amount of acetone in bronchioles
A_muc	mg	Amount of acetone in mucosa
A_alv	mg	Amount of acetone in alveolae
A_art	mg	Amount of acetone in arterial blood
A_met	mg	Amount of metabolized acetone
PR	mg/min	Production rate
A_exh	mg	Amount of acetone exhaled
C_fat	mg/L	Concentration of acetone in fat
C_rich	mg/L	Concentration of acetone in richly perfused tissues
C_rest	mg/L	Concentration of acetone in resting muscle and skin
C_work	mg/L	Concentration of acetone in working muscle

C_liv	mg/L	Concentration of acetone in liver
C_bro	mg/L	Concentration of acetone in bronchioles
C_muc	mg/L	Concentration of acetone in mucosa
C_alv	mg/L	Concentration of acetone in alveolae
C_art	mg/L	Concentration of acetone in arterial blood
time	min	Simulation time vector

Acetone PBK

Evie Papakyriakopoulou @eviep about 7 hours ago R_PBPk

Description Features **Predict** Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form or Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

BW* 71 **height*** 181 **Cendo*** 1.4 **workload*** Rest

inhalation* 8.8 **inhalation_time*** 0

inhalation* 8.8 **inhalation_time*** 1

inhalation* 8.8 **inhalation_time*** 2

model_type* inert-tube **sex*** Male

sim.start* 0 **sim.end*** 240 **sim.step*** 1

Submit

Figure 69. Prediction example from GUI using Acetone Human PBK model

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Figure 70. Plot of Acetone amount (mg) in different compartments of the model applying the exposure scenario described in figure X10.

Figure 71. Plot of Acetone concentration (mg/L) in different compartments of the model applying the exposure scenario described in figure X10.

3.7.9. Jaqpot Infrastructure: Ethylene Glycol PBK

The model applied here is an implementation of the PBK model in humans, developed by Corley et al. (2005) in their paper “Development of a Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic Model for Ethylene Glycol and Its Metabolite, Glycolic Acid, in Rats and Humans”.

This PBK model describes the absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion of ethylene glycol (EG) and its primary metabolite glycolic acid (GA) in humans, with a particular focus on inhalation exposure scenarios. The model was designed to support human health risk assessment by linking external exposures to internal dose metrics, especially in the context of developmental toxicity, which has been associated with elevated GA levels in rodents.

The model is structured around physiologically realistic compartments representing the lungs, liver, kidneys, skin, gastrointestinal tract, fat, richly perfused tissues, and slowly perfused tissues. EG and GA are assumed to distribute instantaneously within each compartment according to perfusion rates and tissue:blood partition coefficients. Metabolic transformations are explicitly represented: EG is oxidized in the liver to GA via a saturable, rate-limiting step, and GA undergoes further metabolism to glyoxylic acid. Elimination pathways are also incorporated: EG is cleared primarily by urinary excretion, while GA clearance is described through a mechanistic kidney submodel that accounts for glomerular filtration and saturable tubular reabsorption (Figure 72). This latter feature is critical for accurately capturing GA kinetics, particularly at lower EG doses where simple first-order clearance models overpredict urinary elimination.

For inhalation exposure, the input parameters 'inhalation' and 'inhalation_time' should be specified as vectors to define the exposure pattern (Table 72). This enables flexible simulation of both continuous and intermittent exposures. For example, an exposure scenario could involve the inhalation of 23 mg/h EG during a 4-hour period, administered in 15-minute time intervals.

The model outputs include predicted time courses of EG and GA concentrations and masses in blood and tissues, as well as the cumulative mass of EG and GA excreted in urine (Table 73).

A full description of the model structure, parameterization, and validation is provided in Corley et al. (2005), including cross-species comparisons between rats and humans and extensions to clinical overdose scenarios. Validation was performed against both controlled human inhalation studies and dose levels.

In the simulation illustrated in Figure 73, the model is driven by an inhalation-exposure scenario representing a controlled human exposure setting. The input vectors inhalation and inhalation_time specify the time-resolved exposure pattern, here corresponding to a constant inhaled EG dose rate of 23 mg/h delivered over a 4-hour period, broken into short inhalation intervals (e.g., 0.25 h). The simulated individual is a 68-kg female, with anthropometric parameters determining organ volumes, blood flows, and renal filtration capacity. Workload is set to “Rest,” ensuring that pulmonary

ventilation, cardiac output, and tissue perfusion reflect a resting physiological state. After the 4-hour exposure window, inhalation is set to zero to simulate a post-exposure clearance phase in clean air. Figures 74 and 75 present the resulting internal distribution of EG and GA under the exposure scenario of Figure 73.

The R implementation of the model, together with scripts for deployment on the Jaqpot platform (<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2233/description>), is available in a public GitHub repository (<https://github.com/ntua-unit-of-control-and-informatics/Insight-PBK/tree/bd7f799641f4ceadb5ef90fc5dbcfa88bc23747d/Corley%20et%20al.2005>), which contains multiple published PBK models for various compounds and organisms.

Figure 72. Schematic representation of the PBK model for EG and GA (Corley et al., 2005)

Table 72: Ethylene Glycol model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
BW	kg	Total body weight of human
inhalation	mg/h	Inhalation rate (amount of the substance in which the individual is exposed per h)

inhalation_time	h	Time at which the subject is exposed to the selected substance
sex	Male or Female	Sex of the human
sim.start	h	First point of the simulation time vector
sim.end	h	Last point of the simulation time vector
sim.step	h	Time increment of the simulation time vector

Table 73: Ethylene Glycol model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
A_ven_EG	mg	Amount of EG in venous blood
A_art_EG	mg	Amount of EG in arterial blood
A_lung_EG	mg	Amount of EG in lungs compartment
A_liver_EG	mg	Amount of EG in liver compartment
A_kidney_EG	mg	Amount of EG in kidney compartment
A_fat_EG	mg	Amount of EG in fat compartment
A_skin_EG	mg	Amount of EG in skin compartment
A_GI_EG	mg	Amount of EG in gastrointestinal compartment
A_rich_EG	mg	Amount of EG in richly perfused tissues compartment
A_slow_EG	mg	Amount of EG in slowly perfused tissues compartment
A_ven_GA	mg	Amount of GA in venous blood
A_art_GA	mg	Amount of GA in arterial blood
A_liver_GA	mg	Amount of GA in liver compartment
A_kidney_GA	mg	Amount of GA in kidney compartment
A_fat_GA	mg	Amount of GA in fat compartment
A_skin_GA	mg	Amount of GA in skin compartment
A_GI_GA	mg	Amount of GA in gastrointestinal compartment
A_rich_GA	mg	Amount of GA in richly perfused tissues compartment
A_slow_GA	mg	Amount of GA in slowly perfused tissues compartment
A_tubule_GA	mg	Amount of GA in tubule kidney compartment
Cum_urine_EG	mg	Cumulative amounts of EG eliminated in the urine
Cum_urine_GA	mg	Cumulative amounts of GA eliminated in the urine
Cum_met_GA	mg	Cumulative amounts of GA metabolite
C_ven_EG	mg/L	Concentration of EG in venous blood
C_art_EG	mg/L	Concentration of EG in arterial blood
C_lung_EG	mg/L	Concentration of EG in lungs compartment
C_liver_EG	mg/L	Concentration of EG in liver compartment
C_kidney_EG	mg/L	Concentration of EG in kidney compartment

C_fat_EG	mg/L	Concentration of EG in fat compartment
C_skin_EG	mg/L	Concentration of EG in skin compartment
C_GI_EG	mg/L	Concentration of EG in gastrointestinal compartment
C_rich_EG	mg/L	Concentration of EG in richly perfused tissues compartment
C_slow_EG	mg/L	Concentration of GA in slowly perfused tissues compartment
C_ven_GA	mg/L	Concentration of GA in venous blood
C_art_GA	mg/L	Concentration of GA in arterial blood
C_liver_GA	mg/L	Concentration of GA in liver compartment
C_kidney_GA	mg/L	Concentration of GA in kidney compartment
C_fat_GA	mg/L	Concentration of GA in fat compartment
C_skin_GA	mg/L	Concentration of GA in skin compartment
C_GI_GA	mg/L	Concentration of GA in gastrointestinal compartment
C_rich_GA	mg/L	Concentration of GA in richly perfused tissues compartment
C_slow_GA	mg/L	Concentration of GA in slowly perfused tissues compartment
C_tubule_GA	mg/L	Concentration of GA in tubule kidney compartment
C_plasma_EG	mg/L	Concentration of EG in plasma compartment
C_plasma_GA	mg/L	Concentration of GA in plasma compartment
time	h	Simulation time vector

Ethylene Glycol PBK

Evie Papakyriakopoulou
@eviep

18 days ago

R_PBPk

Description Features **Predict** Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form or Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

	<p>inhalation*</p> <input type="text" value="23"/> <input type="button" value="Remove"/>	<p>inhalation_time*</p> <input type="text" value="0.25"/> <input type="button" value="Remove"/>	
	<input type="text" value="23"/> <input type="button" value="Remove"/>	<input type="text" value="0.5"/> <input type="button" value="Remove"/>	
<p>BW*</p> <input type="text" value="96"/>	<input type="text" value="23"/> <input type="button" value="Remove"/>	<input type="text" value="0.75"/> <input type="button" value="Remove"/>	<p>sex*</p> <input type="text" value="Female"/>
	<input type="text" value="23"/> <input type="button" value="Remove"/>	<input type="text" value="1"/> <input type="button" value="Remove"/>	
	<input type="button" value="Add value"/>		
<p>sim.start*</p> <input type="text" value="0"/>	<p>sim.end*</p> <input type="text" value="4"/>	<p>sim.step*</p> <input type="text" value="0.01"/>	
<input type="button" value="Submit"/>			

Figure 73. Prediction example from GUI using Ethylene Glycol Human PBK model

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Figure 74. Plot of EG amount (mg) in different compartments of the model applying the exposure scenario described in figure 73.

Figure 75. Plot of EG concentration (mg/L) in different compartments of the model applying the exposure scenario described in figure 73.

3.7.10. Jaqpot Infrastructure: PFBS PBK

This PBK model is an adaptation of the PBK model originally developed by Worley et al. (2017) in the paper “Physiologically based pharmacokinetic modeling of human exposure to perfluorooctanoic acid suggests historical non drinking-water exposures are important for predicting current serum concentrations”. This PBK model was initially developed for predicting the kinetics of PFOA in human organisms. Therefore the model incorporates reabsorption mechanisms of PFAS from renal system to blood circulation and takes into account the binding to proteins. Therefore, reestimation of partition coefficients and recalibration of the urinary elimination kinetic parameters are required to adapt the model for the case of perfluorobutanesulfonic acid (PFBS).

The model consists of multiple compartments representing different human tissues. Specifically, the stomach is considered to be the organ of PFAS input, since the exposure is through consuming contaminated water or food. Next, the model contains specific compartments small intestines, serum, liver, kidney while the remaining tissues are lumped into one compartment, named as rest of the body. The model takes into account both fecal and urinary elimination of the PFAS and a detailed modeling approach has been implemented for the renal elimination. A schematic representation of the model’s

structure is presented in Figure 76, presenting how the compartments of the model are interconnected.

Figure 76. Schematic representation of the PBK model for PFBS and PFHxA (Worley et al., 2017).

The renal excretion of PFAS is modeled with three compartments. PFAS in kidney blood can either pass directly into the filtrate through the glomerular filtration (GFR) or be actively transported into proximal tubule cells via basolateral transporters. The transport of PFAS from kidney blood to proximal tubule cells is a nonlinear process described by Michaelis-Menten kinetics and the parameters $V_{max_{baso}}$ and $K_{m_{baso}}$. Similarly has been modeled the active transportation of PFAS from filtrate into the proximal tubule cells, using the corresponding parameters $V_{max_{api}}$ and $K_{m_{api}}$.

The partition coefficient of the model required adjustments for PFBS, as it is expected to distribute differently than PFOA between the blood and the tissues. However, no tissue-concentration data were available in literature for these two congeners, thus the direct fitting of these parameters was infeasible. Therefore, the new partition coefficients of liver, kidney and rest of the body were estimated by applying the equilibrium distribution modeling (EDM), introduced by Allendorf et al. (2020). EDM is a

modeling approach that estimates how PFAS distribute across different organs and tissues in mammals, including humans. First, the model makes use of experimentally determined distribution coefficients that describe the distribution of PFAS between multiple physiological matrices and water (*w*), including albumin proteins (*alb*) in blood, membrane lipids (*ml*), structural proteins (*sp*) in tissues, storage lipids (*sl*) in fat, and fatty acid binding protein (FABP), wherever it is applicable. The distribution coefficients for PFBS as well as the fractional volumes of each matrix in the tissues were directly sourced from Allendorf et al. (2020).

The total distribution coefficient between each tissue and water was estimated through the following equation

$$D_{i,organ/w} = f_{i_{alb}} D_{i_{alb/w}} + f_{i_{sp}} D_{i_{sp/w}} + f_{i_{ml}} D_{i_{ml/w}} + f_{i_{sl}} D_{i_{sl/w}} + f_{i_{FABP}} D_{i_{FABP/w}} + f_{i_{sp}} D_{i_{sp/w}} + f_{i_w}$$

where, *i* denotes the PFAS congener, $D_{i_{matrix/w}}$ is defined as the distribution coefficient of PFAS *i* between any matrix and water, thus it is estimated as

$$D_{i_{matrix/w}} = \frac{C_{i,matrix}}{C_{i,water}}$$

with $C_{i,matrix}$ and $C_{i,water}$ denoting the concentration of compound *i* in matrix in the corresponding biological matrix and aqueous phase in steady state. The coefficient $f_{i_{matrix}}$ denotes the fraction of the sorbed compound *i* in each matrix at steady state. For instance, the sorption capacity $f_{i_{alb}}$ for albumin relative to all other organ components is estimated through the following equation

$$f_{i_{alb}} = \frac{1}{1 + D_{i_w/alb} \frac{V_w}{V_{alb}} + D_{i_{sp/alb}} \frac{V_{sp}}{V_{alb}} + D_{i_{ml/alb}} \frac{V_{ml}}{V_{alb}} + D_{i_{sl/alb}} \frac{V_{sl}}{V_{alb}} + D_{i_{FABP/alb}} \frac{V_{FABP}}{V_{alb}}}$$

where V_i denotes the volume of the respective matrix (volumes of all matrices for each organ are sourced from Allendorf et al. (2020)). Similar equations for the sorption capacities of the rest matrices are provided by Allendorf et al. (2020).

The final step for the estimation of the tissue:plasma partition coefficients of PFBS for the PBK model is to estimate the following ratio

$$PC_{tissue/plasma} = D_{PFBS,organ/w} / D_{PFBS,plasma/w}$$

Meanwhile, following the compartmentalisation in the model of Worley et al. (2017), the partition coefficients only for liver, kidney and rest of the body compartments were estimated with the EDM approach. The results for the three partition coefficients are presented in table 74.

Table 74: Tissue:plasma partition coefficients for PFBS estimated by EDM.

Tissue	Partition Coefficient
Liver	0.459
Kidney	0.454
Rest of Body	0.410

The experimental data for PFBS came from the study of Olsen et al. (2009), a comparison study of PFBS kinetics between different species, including humans. Specifically, the human data in this study come from the occupational exposure of six workers involved in production of PFBS. Specifically, the workers were removed from the production for the time period that the blood samples were received, meaning that the occupational exposure is considered negligible for the time period of the measurements. PFBS concentrations at serum were reported at up to 10 time points for each subject in a time span of 180 days. The data of each subject were used to recalibrate the relative activity factor of the apical transporters (RAF_{api}) and the $K_{m,apical}$, which is included in the Michaelis-Menten equation that describe the the kinetics of the apical transporters, that are responsible for the reabsorption of PFBS from filtrate into the proximal tubule cells.

The availability of the measurements of each individual subject enabled the application of a hierarchical statistical model, regarding the estimation of RAF_{api} . Specifically, the statistical model is structured by two levels. Firstly, the population level is defined by the prior distributions of population for RAF_{api} and $K_{m,apical}$ as follows:

Population level:

$$\begin{aligned}
 RAF_{api} &\sim \text{LogNormal}(\mu_{pop}, \sigma_{pop}) \\
 \mu_{pop} &\sim N(\mu_{log}, 1.0) \\
 \sigma_{pop} &\sim N^+(0, 0.5) \\
 K_{m,apical} &\sim \text{LogNormal}(\mu_{log, K_m}, \sigma_{log, K_m})
 \end{aligned}$$

where μ_{pop} and σ_{pop} denote the logarithm of location and scale of the log-normal distribution of RAF_{api} . The implementation of log-normal distributions for RAF_{api} and $K_{m,apical}$ is a common strategy, where the kinetic parameters are positive-defined. Moreover, the location of the RAF_{api} distribution is forced to follow normal distribution around the default value of the PBK model of Worley et al. (2017) for PFOA, after being transformed according to the log-normal distribution.

Next, the subject level that is defined by the prior distributions for each subject as:

Subject Level:

For each subject $i \in [1,6]$:

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$$RAF_{api_i} \sim \text{LogNormal}(\mu_{pop}, \sigma_{pop})$$

Consequently, the **log-likelihood** is defined as:

$$\log(C_{obs,ij}) \sim N(\log(C_{pred,ij}(RAF_{api_i}, K_{m,apical})), \sigma)$$

Where j denotes the observations at different timepoints and σ is the observation error standard deviation on the log scale. This error implied multiplicative error on the original concentration scale, meaning that the magnitude of measurement error is proportional to the concentration level itself. This approach is equivalent to assuming constant coefficient of variation across different concentration levels, which is an appropriate approach for pharmacokinetic data.

The posterior distributions of all parameters were estimated with Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling, which was implemented with [Turing.jl](https://www.turing.ac.uk) probabilistic programming language. The algorithm that was employed is No U-Turn Sampler (NUTS), which is a variant of Hamiltonian Monte Carlo, effective for exploring complex posterior distributions in hierarchical models. The implementation for this model consisted of running 4 parallel chains, with each one of them running for 1000 iterations, after following 500 burn-in iterations, that were discarded from the final results of each posterior distribution. Thus, the posterior distributions were estimated based on 4000 iterations in total. The convergence of the chains was assessed by the Gelman-Rubin statistic (\widehat{R}), which was lower than 1.01 for all parameters, indicating strong divergence of the chains. Additionally, the traceplots of the population and individual parameters are presented in Figure 77, validating the convergence of the chains as well. The estimations about the posterior distributions were evaluated with the posterior predictive check of the PBK model. Specifically, the 4000 samples of the MCMC chains were parsed to the PBK model and simulated the data for each one of the subjects that participated in the study. Next, the median and the 95% prediction interval of the serum concentration of each subject were plotted with the experimental serum measurement in Figure 78. This figure validates that the median of the model's predictions fall close to the measured serum concentration for all subjects. Additionally, it is important that all observations of serum concentration fall into the 95% prediction interval of the model, meaning that the model has successfully described the variability that exists in the experimental measurements. Finally, the results for the posterior distributions of the population level are reported in terms of mean and standard deviation in normal scale at table 75.

Table 75: Tissue:plasma partition coefficients for PFBS estimated by EDM.

Parameter	Mean	Standard Deviation
Mean RAFapi	7.141e-5	4.326e-5
SD RAFapi	4.34e-5	8.787e-5
Km_apical	109100.0	45510.0
σ	0.5262	0.0589

Figure 77. Diagnostic traceplots of MCMC for PFBS PBK model calibration.

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Figure 78. Posterior predictive check for the PFBS PBK model in the serum data of 6 subjects.

The final PFBS model is hosted as an online service at Japspot application and can be visited at <https://app.japspot.org/dashboard/models/2315/description>. The model is accompanied by its dedicated user interface and the user can use the model to run online simulations. The input variables of the model that are required to run a simulation are reported in table 76. The model requires the body weight of the simulated human object and takes into account either continuous oral exposure or bolus oral intake. This feature enables both short-term and long-term simulations. Moreover, the user has to select the time scale of the simulation, enabling them to study the kinetics in different time scales, from minutes to years. By selecting the time scale of the simulation all time dependent parameters of the model are automatically scaled accordingly. Finally, the input variables sim.start, sim.end and sim.step refer to the starting, ending time point and to the time-step of the simulation. The output variables of the model are reported in detail in table 77, and they consist of the concentrations of PFBS in all compartments as well as the PFBS amount in them in mass terms.

Table 76: PFBS PBK model input variables.

Name	Units	Description
BW	kg	Bodyweight of simulated human.
ingestion	µg/time_scale	Defines the ingestion rate of PFBS. The units are defined by the selected time scale. This is applied when exp_type = "continuous".
ingestion_time	time_scale	Defines the time points that the ingestion rate of PFBS changes. This is applied when exp_type = "continuous".
admin_dose	µg	Doses of PFBS directly administered to the stomach. This is applied when exp_type = "bolus".
admin_time	time_scale	Time points at which the oral doses are administered. This is applied when exp_type = "bolus".
exp_type	-	Defines the type of exposure. "Continuous" exposure denotes long term oral exposure with specific ingestion rates. "Bolus" exposure denotes bolus dosing with specified doses.
time_scale		Defines the time scale of the simulation. It also adjusts the time scale of all time dependent parameters of the PBK model accordingly.
sim.start	time_scale	Defines the starting time point of the simulation.
sim.end	time_scale	Defines the ending point of the simulation.
sim.step	time_scale	Defines the time step of the simulation.

Table 77: PFBS PBK model output variables.

Name	Units	Description
CR	µg/L	Total PFBS concentration in "rest of the body" compartment.
CVR	µg/L	PFBS concentration in serum in "rest of the body" compartment.
CVK	µg/L	PFBS concentration in serum in kidney tissue.
CPTC	µg/L	PFBS concentration in proximal tubule cells (PTC).
Cfil	µg/L	PFBS concentration in filtrate (Proximal tubule lumen).
CL	µg/L	PFBS concentration in liver.
CVL	µg/L	PFBS concentration in serum of liver.
CA_free	µg/L	Free concentration of PFBS in serum.
CA	µg/L	Total concentration of PFBS in serum.
AR	µg	PFBS mass in "rest of the body" compartment.
AKb	µg	PFBS mass in kidney serum.
APTC	µg	PFBS mass in proximal tubule cells.

Afil	μg	PFBS in filtrate (proximal tubule lumen).
AL	μg	PFBS mass in liver.
Aplas_free	μg	PFBS mass free in serum.
AST	μg	PFBS mass in stomach.
ASI	μg	PFBS mass in small intestine.
Aurine	μg	PFBS mass excreted with urine (cumulative).
Afeces	μg	PFBS mass excreted with feces (cumulative).
Abile	μg	PFBS mass in bile.
Atissue	μg	Total PFBS mass in tissues.
Aloss	μg	Total excreted PFBS mass.
Atotal	μg	Total PFBS mass into the organism and excreted.
time	time_scale	Simulation time.

An example of a simulation with the PFBS PBK model is presented in Figure 79. This example simulates the kinetics of PFBS in a human of 70 kg for 365 days. The subject is supposed to be orally exposed to 0.01 μg/day for the first 100 days and then the exposure is eliminated for the rest of the simulation. After the completion of the simulation, Jackpot user interface automatically creates two plots that present concentration and mass of PFBS over the simulation time. The plots of this example are presented in Figure 80. Finally, the code for the fitting of the model as well as for the deployment on Jaqpot is available at https://github.com/ntua-unit-of-control-and-informatics/Insight-PBK/tree/main/PFAS_models/PFBS.

PFBS Human PBK

Vassilis Minadakis
@vassilis_minadakis 3 days ago R_PBPB

Description Features **Predict** Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

BW* 70 **Remove**

ingestion* 0.01 **Remove** **ingestion_time*** 0 **Remove** **admin_dose*** 0 **Remove**

ingestion 0 **Remove** **ingestion_time** 100 **Remove** **Add value** **Add value**

admin_time* 0 **Remove** **exp_type*** continuous **time_scale*** days **sim.start*** 0 **Add value**

sim.end* 365 **sim.step*** 1 **Add value**

Submit

Figure 79. Prediction example from GUI using PFBS PBK model.

Figure 80. Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$) and mass (μg) of PFBS in different compartments of the model applying the exposure scenario in Figure 79.

3.7.11. Jaqpot Infrastructure: PFHxA PBK

This PBK model is also an extension of the PBK model originally developed by Worley et al. (2017) in the paper “Physiologically based pharmacokinetic modeling of human exposure to perfluorooctanoic acid suggests historical non drinking-water exposures are important for predicting current serum concentrations”. The same structure that is presented in Figure 76 was used to simulate the kinetics of PFHxA, by estimating the partition coefficients with EDM and recalibrating some of the model’s

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kinetic parameters, to adjust to PFHxA. The values of the partition coefficients as estimated from the EDM are reported in table 78.

Table 78: Tissue:plasma partition coefficients for PFHxA estimated by EDM.

Tissue	Partition Coefficient
Liver	0.528
Kidney	0.514
Rest of Body	0.399

The recalibration of the kinetic parameters of the model for PFHxA was accomplished with plasma and urine data derived from the study of Abraham et al. (2024). In this study, a healthy volunteer was orally exposed to a mixture of PFAS with known concentrations. Multiple plasma and urine samples were taken to measure the concentration of each PFAS. Specifically, 58 plasma and 21 urine measurements are reported in a time span of 12 days. Consequently the implementation of a hierarchical model was not feasible in this case, so a simple MCMC approach was followed, using the framework of [Turing.jl](#). The parameters that were estimated through the MCMC are the relative activity factors of apical (RAF_{api}) and basolateral (RAF_{baso}) transporters and the Michaelis-Menten parameter $K_{m,apical}$ for the apical transporters. Moreover, two observation error terms were estimated for plasma and urine data. Finally, a scaling factor (PC_{scale}) was applied on the partition coefficient for the rest of the body that was estimated through the EDM. This adjustment was necessary, since the estimated partition coefficient resulted in excess accumulation of PFHxA in the rest of the body, which was not aligned with the available experimental data. Therefore, the statistical model applied in this case is as follows:

Priors:

$$\begin{aligned}
 RAF_{api} &\sim \text{LogNormal}(\mu_{\log,RAF_{api}}, \sigma_{\log,RAF_{api}}) \\
 RAF_{baso} &\sim \text{LogNormal}(\mu_{\log,RAF_{baso}}, \sigma_{\log,RAF_{baso}}) \\
 K_{m,apical} &\sim \text{LogNormal}(\mu_{\log,K_m}, \sigma_{\log,K_m}) \\
 PC_{scale} &\sim N^+(\mu_{PC_{scale}}, \sigma_{PC_{scale}}) \\
 \sigma_{plasma} &\sim N^+(0, 0.5) \\
 \sigma_{urine} &\sim N^+(0, 0.5)
 \end{aligned}$$

Likelihood:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \log(C_{plasma,j}) &\sim N(\log(C_{pred,j}(\vec{\theta})), \sigma_{plasma}) \\
 \log(A_{urine,j}) &\sim N(\log(A_{pred,j}(\vec{\theta})), \sigma_{urine})
 \end{aligned}$$

The $\mu_{\log,RAF_{api}}$ and $\sigma_{\log,RAF_{api}}$ denote the location and scale of the log-normally distributed RAF_{api} , which are estimated by the mean and standard deviation of RAF_{api} in normal scale after suitable transformations, defined by the log-normal distribution. Similarly, $\mu_{\log,RAF_{baso}}$ and σ_{\log,K_m} are the same parameters for the log-normally distributed RAF_{baso} parameter, as well as μ_{\log,K_m} and σ_{\log,K_m} for

$K_{m,apical}$. Next, PC_{scale} is set to follow a truncated broad normal distribution, as its value can be only positive. Finally, the likelihood is structured by the observations and predictions for plasma concentration and cumulative PFHxA amount excreted through the urine, with $\hat{\theta}$ denoting the vector of the estimated parameters.

The MCMC implementation is similar to that of the PFBS PBK model. Four chains were run in parallel, with 1000 iterations each one, after 500 burn-in iterations each. The estimations about the posterior distributions of the parameters are reported as mean and standard deviation in normal scale in table 79. The convergence of the chains is validated by the metric \hat{R} , which is lower 1.01 for all parameters. Meanwhile, the traceplots of each parameter is reported in Figure 81, and they are aligned with the \hat{R} values, validating MCMC convergence. Finally, the posterior distributions were checked with the plot of the posterior predictive check. As in the case of PFBS, all samples from the chains of MCMC (4,000 samples in total) were used to run the PBK model and the prediction (median and 95% prediction intervals) were plotted against the observed values for plasma concentrations and cumulative excretion. The results of posterior predictive check are presented in Figures 82 and 83. These plots validate that the model accurately predicts the trendline for plasma concentrations and urinary excretion and all observed values fall within the 95% prediction interval of the model.

Table 79: Tissue:plasma partition coefficients for PFBS estimated by EDM.

Parameter	Mean	Standard Deviation
RAFapi	1.41e-6	3.589e-7
RAFbaso	0.02883	0.007836
Km_apical	72750.0	14210.0
PC_scale	0.1226	0.02496
σ_{plasma}	0.3636	0.0398
σ_{urine}	0.5592	0.0725

Figure 81. Diagnostic traceplots of MCMC for PFHxA PBK model calibration.

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Figure 82. Posterior predictive check for the PFHxA PBK model on plasma concentrations.

Figure 83. Posterior predictive check for the PFHxA PBK model on observed cumulative excretion through urine.

The PFHxA Human PBK model is hosted as an online service at Jaqpot application and can be visited at <https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2303/description>. As the structure of the model is identical to that of the PFBS model described above, the number and the type of the input and output variables are identical. Consequently, a detailed report of the input and output variables are provided in tables 80 and 81, respectively. The code for the fitting of the model as well as for the deployment on Jaqpot is available at https://github.com/ntua-unit-of-control-and-informatics/Insight-PBK/tree/main/PFAS_models/PFHxA.

Table 80: PFHxA PBK model input variables.

Name	Units	Description
BW	kg	Bodyweight of simulated human.
ingestion	µg/time_scale	Defines the ingestion rate of PFHxA. The units are defined by the selected time scale. This is applied when exp_type = "continuous".
ingestion_time	time_scale	Defines the time points that the ingestion rate of PFHxA changes. This is applied when exp_type = "continuous".
admin_dose	µg	Doses of PFHxA directly administered to the stomach. This is applied when exp_type = "bolus".
admin_time	time_scale	Time points at which the oral doses are administered. This is applied when exp_type = "bolus".
exp_type	-	Defines the type of exposure. "Continuous" exposure denotes long term oral exposure with specific ingestion rates. "Bolus" exposure denotes bolus dosing with specified doses.
time_scale		Defines the time scale of the simulation. It also adjusts the time scale of all time dependent parameters of the PBK model accordingly.
sim.start	time_scale	Defines the starting time point of the simulation.
sim.end	time_scale	Defines the ending point of the simulation.
sim.step	time_scale	Defines the time step of the simulation.

Table 81: PFHxA PBK model output variables.

Name	Units	Description
CR	µg/L	Total PFHxA concentration in "rest of the body" compartment.
CVR	µg/L	PFHxA concentration in serum in "rest of the body" compartment.
CVK	µg/L	PFHxA concentration in serum in kidney tissue.
CPTC	µg/L	PFHxA concentration in proximal tubule cells (PTC).
Cfil	µg/L	PFHxA concentration in filtrate (Proximal tubule lumen).

CL	µg/L	PFHxA concentration in liver.
CVL	µg/L	PFHxA concentration in serum of liver.
CA_free	µg/L	Free concentration of PFHxA in serum.
CA	µg/L	Total concentration of PFHxA in serum.
AR	µg	PFHxA mass in "rest of the body" compartment.
AKb	µg	PFHxA mass in kidney serum.
APTC	µg	PFHxA mass in proximal tubule cells.
Afil	µg	PFHxA in filtrate (proximal tubule lumen).
AL	µg	PFHxA mass in liver.
Aplas_free	µg	PFHxA mass free in serum.
AST	µg	PFHxA mass in stomach.
ASI	µg	PFHxA mass in small intestine.
Aurine	µg	PFHxA mass excreted with urine (cumulative).
Afeces	µg	PFHxA mass excreted with feces (cumulative).
Abile	µg	PFHxA mass in bile.
Atissue	µg	Total PFBS mass in tissues.
Aloss	µg	Total excreted PFHxA mass.
Atotal	µg	Total PFHxA mass into the organism and excreted.
time	time_scale	Simulation time.

An example of a simulation with the PFBS PBK model is presented in Figure 84. This example simulates the kinetics of PFHxA in a human of 82 kg for 15 days. This exposure scenario simulates the experiment described in Abraham et al. (2024). The subject was orally exposed to a single dose of 3.99 µg PFHxA. Consequently, the final point of the simulation was set to 15 days, while the step was 0.1 days. After the completion of the simulation, Jaqpot user interface automatically creates two plots that present concentration and mass of PFBS over the simulation time. The plots of this example are presented in Figure 85.

PFHxA Human PBK

Vassilis Minadakis
@vassilis_minadakis about 2 hours ago R_PBPk

Description Features Predict Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form or Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

BW* 82 **Remove** **Add value**

ingestion* ingestion 0 **Remove** **Add value**

ingestion_time* ingestion_time 0 **Remove** **Add value**

admin_dose* admin_dose 3.99 **Remove** **Add value**

admin_time* admin_time 0 **Remove** **Add value**

exp_type* bolus **Remove**

time_scale* days **Remove**

sim.start* 0 **Remove**

sim.end* 15 **Remove**

sim.step* 0.1 **Remove**

Submit

Figure 84. Prediction example from GUI using PFBS PBK model.

Figure 85. Concentration ($\mu\text{g/L}$) and mass (μg) of PFHxA in different compartments of the model applying the exposure scenario in Figure 84.

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3.7.12. Jaqpot Infrastructure: In vitro kinetics

The present model is an implementation of the in vitro toxicokinetics model presented in the publication of Fischer et al. (2017) entitled “Modeling Exposure in the Tox21 in Vitro Bioassays”. [10.1021/acs.chemrestox.7b00023]

This model is a steady-state mass balance model that predicts the free chemical concentrations in the medium, that is in equilibrium with the free cellular concentration, which is considered to be the driving force of biological activity. The structural model is presented in Figure 86.

Simulations of the mass balance model yield the free concentration at equilibrium by taking into account the partitioning between the different constituents of the assay. The model considers several parameters of the experimental assay as input (Table 82). Importantly, the user should provide the distribution coefficients between BSA (Bovine Serum Albumin) and water, as well as lipids and water. If these are not available, then the end-user should provide negative values for these two coefficients, and instead, provide the partition coefficients between BSA and water as well as lipids and water for both the neutral and the ion form of the chemical, as well as the pH of the medium and pKa of the chemical. Finally, the simulation is not dynamic, but the user is requested to provide a start and end point of the simulation time vector, as well as a time increment. Despite not being explicitly used, these parameters should follow the following rules: simulation start should be less than the simulation end, and the time increment should be positive.

Model outputs include the nominal and free concentrations, the fraction of chemical in the medium, free in medium and in cells (Table 83). A full description of the model structure and parameterization is available in Fischer et al. (2017). Figure 87 presents an input example through the model’s UI in the Jaqpot Platform.

The model is exposed as a ready to use web application on the Jaqpot platform (<https://app.jaqpot.org/dashboard/models/2302/description>). The R implementation of the model is available in a public GitHub repository (https://github.com/ntua-unit-of-control-and-informatics/PFAS_PBK_models).

Figure 86. Schematic representation of the in vitro toxicokinetics model presented in Fischer et al. (2017). The model estimates the free concentration in the medium and cells by taking into account partitioning to lipids and proteins in the cells and medium.

In Vitro Toxicokinetics Mass Balance Model

Periklis Tsiros @periklists 8 minutes ago R_PBPk

Description Features Predict Metrics Edit Discussion

Choose Your Prediction Input Method

Fill out the form or Upload a CSV file (max 100 rows)

<input type="radio"/> C_nominal *	<input type="radio"/> cells_per_well *	<input type="radio"/> cell_water_content *	<input type="radio"/> cell_protein_content *
10	1500	0.009	0.001
<input type="radio"/> cell_lipid_content *	<input type="radio"/> medium_protein_content *	<input type="radio"/> medium_lipid_content *	<input type="radio"/> serum_protein_content *
0.0003	0	0	0
<input type="radio"/> serum_lipid_content *	<input type="radio"/> serum_fraction *	<input type="radio"/> pKa *	<input type="radio"/> pH *
0	0	3.8	7.4
<input type="radio"/> log_D_bsa_w *	<input type="radio"/> log_D_lip_w *	<input type="radio"/> log_K_bsa_w_neutral *	<input type="radio"/> log_K_bsa_w_ion *
3.9	5	0	0
<input type="radio"/> log_K_lip_w_neutral *	<input type="radio"/> log_K_lip_w_ion *	<input type="radio"/> V_medium *	<input type="radio"/> sim.start *
0	0	100	0
<input type="radio"/> sim.end *	<input type="radio"/> sim.step *		
1	0		

Figure 87. Prediction tab of the in vitro toxicokinetics model.

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Table 82: In vitro toxicokinetics model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
C_nominal	μmol/L	Nominal Concentration
cells_per_well	-	Absolute number of cells per well
cell_water_content	mL per million cells	Water content of cells
cell_protein_content	mL per million cells	Protein content of cells
cell_lipid_content	mL per million cells	Lipid content of cells
medium_protein_content	mL/L	Protein content of medium
medium_lipid_content	mL/L	Lipid content of medium
serum_protein_content	mL/L	Protein content of serum
serum_lipid_content	mL/L	Lipid content of serum
serum_fraction	-	Fraction of serum
pKa	-	Negative logarithm of the acid dissociation constant
pH	-	pH of medium
log_D_bsa_w	-	Logarithm of BSA (Bovine Serum Albumin) to water distribution coefficient
log_D_lip_w	-	Logarithm of lipid to water distribution coefficient
log_K_bsa_w_neutral	-	Logarithm of BSA (Bovine Serum Albumin) to water partition coefficient of the neutral species
log_K_bsa_w_ion	-	Logarithm of BSA (Bovine Serum Albumin) to water partition coefficient of the ion species

log_K_lip_w_neutral	-	Logarithm of lipid to water partition coefficient of the neutral species
log_K_lip_w_ion	-	Logarithm of lipid to water partition coefficient of the ion species
V_medium	uL	Volume of medium
sim.start	h	Initial time point of simulation
sim.end	h	Final time point of simulation
sim.step	h	The integration step of simulation

Table 83: In vitro toxicokinetics model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
C_nominal	µmol/L	Nominal concentration
C_free	µmol/L	Free concentration in the medium at equilibrium
frac_ion	-	Fraction of chemical that is ionised at equilibrium
f_cell	-	Fraction of chemical in cells at equilibrium
f_free_medium	-	Fraction of chemicals that is free in the medium at equilibrium
f_medium	-	Fraction of chemical in the medium at equilibrium
time	hours	Simulation time

3.7.13. Accessing the Jaqpot services through the APIs

As noted earlier, all Jaqpot models are exposed through a unified API, enabling programmatic access from different computing environments. This section presents examples illustrating how to use these APIs. To access the services programmatically, users must have a Jaqpot account and install the Python package “jaqpot-python-sdk.” Every model deployed on Jaqpot has its own dedicated API endpoint, allowing users to submit data and obtain predictions directly through code.

The first example focuses on accessing the ML models for Aquatic Toxicity Prediction for predicting LC50 in fish. Figure 88 shows a Python code snippet demonstrating how to obtain predictions from the Jaqpot platform via its API. After loading the necessary environment variables (including API credentials), the script initializes a JaqpotApiClient instance. The input_data list contains the SMILES strings of two PFAS substances: PFOA and PFBS. These SMILES strings are submitted to the QSAR model using the predict_sync() function, together with the corresponding model identifier

(model_id=2183). The API returns predicted LC₅₀ values for each chemical along with associated metadata, such as APD information.

Figure 89 shows the output generated by the Python script after querying the Fish LC₅₀ QSAR model through the Japlot API. The response consists of a list of prediction objects—one for each submitted chemical. Each object contains the predicted LC₅₀ value (y) together with a detailed set of metadata provided under `jaqpotMetadata`. This includes APD metrics (`doa`), the leverage value (`h`) indicating how similar the chemical is to the model's training data, and the corresponding threshold values used for domain assessment. The metadata also specifies whether the chemical falls within the APD (`inDoa`), the outcome of the majority voting procedure for ensemble-based predictions (`majorityVoting`), and an internal identifier for the returned record (`jaqpotRowId`). This output demonstrates how the API provides not only the predicted toxicity value but also rich contextual information describing the reliability of each prediction—information that is essential for interpreting QSAR results and determining whether the model is being applied within its valid chemical space.


```

Fish_LC50_Predictions.py 1 x
Fish_LC50_Predictions.py > ...
1  from dotenv import load_dotenv
2
3  load_dotenv(".env") # Returns True if successful
4
5  from jaqpot_python_sdk.jaqpot_api_client import JaqpotApiClient
6
7  jaqpot_api_client = JaqpotApiClient()
8
9  input_data = [
10     {"smiles": "C(=O)C(C(C(C(C(C(C(F)(F)(F)(F)(F)(F)(F)(F)(F)(F)(F)(F)O)", # PFOA
11     {"smiles": "C(C(C(F)(F)S(=O)(=O)O)(F)(C(F)(F)(F)(F)O)", # PFBS
12 ]
13 prediction = jaqpot_api_client.predict_sync(model_id=2183, dataset=input_data)
14 print(prediction)
15
  
```

Figure 88. Example of how to access the models for aquatic toxicity prediction through the Japlot APIs.


```

python /Users/vassilis/Documents/GitHub/test_jaqpot_sdk/test_python_sdk.py
[{'y': 2.0689759254455566, 'jaqpotMetadata': {'doa': {'Leverage': {'h': 0.020586699122221375, 'hStar': 0.21265243902439024, 'inDoa': True}, 'majorityVoting': True}, 'jaqpotRowId': 0.0}}, {'y': 2.0689759254455566, 'jaqpotMetadata': {'doa': {'Leverage': {'h': 0.020586699122221375, 'hStar': 0.21265243902439024, 'inDoa': True}, 'majorityVoting': True}, 'jaqpotRowId': 1.0}}]
  
```

Figure 89. Predicted LC₅₀ values generated via calls to Japlot APIs.

The second example demonstrates how to access the PFHxA PBK model through its API, as shown in Figure 90. The figure presents a Python code snippet that uses the *jaqpot-python-sdk* to execute the PFHxA PBK model programmatically. After loading the necessary environment variables, including API credentials, the script initializes a *JaqpotApiClient* and prepares the required *input_data* dictionary containing all parameters defining the exposure scenario, such as body weight, ingestion settings, administration dose, exposure type, time scale, and simulation duration. The configured input dataset is then submitted to the model using the *predict_sync()* function together with the corresponding *model_id*. This programmatic workflow allows users to reproduce the same PBK simulation provided through the Jaqpot GUI, enabling seamless integration into computational pipelines and automated analyses.

The resulting plots are presented in Figure 91. The plots illustrate the simulated concentration–time (top) and mass–time (bottom) profiles for PFHxA across all modelled compartments. Each curve represents the predicted concentration or mass of PFHxA in a specific tissue or compartment over the 15-day simulation period, demonstrating how the substance distributes and clears within the human body. The results produced programmatically are identical to those generated via the Jaqpot graphical interface.


```

PFHxA_PBK_SDK.py 3 x
PFHxA_PBK_SDK.py > ...
1  from dotenv import load_dotenv
2
3  load_dotenv(".env") # Returns True if successful
4
5  from jaqpot_python_sdk.jaqpot_api_client import JaqpotApiClient
6  import pandas as pd
7  import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
8
9  jaqpot_api_client = JaqpotApiClient()
10
11 input_data = [
12     {
13         "BW": 82,
14         "ingestion": 0,
15         "ingestion_time": 0,
16         "admin_dose": 3.99,
17         "admin_time": 0,
18         "exp_type": "bolus",
19         "time_scale": "days",
20         "sim.start": 0,
21         "sim.end": 15,
22         "sim.step": 0.1,
23     }
24 ]
25 prediction = jaqpot_api_client.predict_sync(model_id=2303, dataset=input_data)

```

Figure 90. Example of how to access the PFHxA Human PBK model through the Jaqpot APIs.

Figure 91. Predicted PFHxA concentrations and masses over time generated via calls to Jaqpot APIs.

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4. Integration of External tools

4.1. Jaqpot Infrastructure: Integration of QSAR toolbox

The OECD QSAR Toolbox is a freely available software application developed to support the hazard assessment of chemicals. It is designed to enhance the mechanistic understanding of chemical substances in a cost-effective and scientifically robust manner. Key features of the Toolbox include:

- Grouping of chemicals into categories based on structural, mechanistic, and empirical data.
- Support for read-across and category-based approaches to fill data gaps.
- Integration of various (eco)toxicity datasets and predictive models.
- Simulation tools for metabolism and biotransformation.

These capabilities make the Toolbox particularly valuable in regulatory, academic, and industrial contexts where chemical safety assessment is required. The development of the QSAR Toolbox is a collaborative effort involving the ECHA, the OECD, OECD member and partner countries, as well as the broader QSAR community. The Toolbox is co-owned by the OECD and ECHA, and its continued development is overseen by the QSAR Toolbox Coordination Group, which includes ECHA, the OECD, and the primary developer—the Laboratory of Mathematical Chemistry (LMC). Through this interdisciplinary collaboration, the OECD QSAR Toolbox has become a key global resource supporting robust chemical hazard assessments. It incorporates hundreds of predictive models addressing a wide range of endpoints and indicators related to human and environmental hazards, including many of the indicators identified as critical in the SSbD framework.

Contributors to the QSAR Toolbox's predictive capabilities include widely recognized sources such as VEGA⁶, ECOSAR⁷, EPISUITE⁸ and the Danish (Q)SAR database⁹. A graphical representation of the different models and end-points that are accessible through the QSAR toolbox is provided in Figure 92 and the full list of the 311 QSAR models, 80 profilers and 151 calculators are listed in Appendices A1, A2, A3.

⁶ <https://www.vegahub.eu/portfolio-item/vega-qsar/>

⁷ <https://www.epa.gov/tsca-screening-tools/ecological-structure-activity-relationships-ecosar-predictive-model>

⁸ <https://www.epa.gov/tsca-screening-tools/epi-suitetm-estimation-program-interface>

⁹ <https://qsar.food.dtu.dk/>

Figure 92. QSAR Toolbox - Graph of endpoint tree.

The QSAR Toolbox API has been integrated by NTUA into the Jaqpot platform, with Swagger documentation available at <http://54.155.131.85/swagger/index.html>. A screenshot of the available APIs is provided in Fig. 93. The integration includes all QSAR models and profilers. This implementation provides great flexibility, as it allows users to receive results directly through the Jaqpot API, via the Jaqpot SDK - which enables easy programmatic access and integration into computational workflows -, or through the Jaqpot GUI. By making direct calls to the QSAR Toolbox API, users can also obtain additional information, including the complete data, metadata, and predictions generated by the QSAR Toolbox API. One of the most important features of the Jaqpot implementation is that it allows multiple

operations to be executed within a single API call. This capability streamlines the workflow by enabling users to submit a SMILES representation and simultaneously request several predictions without the need for multiple sequential requests. As a result, the system improves both efficiency and usability, particularly when performing large-scale batch processing or integrating predictive workflows into automated pipelines.

Figure 93. QSAR Toolbox - Graph of endpoint tree

The following example demonstrates the flexibility of the service by showing how to call the VEGA-ready bioavailability model to predict this property for the nicotine molecule using the SMILES string CN1CCC[C@H]1C2=CN=CC=C2.

Receiving the predictions through an API call: Figure 94 shows how the API call is structured in the Swagger documentation of the QSAR Toolbox API, and Figure 95 presents a screenshot of the API response.

Figure 94. An example of a call to the QSAR toolbox API

```
Request URL
http://54.155.131.85/api/v6/qsar/apply/72dd9f8c-dd69-41b5-854c-1aa422a6e371/951cf7f5-3878-cf86-8373-79416a532f90

Server response
Code Details
200
Response body
{"DomainExplain": null,
"DataType": "Qsar prediction.",
"RigidPath": "Environmental Fate and Transport#Biodegradation#in water: Screening Tests",
"Endpoint": "Ready Biodegradability",
"Metadata": [
"VEGA original prediction=Possible Readily Biodegradable",
"VEGA experimental (if found)",
"VEGA reliability class=LOW reliability",
"VEGA Assessment=Possible Readily Biodegradable (LOW reliability)",
"Domain-Out of domain (VEGA - Ready Biodegradability model (IRFMN))",
"Endpoint=Ready Biodegradability",
"Test organisms (species)=Activated sludge (according to OECD 301C Modified MITI (I) Test).",
"Endpoint comment=Ready biodegradability tests are screening tests in with a high concentration of the test substance is used and ultimate bio degradation is measured by non-specific parameters under aerobic conditions. In the OECD 301C Modified MITI (I) test, a substance can be considered ready biodegradable if 60% of the substance is mineralized in 28 days (in terms of ThOD)",
"Assay provider=For the development and testing of the model the datasets was extracted from the OECD QSAR toolbox v 2.0 and from the BIOWIN 5 and 6 models (in EPIsuiteTM) and then combined (see ref. 1, section 9.2). The dataset is described in ref 2 (section 9.2). To validate the model data were extracted from Cheng et al., 2012 (see ref 3, section 9.2). 17 compounds were found with non-concordant data among the OECD QSAR toolbox v 2.0 and the BIOWIN 5 and 6 models (i.e. not classified in the same class: Ready Biodegradable or Not-Ready Biodegradable) and were excluded. All the common data with Cheng et al., 2012 were eliminated and not checked to verify non-concordant data because the data from Cheng et al 2012 were used only as external validation set.",
"Test guideline=OECD 301C Modified MITI (I) Test. It Measures The Oxygen Uptake in A Period of 28 Days of A Solution of The Substance Inoculated With Activated Sludge Under Aerobic Conditions C.f. OECD TG 301 (5)",
"Reference=[1] Lombardo A, Pizzo F, Benfenati E, Manganaro A, Ferrari T, Gini G (2014). A new in silico classification model for ready biodegradability, based on molecular fragments. Chemosphere. 103:10-16 http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.02.073 [2] Benfenati E, Manganaro A, Gini G. VEGA-QSAR: AI inside a platform for predictive toxicology Proceedings of the workshop 'Popularize Artificial Intelligence 2013', December 5th 2013, Turin, Italy Published on CEUR Workshop Proceedings Vol-1107",
"Reference Link=10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.02.073",
"SAR/(Q)SAR=VEGA - Ready Biodegradability model (IRFMN) (v1.0)",
"Endpoint=Ready Biodegradability (IRFMN) (v1.0)"}]
```

Figure 95. An example of a response from the QSAR toolbox API

The response provides the QSAR prediction for the Ready Biodegradability of the compound *nicotine* with additional information that includes:

- Prediction Result: *Possible Readily Biodegradable*
- Domain Status: *Out of Domain* (the substance falls outside the model's APD)
- Data Type: QSAR prediction
- Endpoint: Ready Biodegradability (OECD 301C Modified MITI (I) Test)
- Model Used: VEGA Ready Biodegradability model (IRFMN)
- Reliability: *Low reliability*, as reported by VEGA
- Metadata:
 - Original VEGA prediction and assessment
 - Test organism and guideline
 - Background on dataset construction and model validation
 - Supporting references and description of the assay
- Chemical Information:
 - Substance name(s) and synonyms (nicotine)
 - Chemical identifier (ChemId)

Receiving the predictions through the Japrot SDK:

The following command shows how the model can be executed from a programming environment, for example within a Jupyter or Colab notebook:

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```
# This is the string that corresponds to the VEGA ReadyBiodegradability
model
ready_biodeg_model = "72dd9f8c-dd69-41b5-854c-1aa422a6e371"
# Get the QSAR Ready biodegradability prediction with sdk
prediction = jaqpot_api_client.qsartoolbox_qsar_model_predict_sync(
    smiles="CN1CCC[C@H]1C2=CN=CC=C2",
    qsar_guid=ready_biodeg_model,
)[0]
```

This is the response, which includes the prediction and all additional information mentioned earlier as returned by the API call. :

```
{'DomainResult': 'OutOfDomain',
'DataType': 'Qsar prediction.',
'RigidPath': 'Environmental Fate and Transport#Biodegradation#in water: Screening Tests',
'Endpoint': 'Ready Biodegradability',
'MetaData': ['VEGA original prediction=Possible Readily Biodegradable',
'VEGA experimental (if found)=',
'VEGA reliability class=LOW reliability',
'VEGA Assessment=Possible Readily Biodegradable (LOW reliability)',
'Domain=Out of domain (VEGA - Ready Biodegradability model (IRFMN))',
'Endpoint=Ready Biodegradability',
'Test organisms (species)=Activated sludge (according to OECD 301C Modified MITI (I) Test).',
'Endpoint comment=Ready biodegradability tests are screening tests in with a high concentration of the
test substance is used and ultimate bio degradation is measured by non-specific parameters under aerobic
conditions. In the OECD 301C Modified MITI (I) test, a substance can be considered ready biodegradable
if 60% of the substance is mineralized in 28 days (in terms of ThOD)',
'Assay provider=For the development and testing of the model the datasets was extracted from the OECD
QSAR toolbox v 2.0 and from the BIOWIN 5 and 6 models (in EPISuiteTM) and then combined (see ref. 1,
section 9.2). The dataset is described in ref 2 (section 9.2). To validate the model data were extracted from
Cheng et al., 2012 (see ref 3, section 9.2). 17 compounds were found with non-concordant data among the
OECD QSAR toolbox v 2.0 and the BIOWIN 5 and 6 models (i.e. not classified in the same class: Ready
Biodegradable or Not-Ready Biodegradable) and were excluded. All the common data with Cheng et al.,
2012 were eliminated and not checked to verify non-concordant data because the data from Cheng et al
2012 were used only as external validation set.',
'Test guideline=OECD 301C Modified MITI (I) Test. It Measures The Oxygen Uptake in A Period of 28
Days of A Solution of The Substance Inoculated With Activated Sludge Under Aerobic Conditions C.f.
OECD TG 301 (5)']
```



```
'Reference=[1] Lombardo A, Pizzo F, Benfenati E, Manganaro A, Ferrari T, Gini G (2014). A new in silico
classification model for ready biodegradability, based on molecular fragments. Chemosphere. 108,10–16
http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.02.073 [2] Benfenati E, Manganaro A, Gini G. VEGA-QSAR:
AI inside a platform for predictive toxicology Proceedings of the workshop "Popularize Artificial Intelligence
2013", December 5th 2013, Turin, Italy Published on CEUR Workshop Proceedings Vol-1107',
'Reference Link=10.1016/j.chemosphere.2014.02.073',
'SAR/(Q)SAR=VEGA - Ready Biodegradability model (IRFMN) (v1.0)',
'Domain status=Out of domain',
'Primary group=N/A',
'Primary group with metabolism=N/A',
'Prediction approach=QSAR',
'Value': 'Possible Readily Biodegradable',
'Name': '(-)-3-(1-Methyl-2-pyrrolidyl)pyridine\n,      3-(1-Methyl-pyrrolidin-2-yl)-pyridine,      3-(1-
methylpyrrolidin-2-yl)pyridine,      3-[(2s)-1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinyl]pyridine,      3-[(2S)-1-methylpyrrolidin-2-
yl]pyridine, Nicotine, Nicotineanditssalts, Pyridine, 3-[(2S)-1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinyl]-',
'ChemId': '951cf7f5-3878-cf86-8373-79416a532f90',
'jaqpotMetadata': {'jaqpotRowId': '0'}}
```

Receiving the predictions through the Jaqpot API:

The screenshot in Figure 96 shows how the end-user can invoke the model through the Jaqpot GUI to obtain predictions and additional information, such as the APD of the prediction.:

A Smiles representation	QSAR Model	Value	Unit	Endpoint	Donator	DomainResult	Name
CNCCCC[C@H]1C2=CN=CC=C2	VEGA - Ready Biodegradability model (IRF MN)	Possible Readily Biodegradable		Ready Biodegradability		OutOfDomain	(-)-3-(1-Methyl-2-pyrrolidyl)pyridine, 3-(1-Methyl-pyrrolidin-2-yl)-pyridine, 3-(1-methylpyrrolidin-2-yl)pyridine, 3-[(2s)-1-methyl-2-p...

Figure 96. An example of a response from the QSAR toolbox GUI in Jaqpot

4.2. Enalos Cloud Platform: MicroPlasticFate

The **MicroPlasticFate** web application (<https://www.enaloscloud.novamechanics.com/EnalosWebApps/MicroPlasticFate/>) is a user-friendly web tool, developed to simulate the fate and behaviour of nano- and microplastics (NMPs) in diverse environmental media/compartments through a GUI (Figure 97). This application replicates the core features of the SimpleBox4Plastic (SB4P) multimedia environmental fate model (Quik et al., 2023). It enables users to model the fate and transport of NMPs across multiple environmental scales, including regional, continental and global scale, each of which consists of compartments/media of air, soil, water and sediment. MicroPlasticFate integrates functionalities for in-depth exploration of the environmental persistence of three widely used plastics (Polypropylene (PP), Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) and Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE)) which do not exist as predefined substances in SB4P. Moreover, the web application offers the examination of the fate factors ($FF_{i,j}$) of NMPs that represent the increase of a substance mass in environmental compartment i due to emissions in compartment j (measured in days). MicroPlasticFate web application also features the computation of the proportion of a given substance's volume within a specified compartment at steady-state, providing a comprehensive understanding of NMPs distribution patterns. More information can be found in the work of Papavasiliou et al., 2025.

Figure 97: MicroPlasticFate GUI.

Table 84: MicroPlasticFate model inputs.

Name	Units	Description
Substance	-	Predefined substances including polypropylene (PP), polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and low-density polyethylene (LDPE)
Emission scenario	-	Predefined emissions scenarios including EUSES settings, Thames Catchment 2000 etc.
Radius Primary ENP	nm	Radius size (in nm) of engineered nano-particles
Density primary ENP	kg.m ⁻³	Density of engineered nano-particles
Hamaker constant	J	Hamaker constant for a heteroagglomerate that describe the inter-molecular van der Waals interactions between NPs
Molecular Weight	g.mol ⁻¹	Molecular weight of a substance

Table 85: MicroPlasticFate model outputs.

Name	Units	Description
Steady-State Results	-	A grid output of the steady-state masses (kg) and concentration (g.L ⁻¹) of the emitted substances across air, water, soil and sediment compartments on the regional, continental and global environmental scale
Particle Volume Ratio	%	Particle volume coverage in selected compartment expressed as %
Fate Factor	days	Fate Factor expressed in days for a substance being emitted on the continental scale

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4.3. INSIGHT LCA REST API

The INSIGHT LCA API (version 0.0.5, OpenAPI 3.1.0) is a REST interface designed to expose computational capabilities of Brightway-based life cycle assessment (LCA) systems. It provides endpoints for project discovery, LCIA method retrieval, dataset search, and the execution of both social and environmental LCAs. Although functionally coherent, the current specification remains an early-stage prototype.

General Overview

The API presents a minimalistic yet coherent structure. All operations are exposed as HTTP GET requests and return JSON-formatted responses that will be matched with the ontologies developed in the project. The endpoints allow users to query available projects, retrieve methods, search datasets, and perform LCA calculations for specified nodes. Authentication scheme is currently foreseen, to be deployed with a sign-on by users through OpenID (i.e. based on keycloak technology).

Functional Description

The root endpoint ('/') serves as a basic entry point providing version information and general API metadata. The '/projects' endpoint returns the list of all Brightway projects accessible through the API, forming the starting point for exploration. Each project can be further queried via the '/lciamethods/{project}' endpoint to obtain the available LCIA methods, typically including standard methods such as Environmental Footprint (EF v3.1) and USEtox v2.13. The '/projects/{project}/search' endpoint allows for keyword-based searches within a project, facilitating dataset discovery.

The computational layer is represented by two endpoints: '/slca/{project}/{node_id}' and '/lca/{project}/{node_id}'. The first executes a social life cycle assessment (sLCA) for a given node within the project graph, while the latter performs an environmental LCA using the EF and USEtox methods.

Future iterations should prioritize defining formal JSON schemas for each endpoint, incorporating example responses, and specifying authentication mechanisms. Once stabilized, this API could serve as a foundational component for open and reproducible LCA workflows in research and policy analysis.

The current deployment of the API is available to project partners at the following URL: <https://insight.list.lu> .

Table 86: Summary Table of Endpoints.

Endpoint	Parameters	Purpose	Expected Output
/ (root endpoint of the API)	None	Return API version and metadata	JSON object with version info
/projects	None	List available Brightway projects	Array of project identifiers
/lciamethods/{project}	project (string)	Retrieve LCIA methods for a project	Array of LCIA method descriptors
/projects/{project}/search	project (string), search_criterion (string)	Search datasets within a project	List of matching dataset entries
/slca/{project}/{node_id}	project (string), node_id (integer)	Perform social LCA on a node	Social impact results per category
/lca/{project}/{node_id}	project (string), node_id (integer)	Perform environmental LCA on a node	Environmental impact results (EF v3.1, USEtox v2.13)

The REST API has been developed using the open-api specification and provides a user interface to it through the url <https://insight.list.lu/docs>.

With this interface, we can explore the different endpoints already, with “prototype” inventories.

The following figure (Figure 98) provides a screenshot of the deployment of the REST API.

INSIGHT LCA API 0.0.5 OAS 3.1

/openapi.json

projects
provides the list of projects in the bw instance.

lciamethods/{project}
provides the list of supported LCIA methods of a given project.

projects/{project}/search
allows to look for a specific dataset in a project

slca/{project}/{node_id}
do the social lca of a node

lca/{project}/{node_id}
do the environmental lca of a node using EF v3.1 and USEtox v2.13 methods

default

- GET / Read Root
- GET /projects Read Projects
- GET /lciamethods/{project} Read Methods
- GET /projects/{project}/search Search
- GET /slca/{project}/{node_id} Do Social Lca
- GET /lca/{project}/{node_id} Do Social Lca

Figure 98. Example queries and results for S-LCA and LCA.

The social LCA endpoint for an inventory in the databases from the REST API can be queried through: <http://insight.list.lu/slca/ecoinvent310/244807616517849088>

The provided social risk impact assessment as calculated with the Social Weighting Impact method would look as follows:

Request URL
<http://0.0.0.0:8000/slca/ecoinvent310/244807616517849088>

Server response

Code	Details
200	<p>Response body</p> <pre> Methodology: "Social Impacts Weighting", "Category": "Active involvement of enterprises in corruption and bribery", "Indicator": "Active involvement of enterprises in corruption and bribery", "Score": -61.377517618286916, "unit": "AI med risk hours", "method namespace": "soca-3.10-cutoff" }, { "Activity": "Graphene oxide production", "production amount": null, "Activity unit": "kilogram", "reference product": "Graphene oxide", "Methodology": "Social Impacts Weighting", "Category": "Anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation", "Indicator": "Anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation", "Score": -458.7795851451104, "unit": "AC med risk hours", "method namespace": "soca-3.10-cutoff" }, { "Activity": "Graphene oxide production", "production amount": null, "Activity unit": "kilogram", "reference product": "Graphene oxide", "Methodology": "Social Impacts Weighting", "Category": "Anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation", "Indicator": "Anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation", "Score": -458.7795851451104, "unit": "AC med risk hours", "method namespace": "soca-3.10-cutoff" } } </pre> <p>Response headers</p> <pre> content-length: 18979 content-type: application/json date: Mon, 10 Nov 2025 12:43:55 GMT server: uvicorn </pre>

Responses

Code	Description	Links
200	Successful Response	No links

Media type

Controls Accept header.

Example Value | Schema

Figure 99. Sample output of the S-LCA assessment of the INSIGHT LCA API

The endpoint returns a social life cycle assessment (sLCA) profile for a single activity node in a database inside the project. The node with internal identifier 244807616517849088 is resolved to the activity “Graphene oxide production” with the reference product “Graphene oxide” and an activity unit of “kilogram”. The response consists of a JSON array, where each element represents one characterized social indicator associated with this activity, calculated per functional unit of the activity (here implicitly one kilogram of graphene oxide, as defined by the activity’s reference flow).

Each entry in the array contains the same contextual information about the foreground activity, including the activity name, activity unit, and reference product, as well as the applied social assessment method (“Social Impacts Weighting”). The field method namespace documents the specific implementation context, in this case soca-3.10-cutoff, indicating that the results are derived from a social LCA model coupled to the ecoinvent 3.10 cut-off system. The core variation across records lies in the pair Category and Indicator, which together identify the social theme being assessed (for example “Child Labour, female”, “Fair Salary”, “Trade unionism”, “Public sector corruption”, “GHG Footprints”, “Health expenditure”, “Sanitation coverage”, among others).

For each of these social indicators, the API provides a numerical Score and its corresponding unit. The units take the form of “med risk hours” with an indicator-specific prefix (e.g. “CL med risk hours” for child labour, “FS med risk hours” for fair salary, “GHGF med risk hours” for greenhouse gas footprints), reflecting a risk-based, time-normalised characterization metric. The Score quantifies the potential social risk or performance associated with the supply chain of the specified activity for the given indicator. Positive and negative values are both present in the example, indicating that the underlying method distinguishes between relatively better and worse performance or risk levels compared to a reference situation; the exact sign convention and interpretation are determined by the underlying “Social Impacts Weighting” method, but from the output it is evident that the result is a vector of characterized social indicators rather than raw inventory data.

As for the environmental LCA, the endpoint to query would be: <https://insight.list.lu/lca/ecoinvent310/244807616517849088>

The following figure (Figure 100) provides a graphical view of the answer to the query.

→ insight.list.lu/docs#/default/do_env_lca_lca_project__node_id_get ☆ ▼

Responses

Curl

```
curl -X 'GET' \
  'https://insight.list.lu/lca/ecoinvent310/244807616517849088' \
  -H 'accept: application/json'
```

Request URL

```
https://insight.list.lu/lca/ecoinvent310/244807616517849088
```

Server response

Code	Details
200	<p>Response body</p> <pre>[{"method namespace": "ecoinvent-3.10", "Activity": "Graphene oxide production", "production amount": null, "Activity unit": "kilogram", "reference product": "Graphene oxide", "Methodology": "EF v3.1", "Category": "climate change", "Indicator": "global warming potential (GWP100)", "Score": -452.09522043960004, "unit": "kg CO2-Eq", "method namespace": "ecoinvent-3.10"}, {"method namespace": "ecoinvent-3.10", "Activity": "Graphene oxide production", "production amount": null, "Activity unit": "kilogram", "reference product": "Graphene oxide", "Methodology": "EF v3.1", "Category": "climate change: biogenic", "Indicator": "global warming potential (GWP100)", "Score": -0.02761758559585238, "unit": "kg CO2-Eq", "method namespace": "ecoinvent-3.10"}]</pre> <p>Response headers</p> <pre>connection: keep-alive content-length: 12494 content-security-policy: upgrade-insecure-requests content-type: application/json date: Mon, 10 Nov 2025 13:41:35 GMT strict-transport-security: max-age=16070400; includeSubDomains x-content-type-options: nosniff x-frame-options: SAMEORIGIN x-xss-protection: 1; mode=block</pre>

Figure I00. Sample output of the environmental LCA done with the LCA API.

The previous query returns an environmental life cycle impact assessment profile for a single activity node in the project. The node with internal identifier 244807616517849088 is resolved to the activity “Graphene oxide production” with the reference product “Graphene oxide” and an activity unit of “kilogram”. The response is similar to the social LCA, a JSON array.

For all entries, the foreground context fields (Activity, Activity unit, reference product) are constant, while the fields Methodology, Category, Indicator, Score, unit, and method namespace vary. Two LCIA method families are applied: EF v3.1 and USEtox v2.13. For EF v3.1, the results cover a broad set of midpoint impact categories, including acidification (“accumulated exceedance (AE)”, mol H⁺-eq), several climate change variants (total, biogenic, fossil, and land-use-related, all reported as GWPI100 in kg CO₂-eq), ecotoxicity freshwater (CTUe, split into inorganics and organics), eutrophication in freshwater, marine and terrestrial compartments (kg P-eq, kg N-eq, mol N-eq), human toxicity (carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic, and their inorganic/organic partitions, in CTUh), ionising radiation (kBq U-235-eq), land use (dimensionless soil quality index), material and energy resource use (e.g. abiotic depletion of metals/minerals in kg Sb-eq and fossil fuel depletion in MJ), ozone depletion (kg CFC-11-eq), particulate matter formation (disease incidence), photochemical oxidant formation (kg NMVOC-eq), and water use (m³ world-equivalent deprived).

In addition, the response includes midpoint and endpoint results from USEtox v2.13, with and without long-term (LT) fate included. Endpoint indicators quantify “ecosystem quality” (freshwater ecotoxicity) in PDF m³ yr and “human health” (carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic toxicity) in DALYs. Midpoint indicators report the corresponding toxic potentials in CTUe (ecosystems) and CTUh (humans), again with and without long-term contributions, using specific category labels such as “ecotoxicity: freshwater”, “human toxicity: carcinogenic”, and “human toxicity: non-carcinogenic”.

5. Conclusions - Future actions

The present deliverable builds upon the initial gap analysis conducted in the previous reporting period and demonstrates substantial progress in strengthening the modelling framework that underpins the INSIGHT model graph. Many of the gaps previously identified - across modelling capabilities, impact coverage, and SSbD indicator alignment - have now been partially or fully addressed through the expansion of the tool inventory and the integration of additional internal and external models.

A key improvement introduced in this deliverable is the standardised and explicit definition of inputs and outputs for each model, both for use through the GUIs and through the APIs. This harmonised documentation ensures that model behaviour, data requirements, and expected outputs are transparent and machine-readable, enabling both human users and automated systems to interact with the models consistently.

Access through both the GUI and APIs significantly enhances scalability and interoperability. Non-technical users can run models intuitively through the GUI, while computational scientists and developers can integrate the same models programmatically into pipelines and external workflows using the APIs. This dual-access structure supports complex multi-model workflows, automated high-throughput analysis, and seamless incorporation into the evolving INSIGHT knowledge graph.

In terms of modelling coverage, the INSIGHT model graph incorporates tools for exposure assessment, PBK modelling, environmental fate analysis, toxicogenomics, QSAR prediction models, hazard-assessment approaches, and social and environmental LCA. At the impact level, the INSIGHT modeling ecosystem addresses the health, environmental and social impacts, feeding the relevant IOPs within the INSIGHT SSbD framework.

Future work will focus on expanding the INSIGHT model graph through the integration and development of additional models to address gaps identified during the implementation of the INSIGHT case studies. As the PFAS, graphene-based materials, silica materials, and antimicrobial case studies progress, new requirements for hazard, exposure, sustainability, and socioeconomic assessment will emerge. These needs will guide the incorporation of new models that enhance coverage of SSbD indicators and strengthen the flow of information into the IOP knowledge graph.

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ANNEX A1 – QSAR models from QSAR Toolbox

	key	Endpoint
1	111bb39c-c97c-4f54-b1de-327a230a8a0c	Water Solubility (fragments) (EPISUITE)
2	c8055d19-f4f0-4de9-8a5d-558d56d3b593	VEGA - Water solubility model (IRFMN)
3	a622f86b-c8db-4bcf-8a2e-af849bd1aa2e	Water Solubility (EPISUITE)
4	0fc38150-da93-4cb5-be5c-199d6c5b8944	(Q) Acidic pKa (Chemaxon)
5	f6aec718-ec82-4acb-96a9-7eeb6bdc2a10	Basic pKa (OASIS Regression)
6	b55d4312-7982-4fec-9f78-ce7c03e83252	Acidic pKa (OASIS Consensus)
7	a05eaaa2-958c-4135-872f-041145d2a2a4	Acidic pKa (OASIS Regression)
8	eefcdc4e-242c-4083-8fb2-f76efe87a5a8	Acidic pKa (OASIS Electric)
9	c377150b-77ae-4f99-be14-357b85dd8d1f	(Q) Basic pKa (Chemaxon)
10	5f7a33c0-b694-4265-9fd5-ef0ba5e47d9d	Amino acids pKa (OASIS Regression)
11	af9e50f6-2095-4a4b-aab9-9218d491a705	Impact sensitivity of nitroaliphatic compounds
12	e2968688-dd4d-4b27-a603-56f83449b3a3	Selected Vapor Pressure (EPISUITE)
13	c6177a62-f75b-4a1d-a69d-1e078b4109f0	Subcooled liquid Vapor Pressure (EPISUITE)
14	567d4df5-9979-4ae6-909b-120347ddf7f5	Vapor Pressure (Mackay Method) (EPISUITE)
15	185c398c-22cc-4577-bd1a-a6ce6c81d0b6	VEGA - Vapour Pressure (CONCERT/Kode)
16	382389d0-ac69-4543-b69b-f65040d941e1	Vapor Pressure (Antoine Method) (EPISUITE)
17	6bfe3c72-dff2-4e37-b5a1-ffa9a1a111d1	Vapor Pressure (Modified Grain Method) (EPISUITE)
18	e898dfa3-28ac-4a89-9032-deff475db152	Boiling Point Adapted Stein and Brown Method (EPISUITE)
19	aaea1ad1-a0db-1fb2-290a-6b5f52f049b2	ECOSAR: EARTHWORM 14 d LC50 Mortality
20	68f2567f-71db-478e-adf6-39360aa00f59	VEGA - Bee acute toxicity model (KNN-IRFMN)
21	616f7a34-2fcd-4623-91de-d2a1c17c9122	VEGA - Earthworm Toxicity (CONCERT)
22	e5271d1b-910a-4e7a-a4c2-31225ff2d9b7	VEGA - Sludge Classification Toxicity model (ProtoQSAR-Combase)

23	127eb543-2408-4a9b-b110-7456918279e7	VEGA - Sludge (EC50) Toxicity model (ProtoQSAR-Combase)
24	41927145-a60e-4b32-a201-a220411c4d06	VEGA - Fish Acute (LC50) Toxicity model (IRFMN)
25	5e9d7a1e-b0dc-4eb7-a8c0-622cc97c1758	VEGA - Algae Acute (EC50) Toxicity model (IRFMN)
26	26cb5dca-78d8-dc9b-0007-373280b78019	ECOSAR: GREEN ALGAE ChV
27	934036e4-c346-4aca-aec3-dc3ae1c85980	VEGA - Fish Acute (LC50) Toxicity model (NIC)
28	b3d3b207-cef1-fb5b-4a44-60d5371e413c	ECOSAR: DAPHNIA ChV
29	2c81aac2-5fb7-415b-bffe-8d9ed85a4e49	VEGA - MOA pesticide classification (IRFMN)
30	c0480dd9-3959-1866-5a3c-19b21c905034	ECOSAR: FISH ChV
31	9c92bfa8-a740-4feb-ac9f-c6a8aa3c430c	Daphnia magna 48h EC50 - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
32	1fecb43b-6a02-4d85-96c9-c06b339e8ab7	M1 - LC50 - Pimephales promelas (fathead minnow)
33	894921a0-0a35-e50c-071d-e56f257cb590	ECOSAR: MYSID (SW) 96 h LC50 Mortality
34	f1ca5092-2653-493a-8424-bf2a1225ed43	VEGA - Zebrafish embryo AC50 (IRFMN-CORAL)
35	ee50b7da-3007-4f22-8e15-48af6cfc3a8	ECOSAR: ALGAE ChV
36	e213c53b-7e92-4807-9deb-edadc4f98b2f	VEGA - Fish Acute (LC50) Toxicity model (KNN-Read-Across)
37	e6a7660e-900d-83be-6479-58cd31e025b1	ECOSAR: DAPHNIA 48 h LC50 Mortality
38	1c88a6a2-f966-243e-158f-7aaf5020879b	ECOSAR: GREEN ALGAE 96 h EC50 Growth
39	4625dd91-fea6-4925-aa2c-70ef3c998b28	KATE2020 - Algae 72h EC50
40	96cb4fe7-bc6d-4bb8-930f-df1a20cc145b	VEGA - Daphnia Magna Chronic (NOEC) Toxicity model (IRFMN)
41	eb9d9e00-5df0-4d19-9f4d-40f5fe5341d9	VEGA - Daphnia Magna Acute (EC50) Toxicity model (IRFMN-Combase)
42	c9a2de76-9ea1-b587-6ca7-2946b6689f27	ECOSAR: INVERTEBRATE ChV

43	8cfbfd07-c7b7-cccc-2ad0-c25ca0a3d55a	ECOSAR: INVERTEBRATES (SW) 96 h LC50 Mortality
44	a31d4e97-0a1c-4cbc-bd62-10e9d72c5888	KATE2020 - Fish 96h LC50
45	b9e0dc6e-7e44-7ef7-69f0-985a37221f15	ECOSAR: MYSID 96 h LC50 Mortality
46	6ece9151-0207-441c-8862-bd3abb5cf8c7	VEGA - Daphnia Magna Acute (EC50) Toxicity model (IRFMN)
47	cdefd3f3-5bb4-4285-a302-a1b424521b7b	Photoinduced toxicity of PAHs
48	af3551f8-0257-8ed1-a0e7-d3d46cf6b4c5	ECOSAR: MYSID SHRIMP 96 h LC50 Mortality
49	1b658b5c-8d2f-fdd3-e5a0-4d1d5c76cda8	ECOSAR: LEMNA GIBBA 96 h EC50
50	eaecae22-11d4-403f-aaf4-db7020633c86	Daphnia magna 48h EC50 - Danish QSAR DB battery model
51	e5cdd1e6-1b43-dbee-18ab-122c14bc9561	ECOSAR: MYSID SHRIMP (SW) 96 h LC50 Mortality
52	800b5302-fb43-43e0-9cfb-58d789696685	KATE2020 - Fish ELS NOEC
53	18975284-5bd1-44b5-8b58-31451a308068	Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata 72h EC50 - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
54	0bc7d2aa-9288-3028-84e2-e51f7b8e02ba	ECOSAR: MYSID SHRIMP (SW) ChV
55	dadbe927-3326-4e22-8489-f37c2a8a4cc1	VEGA - Algae Acute (EC50) Toxicity model (ProtoQSAR-Combase)
56	33c41f8e-1c5a-43db-9089-3e2a236b895b	Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata 72h EC50 - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
57	18d757a3-4ea7-457a-94d1-f8840e32b41d	VEGA - Guppy LC50 model (KNN-IRFMN)
58	0502e196-f736-42cb-bbe1-833d5efa5273	M2 - LC50 - Pimephales promelas (fathead minnow)
59	35ced7f6-b7b4-4f9b-9db4-9e9eae4d402	VEGA - Daphnia Magna LC50 48h (EPA)
60	3df0209b-23d0-2469-98e3-13fab13a030e	ECOSAR: MYSID ChV
61	f9e4594d-4303-3c2e-cae5-a57589fba82d	ECOSAR: MYSID (SW) ChV
62	f229dd14-07d6-e453-3fb8-cea52dbb5f2d	ECOSAR: INVERTEBRATES (SW) ChV
63	331fb308-3810-4d5e-8521-8274bee98671	Fathead minnow 96h LC50 - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
64	cfbc2235-1372-44d9-9734-c8795d437591	ECOSAR: FISH (SW) 96 h LC50 Mortality
65	41dd369b-0b4e-42cd-8e5b-68aa00178bc3	VEGA - Fathead Minnow LC50 model (KNN-IRFMN)

66	23797e8a-4c0e-4542-9fdb-4e769e6c9b98	VEGA - Algae Chronic (NOEC) Toxicity model (IRFMN)
67	e2380607-58dc-5363-bc1e-f3a5510943fc	ECOSAR: FISH 14 d LC50 Mortality
68	a2029ec9-dc8a-708a-02ec-ff11b86488ea	ECOSAR: FISH (SW) ChV
69	1ddfc8bc-e8ef-4a2c-b2e5-f38ac41f05f3	VEGA - Fish Chronic (NOEC) Toxicity model (IRFMN)
70	19e369d4-129a-4c97-ade4-ead490bd0509	KATE2020 - Daphnid 48h EC50
71	fd20442b-e70b-441e-9ebd-3b304e189c40	Daphnia magna 48h EC50 - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
72	1ff2e28e-32af-4609-a07b-5ea1a0766ab7	VEGA - Fish Acute (LC50) Toxicity model (IRFMN-Combase)
73	7b65a29d-927e-1bd9-cbcc-9b9d645e9a19	ECOSAR: GREEN ALGAE 96 h EC50
74	fa6e6841-4faa-45e2-9566-49adc10b7b6d	VEGA - Fish Acute (LC50) Toxicity classification (SarPy-IRFMN)
75	3abb1428-a69e-4c88-a662-ba7ce722eda9	Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata 72h EC50 - Danish QSAR DB battery model
76	87599f30-7ed2-4db7-b396-80f9f3c09fa8	VEGA - Algae Classification Toxicity model (ProtoQSAR-Combase)
77	b77ceb47-a0bd-1cdd-798a-52eca641bc98	ECOSAR: ALGAE 72 h EC50
78	b74635c0-085d-46fc-abb-d187064a31f8	M4 - LC50 - Pimephales promelas (fathead minnow)
79	ffd13b83-19ed-4108-8b2b-e04c4dd125e0	VEGA - Fathead Minnow LC50 96h (EPA)
80	67079cdd-9d29-42bd-83df-aff826541ab7	VEGA - Daphnia Magna LC50 48h (DEMETRA)
81	1cdf9a38-9c93-4f72-8593-bdb49f11a755	Fathead minnow 96h LC50 - Danish QSAR DB battery model
82	bc33b29c-d232-458e-9622-89776f2dd2e9	KATE2020 - Algae 72h NOEC
83	e5e2dab3-ae15-254b-d7a8-5e2c210c2175	ECOSAR: FISH 96 h LC50 Mortality
84	af2eea6f-5c36-271d-619b-3deb035ad125	ECOSAR: ALGAE 96 h EC50 Growth
85	43804196-6507-4141-9126-7812e1b2bb27	VEGA - MOA fish toxicity classification (EPA T.E.S.T.)
86	2c5b2fc2-44aa-468e-a7fc-eebd1ca1e587	Fathead minnow 96h LC50 - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model

87	c0109778-3b84-4311-834a-c97c94f75244	M3 - LC50 - Pimephales promelas (fathead minnow)
88	34e20f93-ab15-45d9-8ad3-7c508af317ac	KATE2020 - Daphnid 21d NOEC
89	3f15a3e4-3a32-40f2-b9de-e9d9a2308e37	Half-Life (Model River) (EPISUITE)
90	76e54fa7-c23a-4462-8ec1-af3d68804f33	Half-Life (Model Lake) (EPISUITE)
91	e4296a17-76a4-4099-8172-8e7d0590d393	VEGA - Air Half-Life (IRFMN-CORAL)
92	95a49995-2ed8-475d-a905-b2bd9c94c751	Henrys Law Constant (Bond Method) (EPISUITE)
93	6d4090a2-4186-472b-95cb-2ca3130834dc	Henrys Law Constant (Group Method) (EPISUITE)
94	a0b6bf41-5f5d-4813-ab48-c2e03b8e60c0	Kb Half-Life at pH 8 (EPISUITE)
95	1305c2f3-d468-4755-8de4-808c4bf0265c	VEGA - Hydrolysis (IRFMN-CORAL)
96	3d2c8ae5-8ed0-401e-ba23-6f4418ef4736	Total Kb (EPISUITE)
97	a51c3afb-5e75-46f4-9443-1ac1d056f81a	Kb Half-Life at pH 7 (EPISUITE)
98	9cb95fa7-23b1-44da-a9ad-5572b8a105df	OVERALL OZONE Half-life
99	2a541a5b-8fb0-4c8d-ae5-34e249f0abb4	OVERALL OH rate constant (EPISUITE)
100	43584d7c-3f22-47b1-9bca-8c2a2890a378	OVERALL OH Half-life (EPISUITE)
101	de434d29-b63d-40de-bcd7-dd0ab51b0ff9	OVERALL OZONE rate constant (EPISUITE)
102	eeb91127-f5ba-46eb-acc7-95baf0174029	STP FM (Total removal) (EPISUITE)
103	f4da7814-ae4e-4054-94cb-cd00ed4ac9a4	STP FM (Total biodegradation) (EPISUITE)
104	c56c1dfd-d75b-48d5-8fc5-8e7ca8ebc311	VEGA - Persistence (sediment) quantitative model (IRFMN)
105	dc35f380-4ef1-496d-9375-84f077e61255	VEGA - Persistence (water) model (IRFMN)
106	d4eefe3f-45f0-498a-96f6-9b42fae26a8b	VEGA - Persistence (sediment) model (IRFMN)
107	b19a3738-0465-4473-bfea-9792698da139	VEGA - Persistence (water) quantitative model (IRFMN)
108	72dd9f8c-dd69-41b5-854c-1aa422a6e371	VEGA - Ready Biodegradability model (IRFMN)
109	02fe99cf-6b50-4176-97ac-7aa2a61bca30	BioHC Half-Life (EPISUITE)
110	e737e63f-75b6-44d0-81f4-67aa18fef3c0	Ready Biodegradability Prediction (EPISUITE)

111	23ded23c-3538-4af6-9dfc-cbdc08f05dbc	Not ready biodegradability (POS=Not Ready) - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
112	f39a191f-7916-4ca5-865d-743d0336da44	Biowin5 (MITI Linear Biodeg Probability) (EPISUITE)
113	2d4709aa-02d2-4c9d-9771-de3e49438f24	Biowin7 (Anaerobic Linear Biodeg Prob) (EPISUITE)
114	f1b29404-af2f-4186-87c6-2c17cc050435	Biowin3 (Survey Model - Ultimate Biodeg) (EPISUITE)
115	c2fb5684-dc8e-4071-bccd-8682b035e935	System-Integrated Model (HC-BioSIM)
116	d342928e-6b14-430b-bc95-a1ce090a18af	Biowin2 (Non-Linear Biodeg Probability) (EPISUITE)
117	9c47406d-7372-40c8-bf82-5cc86aa8e472	Not ready biodegradability - Danish QSAR DB battery model
118	7876b7a9-494b-440c-aa11-4621032178da	Biowin4 (Survey Model - Primary Biodeg) (EPISUITE)
119	412eccdf-6b1c-4954-a6c9-640428ec53f1	Biowin6 (MITI Non-Linear Biodeg Probability) (EPISUITE)
120	8d694a3a-16a8-4500-9c12-41a14672884c	Not ready biodegradability - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
121	28970c26-efa8-41ed-adbb-ff751e8bff01	Not ready biodegradability - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
122	2b18d26f-5448-48ba-a0a9-9b445fab0d12	Biowin1 (Linear Biodeg Probability) (EPISUITE)
123	0e2788dc-969c-448c-a151-149138fd32d9	VEGA - Persistence (soil) model (IRFMN)
124	2292b765-55ba-4776-bf60-1187dae090fd	VEGA - Persistence (soil) quantitative model (IRFMN)
125	8215ff87-71d6-4e43-83ea-e48def88a06b	Estrogen Receptor α Binding, Balanced Training Set (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB battery model
126	436cb0f1-4d79-4597-ac74-495cf38b0ae9	Thyroid Receptor α Binding (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
127	22a9b996-a71c-4f3a-a752-0c1205c09eb1	VEGA - Estrogen Receptor-mediated effect (IRFMN-CERAPP)
128	8d5dec9a-fb3e-4e3e-bdf4-02c5633701e7	Androgen Receptor Antagonism (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB battery model

129	3846de5d-cf1b-45f4-9476-88a7c005c153	Estrogen Receptor α Binding, Full training set (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
130	53582332-9126-4f7a-9169-b5cd9f5746e4	VEGA - Endocrine Disruptor activity screening (IRFMN)
131	6ecc55b8-cfde-4e91-ac78-13609e1d1168	VEGA - Thyroperoxidase Inhibitory Activity (OBERON)
132	4fc70e4d-10ac-46c8-b8ee-e91f626cb8f6	Estrogen Receptor α Activation (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
133	aa86909f-af28-4a88-9947-86120c37a312	Thyroid Receptor β Binding (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
134	4dff3718-4c9a-4d07-8632-00cdf7e7a595	Estrogen Receptor α Binding, Balanced Training Set (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
135	e78ad56c-945c-40a8-8320-c51c54a20eec	Thyroid Receptor α Binding (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
136	14d72058-9def-479b-a6e7-4aca07429db0	Estrogen Receptor α Activation (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
137	ea33a302-537d-4fad-b33f-de11dd218b21	Pregnane X Receptor (PXR) Binding (human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
138	19044aea-d9ed-4f0d-9629-bb0fae20b18c	VEGA - Thyroid Receptor Beta effect (NRMEA)
139	526920e1-c9ab-4501-8b25-13ca3b341fae	Androgen Receptor Antagonism (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
140	ee5460df-018b-4967-aaef-f2c078bd1a6d	Pregnane X Receptor (PXR) Binding (human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
141	4156f266-b55d-4cb9-b5b3-980f1e07cd68	Androgen Receptor Antagonism (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
142	cdc5f9c5-56e2-458f-a6ca-4753345e4ff5	Estrogen Receptor α Binding, Full training set (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
143	2d396fc4-3d33-4795-a289-7e45c921c627	VEGA - Aromatase activity model (IRFMN)
144	9b854fbb-0172-4d1b-a9a2-66034c4d7bd0	Estrogen Receptor α Binding, Balanced Training Set (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model

145	26295ed6-8ee2-47d7-a6e2-77d96aa098c8	Androgen Receptor Antagonism (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
146	324856af-e295-45c8-9116-e2fc6723634a	Thyroid Receptor α Binding (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
147	c128e0bb-e326-4bc0-9cec-b8abd01e0bcd	Pregnane X Receptor (PXR) Binding (human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB battery model
148	f0fedc45-292c-42b0-b8cb-e7c692151f92	VEGA - Thyroid Receptor Alpha effect (NRMEA)
149	38ba45e5-1cde-4500-9e23-7690c72e5953	VEGA - Aromatase activity model (TOX21)
150	4cea4b42-1631-492b-ad36-1c5420dbf1b8	Estrogen Receptor α Activation (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
151	00d21e8a-7632-4279-ae8b-cf9d4d5f0f45	VEGA - Androgen Receptor-mediated effect (IRFMN-COMPARA)
152	4dc67e74-953f-4ee6-8bd3-e55d9c886e16	Thyroid Receptor α Binding (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB battery model
153	e1a651d3-b815-40c6-b4c7-7f5334a62b62	VEGA - Estrogen Receptor Relative Binding Affinity model (IRFMN)
154	704d95dd-902b-4c88-883f-7f32ba8bc78d	Estrogen Receptor α Binding, Full training set (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
155	c6ce4f63-08eb-46ae-90f1-cf8b59edd40a	Estrogen Receptor α Binding, Balanced Training Set (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
156	618c9796-1402-4c15-8eaf-b9d74c1a99b3	Estrogen Receptor α Activation (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB battery model
157	30fcefe1-c953-4761-a0b8-bd51248d0205	Thyroid Receptor β Binding (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB battery model
158	3dbfd255-d4ec-4d6c-ad2d-5da60e8bfa6a	VEGA - Glucocorticoid Receptor (OBERON)
159	f62fdadd-30dc-4e86-b035-555a0c477394	Pregnane X Receptor (PXR) Binding (human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
160	b6b748c3-50e2-4741-9bbe-9bdcf7ebe564	QSAR rtER Expert System - USEPA
161	d4b7f4ab-f8de-4760-95dd-f9647507cbfb	Thyroid Receptor β Binding (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model

162	e5e79b82-3e71-48fe-9190-2797322c7248	Thyroid Receptor β Binding (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
163	1c8af3ba-52b2-4a08-a94f-ae1bd1736c45	Estrogen Receptor α Binding, Full training set (Human in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB battery model
164	3fa56226-315a-4e18-9021-1df8eae5fd3	FDA RCA Cancer Rat - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
165	1e7d360f-85da-4957-84cf-17de3dee9538	FDA RCA Cancer Rodent - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
166	812fe6bf-a77d-48e0-8cb9-098f51b27fe9	FDA RCA Cancer Male Rat - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
167	edaafce9-0b6d-49a3-9801-47dfbf3bdd54	VEGA - Carcinogenicity model (CAESAR)
168	a86720fe-34f5-4bbc-a3f8-4c38dd642a62	Liver Specific Cancer in Rat or Mouse - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
169	c40d6a42-80bd-4917-8878-40e053565bc7	Liver Specific Cancer in Rat or Mouse - Danish QSAR DB battery model
170	7ef3e1a1-d10a-4278-bd90-e3da310335c6	FDA RCA Cancer Rat - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
171	a329e3be-5b40-4fd0-b5ad-2f7d8a2e89cc	Liver Specific Cancer in Rat or Mouse - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
172	eb6861f5-178d-4109-8bc3-6c2c085e8ac2	FDA RCA Cancer Female Rat - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
173	c11ced21-23d1-4574-aa17-d069bb4fff60	FDA RCA Cancer Mouse - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
174	12b85d79-c468-4da6-8e2e-3fe9622f84b6	FDA RCA Cancer Female Mouse - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
175	892add19-9efa-4011-b8dc-f23c3f9f3d29	FDA RCA Cancer Female Rat - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
176	f7395d96-ddfb-4b68-b8cd-ac606567cc71	FDA RCA Cancer Male Rat - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
177	41b3e7be-562a-44a2-82f6-15afad27e334	FDA RCA Cancer Male Mouse - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
178	1ce26c1e-98bb-4311-9b84-ae571a0d074b	VEGA - Carcinogenicity in male rat (CORAL)
179	adc64575-36e0-4eb5-86df-fc99825e2762	FDA RCA Cancer Male Mouse - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model

180	1e68bcdf-b2b8-4d84-b45e-ed38b3299b05	VEGA - Carcinogenicity model (IRFMN- ISSCAN-CGX)
181	494572f1-eaca-49ba-95d4-29204b504b9f	VEGA - Carcinogenicity inhalation classification model (IRFMN)
182	9bb94df1-4788-4f17-bbd9-ab4c562091d0	FDA RCA Cancer Mouse - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
183	0a590899-12a7-466c-a8dc-aa584870d0e6	Liver Specific Cancer in Rat or Mouse - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
184	e9b1d082-4358-4f13-8268-3239d5de2cdd	VEGA - Carcinogenicity model (ISS)
185	1d743a96-53b9-428f-bae0-165eb7a48435	FDA RCA Cancer Rodent - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
186	06e49033-ac62-4773-8b44-49cb3ad99e84	VEGA - Carcinogenicity oral Slope Factor model (IRFMN)
187	e2078536-1427-4d94-88dc- 766215ea9abb	FDA RCA Cancer Female Mouse - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
188	0665aa46-d259-4194-9f4b-9d04d65095a4	VEGA - Carcinogenicity model (IRFMN- Antares)
189	9dcaa97c-bd11-420a-8bc8-770324496760	VEGA - Carcinogenicity inhalation Slope Factor model (IRFMN)
190	66f66df4-cc3f-4c8b-a932-8ea409f17b44	VEGA - Carcinogenicity in female Rat (CORAL)
191	38cc50db-7cc8-4398-8ff3-78fe7aded446	VEGA - Carcinogenicity oral classification model (IRFMN)
192	fbcad6d4-4b84-47a4-9e3b-fbb3d687d7bf	VEGA - NOAEL (CONCERT/Coral)
193	64e253a3-716b-4dbc-bab5-ae4569550cf0	MRDD in Humans \leq 2.69 mg/kg-bw/d - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
194	e2456d4f-0138-4351-943a-cf5a90e8bdb6	VEGA - NOAEL (IRFMN-CORAL)
195	7b70844d-3e9e-4739-8b85-beaae73c2a93	MRDD in Humans \leq 2.69 mg/kg-bw/d - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
196	bfa67d55-725a-431e-9888-9d36a5e88c03	VEGA - LOAEL (CONCERT/Coral)
197	8dbe60c0-1254-4c38-b480-5838e3cf5cd8	VEGA - Liver LOAEL (CORAL)
198	262d365e-4bf3-4d3f-bcd9-069381b64d5d	MRDD in Humans \leq 2.69 mg/kg-bw/d - Danish QSAR DB battery model
199	9be29f2a-2921-4c96-bccb-9ef8e3125749	VEGA - Liver NOAEL (CORAL)

200	98f01ecc-7ccb-4d0c-a24f-a8f6e6ddacf5	MRDD in Humans \leq 2.69 mg/kg-bw/d - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
201	a6107f3b-17a5-4338-9cb5-e393f7b8f2c0	VEGA - Hepatic Steatosis MIE assay for PXR up (TOXCAST)
202	9e25a61c-7b07-40d1-9350-0584b229e49a	VEGA - Hepatic Steatosis MIE assay for NRF2 (TOXCAST)
203	734f4ab8-2d26-40fe-b345-469e2a50089a	VEGA - Hepatic Steatosis MIE assay for PPARg up (TOXCAST)
204	2bf928f6-5430-44fe-a20d-2df08d011d07	VEGA - Hepatic Steatosis MIE assay for PPARa up (TOXCAST)
205	16251e73-9841-497b-b293-80b0a040f1fa	Allergic Contact Dermatitis, Guinea Pig and Human - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
206	27ab0aa7-1608-49e1-a1bb-eea25a8edadc	Respiratory Sensitisation in Humans - Danish QSAR DB battery model
207	f8152429-7dd7-4a4b-94b4-34819309d3d7	VEGA - Skin Sensitization model (IRFMN-JRC)
208	b3649eb6-3aa5-40fe-9f58-bf948f138194	Respiratory Sensitisation in Humans - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
209	a7fa53db-fc64-4666-907c-91fad51a1a9f	Respiratory Sensitisation in Humans - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
210	0aca345d-becd-478a-a680-5203f94405fc	VEGA - Skin Sensitization (CONCERT/SarPy)
211	2ecd574b-0766-4494-8e38-99a915b7969e	Allergic Contact Dermatitis, Guinea Pig and Human - Danish QSAR DB battery model
212	64331e8b-92b7-4175-84c2-5af114b0cf84	VEGA - Skin Sensitization model (TOXTREE)
213	e940daec-8354-4d9d-859c-3bc608825029	VEGA - Skin Sensitization model (NCSTOX)
214	86a6ccb3-4207-4940-a1cf-ac5dfcc6e59c	Skin sensitization for DASS
215	d11c5087-96a3-4864-864f-62c29d68a6c7	Allergic Contact Dermatitis, Guinea Pig and Human - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
216	22ddae20-e190-4529-a316-fe69c67e9bed	Respiratory Sensitisation in Humans - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
217	7d3efbeb-2974-42aa-95dd-579de5906f7b	VEGA - Skin Sensitization (CONCERT/Kode)
218	bc0a335b-d524-4c11-9346-1318ff353c01	VEGA - Skin Sensitization model (CAESAR)

219	26b06772-c669-475c-9854-437d31550f61	Allergic Contact Dermatitis, Guinea Pig and Human - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
220	f2d0c665-8816-423b-9e62-96ac5a6061a9	Photoinduced toxicity based on 3T3 NRU data
221	49d71d48-712d-4dac-9249-845ef482ebff	Acute toxicity in Mouse, Intravenous - Danish QSAR DB ACDLabs model
222	ec2a6dc9-26f8-4afa-95e1-e6a65c3c6e09	Acute toxicity in Rat, Oral - Danish QSAR DB ACDLabs model
223	915ef11a-39e3-443b-b7ae-ad0c93ccfedb	Acute toxicity in Rat, Intraperitoneal - Danish QSAR DB ACDLabs model
224	59313383-78d1-46cf-a8c9-f7d27739f902	Acute toxicity in Mouse, Intraperitoneal - Danish QSAR DB ACDLabs model
225	f2463f89-ff45-4750-81b9-02286f3bdcf7	Acute toxicity in Mouse, Oral - Danish QSAR DB ACDLabs model
226	15c85188-6634-4b17-95d9-d08ecd72b48e	Acute toxicity in Mouse, Subcutaneous - Danish QSAR DB ACDLabs model
227	a822e983-b92e-48a9-961c-bbeb9d8707c7	VEGA - Hepatotoxicity model (IRFMN)
228	5656b084-830e-4581-b734-402e90bfc7bb	VEGA - Acute Toxicity (LD50) model (KNN)
229	7b713887-0b12-44bd-9c59-3077f5c1e45e	Ashby Structural Alerts - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
230	b4057991-b20e-4888-bef0-59c65c722b4c	Chromosome Aberrations in Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) Cells - Danish QSAR DB battery model
231	c9643d3b-3e80-45fa-8d55-8c02b33d507d	Unscheduled DNA Synthesis (UDS) in Rat Hepatocytes - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
232	7d490692-9270-404d-83e6-75ab676871b1	Syrian Hamster Embryo (SHE) Cell Transformation - Danish QSAR DB battery model
233	2e13fb9d-a85c-4499-a044-e70048faecda	Chromosome Aberrations in Chinese Hamster Lung (CHL) Cells - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
234	8fe36ebc-9c05-40b4-8b9f-8e1f132ad584	Comet Assay in Mouse - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model

235	c8884470-59a2-48b4-b0e9-c94241bbcd33	Potent Ames Mutagens, Reversions \geq 10 Times Controls – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db Leadscope model
236	0a83c768-9af5-42de-8d14-9c146ca0fc28	Dominant Lethal Mutations in Rodents - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
237	d64d0299-5516-41cb-a29b-d52bdbb1e95c	Sister Chromatid Exchange in Mouse Bone Marrow Cells - Danish QSAR DB battery model
238	d2142f81-3e8c-4b60-883a-bbb3cf989ebb	Unscheduled DNA Synthesis (UDS) in Rat Hepatocytes - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
239	3ddaf03e-9d27-4cfd-ab64-1e94c9db6a3c	Dominant Lethal Mutations in Rodents - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
240	4520d95c-4fd8-4891-8485-7dc4d6f572e5	Chromosome Aberrations in Chinese Hamster Lung (CHL) Cells - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
241	c82df733-0700-4341-b2f1-b2e9edb16ebc	Frameshift Ames Mutagens – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db SciQSAR model
242	e6eb00de-1336-489b-bd9e-0972784b700a	Chromosome Aberrations in Chinese Hamster Lung (CHL) Cells - Danish QSAR DB battery model
243	4d487549-d4f4-40c5-98d2-d56b02e29ff7	Chromosome Aberrations in Chinese Hamster Lung (CHL) Cells - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
244	8df4a7f1-caec-4d23-9e76-98ee813c73b0	VEGA - Mutagenicity (Ames test) model (SarPy-IRFMN)
245	a227dc2c-4210-41da-b788-95e562560dd0	VEGA - Mutagenicity (Ames test) model (ISS)
246	809736b2-a7fc-4efb-9c09-300b8c279667	Ames test in <i>S. typhimurium</i> (in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
247	efc4bb1c-8ddc-4bbd-95d3-7ac76ae1dc59	Ames test in <i>S. typhimurium</i> (in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
248	17fff865-562d-47ca-94fb-a8d02e22ac0e	Sister Chromatid Exchange in Mouse Bone Marrow Cells - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
249	72b6afe7-8fe0-470b-8169-87ddeb3350	Base-Pair Ames Mutagens – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db battery model

250	924cfabf-25c4-4eef-9f7f-d68082aaf4cb	Chromosome Aberrations in Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) Cells - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
251	d66973dc-75aa-402a-8122-4d147af744c4	Micronucleus Test in Mouse Erythrocytes - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
252	ffeb9506-1ea2-4666-aeb3-b2df8cf3d683	VEGA - Mutagenicity (Ames test) model for aromatic amines (CONCERT/IRFMN)
253	54d276c3-59df-40d7-9a41-2f2488e23857	Comet Assay in Mouse - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
254	b5621d67-c022-49b0-a24a-5566f7fe3832	Sex-Linked Recessive Lethal (SLRL) Test in Drosophila m. - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
255	3047fa8d-c399-4f74-8a43-925267e66845	Dominant Lethal Mutations in Rodents - Danish QSAR DB battery model
256	478beb9d-ad27-487a-b41f-56c8ec42ff1b	Mutations in Thymidine Kinase Locus in Mouse Lymphoma Cells - Danish QSAR DB battery model
257	a504bfae-4f70-4684-a47b-56971bfcf5ef	Direct Acting Mutagens (without S9) – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db CASE Ultra model
258	7e75d2d4-dea5-42bf-8844-b9eb1b7cc6f5	Sex-Linked Recessive Lethal (SLRL) Test in Drosophila m. - Danish QSAR DB battery model
259	c03625e8-e84c-4359-8be6-7d071bdc2e66	Syrian Hamster Embryo (SHE) Cell Transformation - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
260	873e450d-5bfl-4d81-b2f2-997ed3ab7f7a	VEGA - Mutagenicity (Ames test) model (CAESAR)
261	ac5c9912-0a29-43b0-96ab-24477386a51b	Sister Chromatid Exchange in Mouse Bone Marrow Cells - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
262	fl18ee85-6f58-441d-bb5c-3292085efe3e	Mutations in HGPRT (Hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase) Locus in Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) Cells - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
263	49c43e8c-7541-41e5-939a-009c2614f83d	Direct Acting Mutagens (without S9) – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db Leadscope model

264	433f5575-c51c-4489-a831-33fc009f8e0f	Micronucleus Test in Mouse Erythrocytes - Danish QSAR DB battery model
265	503aa08f-8db8-4f33-89c0-0000732a82b5	Frameshift Ames Mutagens – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db Leadscope model
266	df2fef50-a40b-49c2-8824-2420eb36f4a8	Direct Acting Mutagens (without S9) – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db SciQSAR model
267	ab931ba1-667d-4f2c-8284-9fff81c550a1	Micronucleus Test in Mouse Erythrocytes - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
268	55e2f43b-48c0-4495-9d60-11d4cce5c88	Potent Ames Mutagens, Reversions ≥ 10 Times Controls – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db battery model
269	238c4984-33b6-4f35-992d-6a74a373b163	Ashby Structural Alerts - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
270	c5543ce9-a424-4466-9c4a-e759ab141c54	VEGA - Chromosomal aberration model (CORAL)
271	97ad0be8-f79e-4da1-b88b-083e266ca1e8	Mutations in Thymidine Kinase Locus in Mouse Lymphoma Cells - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
272	b496b7d0-ae64-47cf-8ee7-b4125ff41a32	VEGA - In vitro Micronucleus activity (IRFMN-VERMEER)
273	c42ebdec-0a61-4667-bf2f-41aac0f465af	Base-Pair Ames Mutagens – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db SciQSAR model
274	6592a47b-75e9-4055-80d0-dc7693077870	VEGA - Mutagenicity (Ames test) model (KNN-Read-Across)
275	61765a2b-93ce-4ab3-8e04-8869a5ea33c2	Ames test in <i>S. typhimurium</i> (in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
276	264d8ea1-d79f-4cc8-8e72-d96468444c8b	Base-Pair Ames Mutagens – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db Leadscope model
277	a53fd09c-1222-4472-b0d2-1a8911407ce8	Mutations in HGPRT (Hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase) Locus in Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) Cells - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
278	e3292d61-903e-42d6-821d-0787758f55fb	Unscheduled DNA Synthesis (UDS) in Rat Hepatocytes - Danish QSAR DB battery model

279	d91ec923-da97-4bab-95a4-0e07f51dbbab	Ashby Structural Alerts - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
280	a765be17-bf24-4497-85e7-c07712dfb08f	Sister Chromatid Exchange in Mouse Bone Marrow Cells - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
281	d309058f-b2b3-441c-ae84-3fe2a3c148eb	Syrian Hamster Embryo (SHE) Cell Transformation - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
282	0e999ed6-5ed4-4b1f-9f34-8321782b69e9	Ames test in <i>S. typhimurium</i> (in vitro) - Danish QSAR DB battery model
283	1d42e27f-2e37-46e6-bab3-76752869d60e	Potent Ames Mutagens, Reversions ≥ 10 Times Controls – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db SciQSAR model
284	80f39253-5987-4ba1-9a06-d4504b3988b9	Mutations in HGPRT (Hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase) Locus in Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) Cells - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
285	7f35a30c-e929-4c4a-b2b1-882efffe1609	Mutations in HGPRT (Hypoxanthine-guanine phosphoribosyltransferase) Locus in Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) Cells - Danish QSAR DB battery model
286	ebd9cb06-7279-44a5-ad7b-9a7f6a0c3802	Unscheduled DNA Synthesis (UDS) in Rat Hepatocytes - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
287	23e9216d-69b5-433b-b1ab-02f4e24f3fd9	Mutations in Thymidine Kinase Locus in Mouse Lymphoma Cells - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
288	8d6ff825-d774-42a8-99b9-efbdb468f7e3	Syrian Hamster Embryo (SHE) Cell Transformation - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
289	05935271-21a5-4794-94b8-fdb904f3ce2e	Base-Pair Ames Mutagens – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db CASE Ultra model
290	e4356698-c6a8-4e38-95f7-44c790ce9d79	Frameshift Ames Mutagens – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db CASE Ultra model
291	01a2bc45-f51c-4c72-ae20-ec6e21fd20a1	Frameshift Ames Mutagens – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db battery model

292	d05c14bc-af5c-4f25-891b-87ae78a29aa7	Ashby Structural Alerts - Danish QSAR DB battery model
293	cb1ce7fe-4d12-45e1-9210-46f5b6d9c751	Comet Assay in Mouse - Danish QSAR DB battery model
294	b16efd7b-a6cf-491d-a517-d6dc31ee0da6	Sex-Linked Recessive Lethal (SLRL) Test in Drosophila m. - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
295	13b4fb2a-d0ab-40aa-8028-eee03508d3ee	Comet Assay in Mouse - Danish QSAR DB CASE Ultra model
296	451c2a16-6c4c-4013-b9be-3e09023d0bb9	Chromosome Aberrations in Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) Cells - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
297	525a4569-dde2-478d-968d-5f6f1e7d4574	Mutations in Thymidine Kinase Locus in Mouse Lymphoma Cells - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
298	a2734343-7eee-4b79-a37b-348732c8b43f	Micronucleus Test in Mouse Erythrocytes - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
299	aacaca74-8e21-4c56-aca2-5f7b2b7413c6	Chromosome Aberrations in Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) Cells - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
300	76674233-021f-40b4-b8cc-804f723b7f60	Direct Acting Mutagens (without S9) – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db battery model
301	724936ce-90ff-4393-a864-7bce04f3bf3d	Sex-Linked Recessive Lethal (SLRL) Test in Drosophila m. - Danish QSAR DB SciQSAR model
302	3dfa83b9-089b-4659-a9ce-37c7d42242a6	Potent Ames Mutagens, Reversions ≥ 10 Times Controls – ONLY use for Ames POS_IN - Danish db CASE Ultra model
303	479d3c50-eca5-48c8-93da-eb7d85130666	Dominant Lethal Mutations in Rodents - Danish QSAR DB Leadscope model
304	7d8932eb-9fb8-45af-92a0-e7dc11e5b2a1	VEGA - In vivo Micronucleus activity (IRFMN)
305	249fd511-d84e-4502-9d47-6c4076db6917	VEGA - Skin Permeation (LogKp) model (Ten Berge)
306	de9a6f5b-6a39-4677-9ec5-9a0a81d60429	VEGA - Skin Permeation (LogKp) model (Potts and Guy)

307	6ab04118-e051-4ecd-a920-da31d6572f91	VEGA - Plasma Protein Binding - sqFU (CORAL)
308	fa5b0f2e-1770-421c-9565-dfd9e4b54ddd	VEGA - Plasma Protein Binding - LogK (IRFMN)
309	bd99390e-49a9-4dea-a30c-1506c7869aa9	VEGA - Total body elimination half-life (QSARINS)
310	5c3f66d1-debc-4f38-93a6-051390828603	VEGA - P-Glycoprotein activity model (NIC)
311	0e23306d-e68d-4e1d-a233-8d9cc47fc713	VEGA - Adipose tissue - blood model (INERIS)

ANNEX A2 – QSAR PROFILERS FROM QSAR TOOLBOX

	key	Profiler
1	1f1091d6-b4dd-4400-8dcf-bdbc1397a3de	1 ECHA P profiler
2	6db1fc83-858a-4fc7-9289-753c7c6b38f7	2 ECHA B profiler
3	30153132-a1f3-4a5a-846b-3aac62ddf453	3 ECHA T profiler (ENV)
4	a06271f5-944e-4892-b0ad-fa5f7217ec14	Acute aquatic toxicity classification by Verhaar (Modified)
5	5f241597-c420-43f9-8ff7-af33dff99c60	Acute aquatic toxicity MOA by OASIS
6	5a23498e-11ea-4569-b120-b4a0f2cad786	Acute Oral Toxicity
7	6e91aee2-2c3e-4e4b-8b44-5d14018bb4eb	All TERPENES
8	585c3344-45f5-4c22-8466-7324383a3c30	All terpenes_R7
9	f662ac67-684c-4c3f-8a66-160d2b63f435	Aquatic toxicity classification by ECOSAR
10	62d7947a-d473-45d6-8f1c-ebd45cac6267	Bioaccumulation - metabolism alerts
11	66ce7511-d556-4052-81db-5eaf2d370e7a	Bioaccumulation - metabolism half-lives
12	e0f6c1c4-04bc-47cb-bf31-86948f38a607	Biodeg BioHC half-life (Biowin)
13	0d6c0447-e311-4201-933a-bb75cd845ca7	Biodegradation fragments (BioWIN MITI)
14	44619e93-36a4-412f-9575-c21a4928fa57	Biodegradation primary (Biowin 4)
15	98258538-a931-408f-b459-15d769090db9	Biodegradation probability (Biowin 1)
16	528c9b02-d816-4996-891a-94d150d7e374	Biodegradation probability (Biowin 2)
17	042065de-c0a9-459d-a256-9a572b5bdedb	Biodegradation probability (Biowin 5)
18	995f48fb-21ad-4ae8-9e33-42e4c58ead97	Biodegradation probability (Biowin 6)
19	288b2dcd-153b-4c3b-bf23-01e39be21f9b	Biodegradation probability (Biowin 7)

20	a073010f-e717-4b16-97be-2329de725403	Biodegradation ultimate (Biowin 3)
21	48ddf1f2-fae6-4672-8f71-6c13e6f1008e	Blood brain barrier
22	2256b12d-5ef8-49a2-af9a-b453b3f23d96	Carcinogenicity (genotox and nongenotox) alerts by ISS
23	ee991334-f544-4b4c-b5d9-ff5ca5935101	Chemical elements
24	7d637c92-6764-476b-903e-09735cd3119	DART scheme
25	dfd344a8-775a-4999-9ccc-2cdc94fd785	Database Affiliation
26	cba502bd-358a-426d-ab7a-688a7202f091	DNA alerts for AMES, CA and MNT by OASIS
27	23d69016-71e4-4dbf-8306-2faad3071f99	DNA binding by OASIS
28	2782c679-745d-4ae5-8e91-e18daf8c93e0	DNA binding by OECD
29	82022987-367a-4aca-b962-9ec7127e3040	Estrogen Receptor Binding
30	97f51119-d6a1-4597-b9a4-5389763d3cfe	Example Prioritization Scheme (PBT)
31	ae169ec2-d1b5-4fb7-a59c-9dd5eb00c7f7	Eye irritation/corrosion Exclusion rules by BfR
32	e5349d01-44b1-44bd-9213-2d194d9549fa	Eye irritation/corrosion Inclusion rules by BfR
33	d00b495e-31d6-4640-b5d5-64b7f4e25f97	Groups of elements
34	f5975ac5-ef52-44e9-9c2d-ec676c724c4b	Hydrolysis half-life (Ka, pH 7)(Hydrowin)
35	ddd59664-8509-4a0d-9d24-99b37d91ca85	Hydrolysis half-life (Ka, pH 8)(Hydrowin)
36	35894a1a-1570-44a3-aa8e-4de2ba44ad38	Hydrolysis half-life (Kb, pH 7)(Hydrowin)
37	cbcd33a4-bd5a-4769-a7ae-503277a8c562	Hydrolysis half-life (Kb, pH 8)(Hydrowin)
38	04d1717a-70a8-4e1f-8a6d-08338bdd7ec4	Hydrolysis half-life (pH 6.5-7.4)
39	50d215a3-adb9-4b37-b72b-6bc04f313056	in vitro mutagenicity (Ames test) alerts by ISS
40	12fb37d0-fdde-4985-8092-34dd6aa32023	in vivo mutagenicity (Micronucleus) alerts by ISS
41	3e8e16a0-7723-4649-80cd-90c21f39ca01	Inventory Affiliation
42	5486d6ff-3241-401c-82a3-d7eb9a1b2be1	Ionization at pH = 1

43	4ced55c3-7eb8-4f9e-9c8f-3e43c6b8053c	Ionization at pH = 4
44	65f6a209-e50c-40f8-809a-3ae6baba33d4	Ionization at pH = 7.4
45	f6c44acb-1264-4ba6-9815-2ad226f858c3	Ionization at pH = 9
46	561749ad-2c8b-1ad4-b56a-dc418a9438b2	iSafeRat® Mechanisms of toxic Action profiler
47	e8aeedd7-72d8-4003-b2ed-cd6529677b8f	Keratinocyte gene expression
48	92343cf5-043c-444b-bf10-0be0ccfc134e	Lipinski Rule Oasis
49	799fd171-ca3b-4c61-8e99-a2fcbdde5ccc	OECD HPV Chemical Categories
50	52e345cb-8f65-4524-9f33-64b96ed13878	Oncologic Primary Classification
51	eac042c5-58d0-4f61-944d-74f800f15cac	Oral absorption
52	0e9ebafd-9dcd-4899-b5bb-11b85ef32b23	Organic functional groups
53	4fbdaa0a-0d8d-4b7e-8851-b8817bf50b03	Organic functional groups (nested)
54	fa31b3b4-853e-470d-9a71-eded98e60c4e	Organic functional groups (US EPA)
55	9259b6a8-a0ee-4344-bc18-ef5e394d7274	Organic functional groups, Norbert Haider (checkmol)
56	2dd5c9d5-59ad-4158-b620-0e6cf8660e4f	Protein binding alerts for Chromosomal aberration by OASIS
57	1680d436-1615-40b9-9417-4bce5fe787fa	Protein binding alerts for skin sensitization according to GHS
58	98f8a7b9-0740-4b71-af83-f108fb4f722d	Protein binding alerts for skin sensitization by OASIS
59	71bf1896-8d07-4ff8-a7eb-5298fe3bd1b9	Protein binding by OASIS
60	723eb011-3e5b-4565-9358-4c3d8620ba5d	Protein binding by OECD
61	6b981ca5-a945-4331-9e92-a8948cddb1e9	Protein binding potency Cys (DPRA 13%)
62	a76653ce-8e5e-49a5-83e6-58c6139ca7fe	Protein binding potency GSH
63	043c65bc-a16d-472c-aa76-7e3d0b3f48eb	Protein Binding Potency h-CLAT
64	e6fd8c5f-32b0-4f16-a8ed-95b03298e83e	Protein binding potency Lys (DPRA 13%)
65	5b1bc853-0ec0-423a-9200-21c440c9a7cc	Repeated dose (HESS)
66	5e181bd3-3d8d-4d9e-b981-54c4ca97bb8b	Respiratory sensitisation

67	269cbe29-b1e2-484b-905f-bbd83a380899	Retinoic Acid Receptor Binding
68	32656e9d-5057-4019-ba83-d2713ef60605	rtER Expert System - USEPA
69	b78ae496-5748-49d1-93d1-7530d5e2e367	Skin irritation/corrosion Exclusion rules by BfR
70	205eaaae-5679-47ad-b6e7-b544b95436ae	Skin irritation/corrosion Inclusion rules by BfR
71	359655bf-5bdb-43f6-96b7-6162bffe9ea1	Skin permeability
72	ac82ed8d-a156-42d4-83e2-ac420b748304	Structure similarity
73	ff16af4c-efe9-4a7e-8a2f-a172104c2614	Substance type
74	6e1f573f-c6d3-42e5-a800-7c118f442a14	Tautomers unstable
75	aa645923-a592-46fe-9069-737a2e4a7ac6	Toxic hazard classification by Cramer
76	8118699b-f496-41fa-b0bd-d1fab56af3d9	Toxic hazard classification by Cramer (extended)_v.2.5
77	34996c50-e065-4407-8aa9-e09c9e485cea	Toxic hazard classification by Cramer_v.2.5
78	9aed1a13-4f47-4302-9e23-edfeb3c4283f	Ultimate biodeg
79	f05e3ca0-bba7-4a31-89a0-ab345fad7ef7	Uncouplers (MITOTOX)
80	1a058730-3759-47c0-9f79-273598cf85f1	US-EPA New Chemical Categories

ANNEX A3 – QSAR CALCULATORS FROM QSAR TOOLBOX

	key	Property
1	036e8e9a-cbc8-47d8-b123-c8b5867fbf20	Calculated heat of formation
2	4d251795-5ce3-4dd9-b51e-fd73b8268815	Diameter effective
3	1804a854-9041-4495-9931-7414c22a5e49	Diameter maximum
4	4ea82d5b-449a-4a37-aba1-1205757440ea	Diameter minimum
5	3d368015-29ba-4732-83eb-e8dbcaceedc5	Dipole moment
6	8972176e-2f79-48c3-afa2-9a490107ff94	Electronegativity
7	c3f07bc4-04ec-4559-a591-dc3d43184b9a	GAP Energy
8	69743ffc-6464-4940-a391-f15aa46e6463	Geometric info Wiener index
9	79a77fbc-0293-4175-8971-1be40a49e0ef	Geometric Wiener index
10	1ef22f57-67ef-47c7-9256-86f8aaa09752	HOMO Energy
11	0f74bf52-4574-419e-911e-3cbbaa40c546	LUMO Energy
12	fc50f3d8-fe38-4658-8431-9ca643f5b3d4	Maximum distance
13	d9f4b140-9122-4d0a-b783-6ff716d3812d	Maximum donor delocalizability
14	c7479fe4-9422-407c-bd4f-6ffe4cf8b8be	Planarity
15	5c3b7c38-3c68-4107-8c4f-b6a577f109ff	Planarity conjugated
16	1a7b9402-20bb-4504-906f-718b070fc1d9	VdW surface
17	807187a3-963c-481f-9d76-290ddb8cd00a	VdW surface DPSA1
18	5f5232f0-50aa-4701-9da2-c326041a7fbb	VdW surface DPSA2
19	9452c7e2-3faa-4e5e-bdd0-edb4caea17c0	VdW surface DPSA3
20	2c50bb51-b746-4a0d-99cb-8c74aa6897be	VdW surface PNSA1
21	dedc426d-8d5e-4c14-a0dc-c5499f2420dd	VdW surface PNSA2
22	660fa11d-34d9-44b6-bd05-7d981e85195d	VdW surface PNSA3
23	348dff55-97ac-4b2d-8ca2-05d4a792dbfa	VdW surface PPSA1
24	6f03a50c-4042-4925-bfc5-9948ac80e1f0	VdW surface PPSA2
25	5c9e9233-c1b5-44f9-acdf-3e7f3deaf284	VdW surface PPSA3
26	992719d7-fb72-4bf0-b6e9-a90f6119e9a2	VdW volume
27	edbc2aff-a3dc-48a1-afc2-cf0ff9906ec7	Volume Polarizability

28	6ff39f26-51a1-4b6a-b088-0515958bcaa7	(Q) Acidic pKa (Chemaxon)
29	af55961b-adc3-438c-8925-cb06f84839fd	(Q) Basic pKa (Chemaxon)
30	06aac1c2-d817-4509-a691-f0f508e5b4ef	Acidic pKa (OASIS composite calculator)
31	f82c7750-0abd-45a3-a0da-a797015fb3ea	Acidic pKa (OASIS Consensus)
32	34f5bbe7-10fd-457d-b279-3e41e9cde208	Acidic pKa (OASIS Electric)
33	3ac09b97-c12c-449b-bf2a-b45eeabbd45	Acidic pKa (OASIS Regression)
34	451a39fb-59c9-4d09-a491-b00c72bf6f8b	Amino acids pKa (OASIS Regression)
35	9bb20642-1f3b-4d2d-acba-0d6d4b688f92	BAF
36	f272f5da-b806-4e82-8450-5f1b6787b68d	BAF (lower trophic)
37	a561e542-a9e9-4088-a185-d38c40892d61	BAF (mid trophic)
38	33784cff-0ecb-480c-bac4-2ba26f766da0	BAF (upper trophic, biotransformation rate is zero)
39	d02d698c-aa78-436b-acc3-cd64a604b1d7	BAF (upper trophic)
40	2f741ad2-6b02-40a2-a515-b4fd9b3d3f73	Basic pKa (OASIS Regression)
41	46b6e16b-40c0-4038-be12-0a219421b259	BCF
42	2a5e2a0c-4297-4d55-b47b-8ab806bb606c	BCF (lower trophic)
43	1fb5f79b-a392-4a51-af21-c12ad2ca2798	BCF (mid trophic)
44	594eed30-cd2b-4dbd-a292-464605e1b4fd	BCF (upper trophic, biotransformation rate is zero)
45	2b094e5c-0418-4276-a51a-3acb8f4dee92	BCF (upper trophic)
46	ae2c0208-7446-40fa-a717-90b4cb5c0f69	Bio Half-Life
47	a175721a-26c8-4efe-9fd2-58b8b9501ea8	Biodeg probability (Biowin 1)
48	26fa8f20-a641-4694-984a-cf0916a96582	Biodeg probability (Biowin 2)
49	2214f1e7-d6a4-44e4-b9b8-4f83ee718438	Biodeg probability (Biowin 5)
50	d68d4ae3-6e41-4985-899c-fb54f0bd7aed	Biodeg probability (Biowin 6)
51	a250a49f-10d6-4022-887d-89fa6d9c4549	Biodeg probability (Biowin 7)
52	ff21291e-b0ae-41ae-b875-5099850cee1f	BioHC Half-Life
53	aeaeede6-6140-4d2c-a0cb-6cbffed9cd56	Biotransformation Half-Life
54	8ef98a7f-b34b-49f4-931c-08e451c410b7	Boiling point
55	c810f6a2-b524-42c0-8e7a-b90a21b8e7cb	Exp Boiling Point
56	9f32f266-c291-4a33-abf9-3a40f6093959	Exp Henrys Law Constant
57	c528e5b7-4af2-461b-b8f0-12fd3646c7c6	Exp Log P

58	d2042be6-b33f-425a-9c9e-676e079f23f5	Exp Melting Point
59	db67dc5d-8184-4f1e-ae06-59fd1d762759	Exp NO3 rate constant
60	a0177de0-be88-463e-ab7e-d29bc1b68625	Exp OH rate constant
61	425bac7f-e6e6-466f-9109-3f1b0fb29adc	Exp Ozone rate constant
62	e9860770-1101-44b1-8c4b-7bcd6186b29e	Exp Vapor Pressure
63	1566ef0c-4ac6-4b0b-aadf-a4f29e8f3367	Exp Water Solubility
64	d1746575-3733-47ee-a43a-2a127d281aa5	FM advection air
65	b38156ed-a833-45dc-8880-ed0d1dd35a29	FM advection sediment
66	183d2e2f-2dcd-48f6-8bd7-8311e32720c4	FM advection soil
67	55ffc4c8-a9fa-49bb-a48a-d795d1a5c097	FM advection time
68	6b60006b-6b4d-4239-bf78-edd57ca6b693	FM advection water
69	59558eb1-dc32-424c-84d7-d023148ae8a3	FM emissions air
70	f1cced06-0dd6-45df-8285-080cbe6c2f80	FM emissions sediment
71	9a447f9c-9d64-4984-9d55-a5284c26ad3c	FM emissions soil
72	46bfefbb-928d-4f37-8426-334ab675819e	FM emissions water
73	44520273-fabd-42c4-820f-43f4115eb28c	FM fugacity air
74	9d7410fb-591a-4b20-aa6d-6e9cf049418d	FM fugacity sediment
75	71162ccd-66e3-4342-83ec-9cba1a45671f	FM fugacity soil
76	53215389-fd91-4c8c-92e7-2c386814de61	FM fugacity water
77	ff199f03-2c7d-4f19-80aa-a7d5a07a024a	FM half-life air
78	e76930cc-706f-40a4-9d3b-8c77b9cb4eef	FM half-life sediment
79	0b471191-558f-45ab-9027-170045b01700	FM half-life soil
80	5f58d661-f8a7-4bcf-8e5d-8199ff5123e7	FM half-life water
81	7cfc1fe8-2f04-4f9b-9b9e-ee6e326ae002	FM mass amount air
82	f681a891-3b17-424e-88c3-0a332c274d00	FM mass amount sediment
83	ff29bccf-3944-48c7-9279-9f19db4a52d2	FM mass amount soil
84	e1bc24e7-73c2-4638-ae54-913a99308d10	FM mass amount water
85	a5145b2b-71db-4772-b30b-77df3bef6208	FM percent advected
86	f5623c51-9f40-4586-b74b-3d77e9e52bfc	FM percent reacted
87	923ae9b5-a5b3-420d-8fe5-dc8840a4a25f	FM persistence time
88	fad94e4e-c8d4-4650-8be5-98c31020eb98	FM reaction air
89	7b797845-457d-4d05-a540-40aa8ab6e536	FM reaction sediment

90	83b4bf49-eb54-43d1-b2fa-87f81ab04d63	FM reaction soil
91	bc616d24-d20d-4317-b243-a3c588fc8a33	FM reaction time
92	0f74b5fb-bc78-490e-816a-4ac01c3b4329	FM reaction water
93	a5aa91d5-6d28-4d51-88f3-0ec3e5133bed	GSH Reactivity
94	1f4dbfde-b9dd-448c-a2da-c949277e0dd6	Half-Life (Model Lake)
95	20cce1cd-8e39-46da-8c63-229691d5bbaf	Half-Life (Model River)
96	2d8063ed-0fc1-47d3-9932-db3790b0c696	Half-Life (Observed metabolism)
97	5231e80b-4ba3-493c-9e43-27ab2bee405d	Henry's Law Constant (Bond Method)
98	bcacf3d05-13b1-4adf-ae2-0ace456a4cd7	Henry's law Constant (Group Method)
99	7f667b37-8996-459d-bcd5-c1ea5f6b49c1	Hydrolysis half-life (pH 6.5-7.4)
100	925d9437-38a5-45b2-a632-6fd9ee0bc4c0	Ka Half-Life (pH 7)
101	dcfc8db9-b589-47c0-808a-d399aa9df64a	Ka Half-Life (pH 8)
102	c9a2e0a8-13fc-456a-80e9-ea138f7c13e9	Kb half-life (pH 7)
103	d74de08b-88f8-4987-8965-0cc8c7bcd4ad	Kb half-life (pH 8)
104	363136e6-bfa4-4f4c-8855-d08bf998da27	kM
105	617bc4ae-09c4-4ed1-b7b2-62e4ecab29be	Koc (Log Kow)
106	614e937a-1825-4aac-84b3-f0fbcac6c371	Koc (MCI)
107	de85401f-2ddc-437c-99a7-edfb637e1852	Kp (Mackay method)
108	2f290f09-d86d-41dc-b22e-e7102d7304b4	Kp (Octanol/air (Koa) model)
109	ebb921a6-a46a-4f13-9682-e06842d4ec47	Lipid Solubility
110	3ace2a92-d8df-4702-8e43-6a2c2d9d8698	log BCF max
111	80793efd-f61b-4a11-a2cd-509835c48695	Log Koa (Air-water partition coefficient model)
112	44dff8ec-d2eb-49d8-824a-70fc73a4e431	Log Koa (Henry's law constant model)
113	41552380-4d5d-4eab-bee0-03774c0eabb6	log Kow
114	6a2527dc-0e12-4404-8351-ace5154f42f3	Mean Melting Point
115	7b31e035-c1e0-4345-9626-00e17d0df158	Melting Point (Adapted Joback Method)
116	b044db97-2bee-4357-be63-000fcd481923	Melting point (Gold and Ogle method)
117	5af55e42-ba54-4133-8dd5-c21403075b40	Molar refraction I
118	6506737b-c005-4e39-94dd-d07ceff1f06d	Molar refraction II
119	5201c805-e2c7-49a2-bb50-d2dfc7eb8f16	Molecular Weight
120	2583b370-d47f-4a7c-9124-2a77e52025c6	Number of aromatic bonds

I21	cf4c1868-7175-4fd5-ae35-98bed29e43f1	Number of cyclic bonds
I22	7cbec8b9-f13b-431e-89ea-b427cbccdf5a	Number of double bonds
I23	4fc77382-852a-4267-812b-cc3addd2a871	Number of heavy atoms
I24	02c7deb7-8b97-42b0-8f10-b514bfed41b6	Number of nitro groups
I25	22bd1f84-e7b6-47bd-b063-70d6e0ac3ed4	Number of rings
I26	2f548a7a-5e28-431a-ab26-7c43f6813348	Number of single bonds
I27	0b4681d0-d53f-4fb8-ba7f-11ce430e706e	Number of single bonds (with H)
I28	7e2c037a-f7c5-49e7-a80e-0930ab5467c2	OVERALL OH Half-life
I29	730ad5f4-f29e-4dde-8ed2-0cf5afb698f4	OVERALL OH rate constant
I30	11d0eb5c-c12c-4454-b0d3-f941518ec8d4	OVERALL OZONE Half-life
I31	4b236c83-3ce9-4902-b7de-7efa2c2ab7bb	OVERALL OZONE rate constant
I32	d46b249c-11b4-4fb9-a147-b1bd815c4fdf	phi (Junge-Pankow model)
I33	39f0f6c8-96c1-4d3b-ad8c-8d6841f40676	phi (Mackay model)
I34	8021fad0-a401-475b-af69-0f7a5d2ec871	phi (Octanol/air (Koa) model)
I35	1c4f7a1d-5f60-46f1-822f-c740430c1c64	Primary biodeg (Biowin 4)
I36	8a60f10c-d448-415f-80e7-2410234d2dc3	Ready Biodegradability Prediction
I37	26d2aecb-bc27-425c-bbdd-5a988be02739	Relative number of N atoms
I38	9dc64fed-3cc1-413a-a62a-c4da7ae036a2	Selected Melting Point
I39	aee3c2be-eb11-4abc-8cf8-2c2175568d3b	Selected Vapor Pressure
I40	7ad07f45-3232-4c9e-abbd-aa13eea1f0f9	Similarity
I41	c3b10444-221a-424a-b00d-d50e1085db58	STP FM (Total biodegradation)
I42	277ef2b8-df72-4e74-a805-9c61aa1a9aad	STP FM (Total removal)
I43	927fccab-a942-472e-a2d0-96b989b9f6ce	Subcooled liquid Vapor Pressure
I44	caa133cb-e996-4593-81a1-d5db7c380b34	Surface Tension
I45	ec05e8c5-79b3-44cb-bbd8-144b646f3b57	Total Kb
I46	c4a6d74b-fa52-45d1-8e98-f329e6334a95	Ultimate biodeg (Biowin 3)
I47	7fbe8bfb-1425-4a11-8113-ec183203c073	Vapor Pressure (Antoine method)
I48	c7dc2a96-b737-48bf-8bf0-604469d2b482	Vapor Pressure (Mackay method)
I49	89be8944-dbf5-48a0-9d64-b851727a8996	Vapor Pressure (Modified Grain Method)
I50	fbdbb4ca-3ece-4047-9c74-6559e4b7fa4d	Water Solubility
I51	0cb28eb0-77e1-458d-91eb-35f294f0c32a	Water Solubility (fragments)

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